

The effect of corporate governance mechanisms on earnings management: UK Evidence

By

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Abstract

This study examines the relationship between corporate governance measures and earnings management in UK-listed corporations. While managers must behave in the best interests of shareholders, accounting flexibility permits them to prioritise their own needs. In response to high-profile company failure, the UK's Cadbury Report (1992) established principles to improve corporate governance, business performance, and investor trust. Board independence, limiting the CEO's dual function, board diversity, and financial reporting transparency are all important governance elements. This research examines the impact of different proxies of corporate governance, such as audit committee size, board independence, and female board member representation, on earnings management in a sample of 101 (FTSE 100) companies from 2019 to 2022. The findings reveal negative associations between board independence, audit committee size, and the proportion of female board members with earnings management practices. However, these relationships lack statistical significance. Previous studies have used data samples from companies worldwide, but UK-listed companies appear to have been overlooked. This study aims to fill this gap and contribute to the ongoing discourse on the efficiency of corporate governance in mitigating earnings management activities.

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Declaration

I hereby certify that this is my original work and that all sources used in this study are properly cited. Definitions or remarks of others are cited according to the university's guidelines, and this research is not published elsewhere.

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Abbreviations

AEM - Accrual-based Earning
Management

BCCI - Bank of Credit and Commerce
International

CEO - Chief Executive Officer

CFO - Chief Financial Officer

CG - Corporate Governance

EM - Earnings Management

FAME - Financial Analysis Made Easy

GAAP - Generally Accepted Accounting
Principles

IFRS - International Financial Reporting
Standards

IPO - Initial Public Offering

LSE - London Stock Exchange

PPE - Property, Plant, and Equipment

REM - Real Earning Management

R&D - Research and Development

SEC - Securities and Exchange

Commission

Chapter 1

Introduction

Businesses are created to generate profit, but their strategies vary widely. Private and public limited firms (listed on the stock exchange) operate differently. A private company is typically run by its owners (Jensen, 2019). On the other hand, listed companies are owned by their shareholders but run by their agents (directors). Therefore, a company's profitability and performance are shaped by the directors. Depending on the company's performance, directors are rewarded in various ways. In some cases, company directors may engage in activities that mislead shareholders or other stakeholders of the company by making unreliable financial statements to benefit themselves, thus damaging the company (Frankel, Johnson, and Nelson, 2002).

Moreover, shareholders can lose regular profits, dividends, and investments (Shleifer and Vishny, 1986). The reliability of company financial records has been questioned in light of recent financial crises (Fodio, Ibikunle, and Oba, 2013). As a result, countries have recognised the need to discover better ways of stopping firms from engaging in such practices. According to agency theory, directors are the agents of shareholders. As such, the UK's Corporate Governance Code was implemented in 1992 to strengthen this relationship's dependability and accountability. Messier, Glover, and Prawitt (2008) and Buyuksalvarci and Abdioglu (2010) characterised the corporate governance (CG) system as a direct control mechanism for organisations.

In addition, Tricker (2009) and the OECD (2004) define corporate governance as a sequence of interactions between a firm's governing body and its shareholders or other stakeholders. The Corporate Governance Code's rules and regulations make the board of the firm more accountable and responsible. Many nations have adopted CG practices in recent years

to regain investor confidence following multiple financial scandals. Examples of such Laws include the US Sarbanes-Oxley Act and the UK Corporate Governance Code. These scandals—which involve companies like WorldCom, Waste Management, Xerox, Enron, and Tyco—cast doubt on the organisation’s financial reporting. In particular, the companies’ investors started to doubt their financial accounts.

1.1. Background

This research defines earnings management (EM) as circumstances where directors misuse the UK’s generally accepted accounting principles (GAAP) or International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) to manipulate the company’s financial performance in their favour. Managerial involvement with accounting data is also known as “cosmetic accounting” or “accounting manipulation” (Maduagufor, 2008; Gao and Zhang, 2019). There has been an increasing focus on EM. Due to EM practices, financial results that do not accurately reflect a company’s financial performance are less reliable and can be misleading. Countries have also attempted to develop more effective rules and procedures to combat such detrimental activities.

The public no longer has faith in the integrity and dependability of publicly available financial information due to many, often high-profile, cases of corruption and scandals that auditors, investors, and regulators have observed over the years (Eilifsen *et al.*, 2010). Poor EM activities have been at the root of numerous bankruptcies, as demonstrated by the American cases of Enron and WorldCom. Better corporate governance helps gain investor confidence and produces reliable financial information. This study creates hypotheses to observe the connection between CG mechanisms and EM using financial data from UK-based businesses.

CG has become an attractive area for research in the past few decades. Examining international data, research has suggested that firms with a recognised CG policy perform better in fundamental areas of the business compared to firms without such a system (Orazalin, 2020;

Messier, Glover, and Prawitt, 2008; Chung, Firth, and Kim, 2002; Lin and Hwang, 2010; Skousen, Glover, and Prawitt, 2005; Davidson, Goodwin-Stewart, and Kent, 2005). The CG structure impacts several elements of the organisation (Alabdullah and Ahmed, 2020; Brown and Gorgens, 2009), including the business model, setting or achieving objectives, and risk and performance optimisation.

Business analysts tend to favour companies with a recognised CG system. Good CG procedures improve the credibility, openness, and accountability of the company (Jimoh and Iyoha, 2012). Financial statements' reliability and control over EM could be enhanced using CG mechanisms (La Porta *et al.*, 2002; Leuz, Nanda, and Wysocki, 2003). An organisation benefits from CG by building trust and confidence among its stakeholders and shareholders. It reduces the possibility of EM because of vital monitoring tools. The company's shareholders are more confident that they will obtain a respectable return on their investment thanks to CG rules (Shleifer and Vishny, 1986).

EM can undermine investors' confidence in financial statements, reducing the reliability of reported results and their use as a tool for investment decisions (Ruiz, 2016). Controlling owners and managers have a motive to distort reported results to conceal real business performance and their internal control benefits from outsiders. Therefore, this study investigates whether CG mechanisms can reduce EM activities. Researchers have described EM in various ways. Jackson and Pitman (2001) characterise EM as "*an intentional structuring of reporting or production decisions around the bottom line impact*". Schipper (1989) describes it as an intentional effort by managers to gain personal benefit while making financial reports.

To deceive interested stakeholders, firm directors employ subjective judgement to construct financial reports or modify financial accounts (Healy and Wahlen, 1999). "*Earnings management*" is the phrase used to describe managers' opportunistic activities that comply with UK generally accepted accounting principles (GAAP). "*Earnings manipulation*" refers to

managers' opportunistic activities outside the GAAP. EM influences contractual outcomes, which depend on the company's financial information. Academics often characterise EM as a manager's intentional involvement in external financial reporting to maximise personal profit. EM is depicted in this interpretation as a result of managers' earnings manipulation. Because accounting results are becoming increasingly relevant to the value of organisations, several valuation models use earnings to assess shares. The company's shareholders are the owners, and the directors are responsible for daily activities. The directors are also responsible for producing financial reports for the company.

The gap between shareholders and their agents (the directors) may be mitigated by utilising CG mechanisms. Consequently, corporate directors act in the shareholders' best interests (Gazi, 2009). It has been observed that reporting flexibility allows corporate managers to produce financial statements that might not be useful for their users (Habib, Uddin, and Islam, 2013; Campello *et al.*, 2011). EM may provide the false appearance of improved profitability, larger margins, and successful reorganisation (Ketola, 2009). Similarly, EM can assure managers by falsely demonstrating that the firm and the economy can achieve more significant results even during challenging times. As a result, executives engage in this behaviour to increase their profits and maintain their positions. Less EM is common in nations with advanced equity markets, dispersed ownership structures, considerable shareholder rights, and effective legal prosecution (Ketola, 2009). Not addressing EM has resulted in failed firms and the subsequent loss of employment and compensatory benefits for citizens.

Managers may employ reporting flexibility to manage earnings (Xie, Davidson and DaDalt, 2003). This negatively impacts reported profitability and significantly impacts decision-making. Additionally, managers could use EM to accomplish specific capital market goals, such as remuneration or exceeding expectations. The general assumption is that boards may be better able to regulate opportunistic EM if they have more independent non-executive

members. When independent non-executive directors, and executive directors are distributed equally throughout firm boards, accurate financial reporting is more likely (Karamanou and Vafeas, 2005).

This research paper is driven by CG mechanisms and intends to investigate whether these mechanisms work in real-world business environments. The problem identified, and the goals and objectives of this study are described in the following paragraphs. The literature review chapter includes information on EM and CG methods, their relationships, and the perspectives of other scholars.

1.2. Problem Statement

The concern that emerged following several noteworthy company failures has served as inspiration for this study. Therefore, it is crucial to understand the effectiveness of CG and how it relates to financial reports (Chambers, 1999; Tie, 1999). Following numerous high-profile corporate failures and accounting scams, the integrity of the financial statement has become an issue for professionals, governing bodies, economic analysts, and other interested third parties (Levitt, 1998; Gurung and Gupta, 2019). Financial statements are important documents for evaluating the performance of a company. They provide valuable information to users to assist them in making financial decisions.

Although financial statements can become unreliable because of EM, earlier studies have described EM as a “pervasive phenomenon” (Healy, 1985). They suggest many reasons managers engage with EM, such as contractual motivation. EM is harmful to the company, particularly to those who use its financial statements. However, this manipulation practice does not hurt the managers as much as it does the company’s shareholders. Hence, many countries have introduced safeguard procedures such as CG to tackle this problem.

A key factor contributing to business failure is the management of earnings. The Corporate Governance Code has many mechanisms to help reduce EM. These techniques include considering the number of directors who are independent, the number of female members, the board size, the audit committee size, an independent chairman, and others. The Corporate Governance Code suggests that these codes, together with others, helped the companies resolve problems with EM. Managers engage in EM tasks for various reasons, including reporting consistent earnings year over year, improving organisational performance to attract investors, lowering taxes, or increasing shareholders' wealth on paper in the hopes of attracting more investors. EM is mostly achieved through tampering with accounts for loan losses, unjustified write-offs, provisions for debt on the balance sheet and income statements, and by making use of particular accounting law gaps to deceive stakeholders (Bashir, 2017; Jones, 2011; Wu, 2016; Mahjoub and Miloudi, 2016).

Investors regard the reported earnings of failing firms as less credible and place a lower value on them. In contrast, they place a substantially higher value on successful firms' reported earnings. Insiders may be incentivised to falsify stated results to satisfy the stock market and attract new investors. This research paper finds EM a problem for businesses and intends to determine whether the CG mechanisms indicated earlier help reduce EM.

A company's board size plays a role in the running of the company. The company's board is comprised of all of the board members, including the executive directors, non-executive directors, the chairman, and the chief executive officer (CEO) (Shakir, 2008). The board's size for the firm could serve as a motivator for managing earnings. Any company performing poorly might manipulate earnings figures to meet its planned targets. The company's board might agree to engage in such activity to avoid reputation loss and save themselves (Sun *et al.*, 2013). This type of activity typically occurs when the company's board size is small and the members are known to each other. The Corporate Governance Code sets

rules for selecting board members. It suggests various board sizes based on the size of the company, independent directors from outside the corporation, and a particular number of independent directors. Additionally, board members must be appointed for a set period.

Researchers have also suggested that newly constituted boards can manipulate earnings to enhance their standing in the labour market (Fortin *et al.*, 2011; Ashiq and Weining, 2015). Boards of directors may engage in such activities to portray themselves and the company positively and to satisfy shareholders. Saving the company's reputation is also a motive for falsifying financial statements. By managing earnings, the board members aim to demonstrate their dedication to shareholders. How EM is carried out may be influenced by the board of directors and a variety of other corporate circumstances. Many intentions can motivate managers to manipulate earnings including incentives, pressure, attitudes, rationalisations, and opportunities (Mard, 2003).

When management or staff are under financial hardship or stress, they can be more inclined to commit fraud. Fraud in financial reporting is an attempt to cover up a purposeful misstatement made by those who create the financial reports. The benefit could be a specific gain (such as misappropriating assets and stealing small cash) or a distinct advantage (such as falsifying financial statements and fabricating sales to fulfil a goal). Individuals may be under pressure because of unrealistic performance goals and may be concerned about what will happen to them if the goals are not met.

Various conditions make it possible for fraud to be committed. It could be a position of power that someone can take advantage of, or it could be a failure of safeguards, such as the ability to issue checks to a personal bank account without a second person's approval. Individuals engaged can explain away carrying out a dishonest act. For instance, they can believe that because they work for a major corporation, what they are doing harms no one, and everybody does it; they are also able to do it. This study finds these behaviours of the manager

to be a problem for the company's survival. Thus, it wishes to test if the existing CG structure and its mechanisms help reduce the company manager's opportunistic behaviours.

To discover the relationships between CG characteristics and EM, the yearly reports of the listed companies on the London Stock Exchange (LSE) in the UK were examined. These firms must follow the 2010 Corporate Governance Code (ICAEW, 2017). The code was updated in 2018. It is used to boost investor trust and financial reporting quality. This research focused on several CG criteria, including the ratio of female board members, audit committee size, the board's independence, and the existence of an independent chairman. The modified Jones model will be used to examine the connection between discretionary accruals and EM.

1.3. Aims, Objectives, and Research Questions

The aims of this study are as follows:

- ▶ To identify if the current Corporate Governance Code (2018) serves its purpose.
- ▶ To analyse the traits of businesses that manipulate earnings and the factors that lead to these manipulations.
- ▶ To determine how CG mechanisms and EM are related.
- ▶ To assist investors or other third parties in understanding the organisation's financial reports before making any financial choices.
- ▶ According to the current needs, this study intends to highlight a better roadmap for implementing the CG mechanisms or framework.

CG was established to restore shareholder trust after several high-profile business incidents in recent times. Its purpose is to close the gap between corporate executives and shareholders. When company directors prioritise the interests of the shareholders, CG becomes more beneficial (Gazi, 2009; Mrabure and Abhulimhen-Iyoha, 2020). Although

managers' opportunistic behaviours may profit them personally, they harm the shareholders. CG elements are likely to lessen the incidence of such events and boost the trustworthiness of a firm's financial performance. Enron, WorldCom, and Tyco, among other company disasters in the USA, show how urgently corporate governance has to be improved. These businesses were well-regulated and located in highly effective capital markets.

Several regulations and codes have been introduced to decrease financial fraud and regain investors' confidence. The UK introduced the Corporate Governance Code as a result of the 1992 Cadbury Report (Cohen, Dey, and Lys, 2008). In this study, the links between EM and CG practices are investigated using data from UK-listed businesses. As one of the first countries to launch corporate governance mechanisms, few studies have measured whether these mechanisms work for the firms listed within the country. The solutions to the queries listed in the research questions section are crucial to the efficient operation of financial markets. Investors may see improved returns, auditors may avoid expensive lawsuits, analysts may avoid reputational damage, and regulators may see improved investor protection and fewer disastrous investments by finding the answers to those questions. The primary objectives of this study are:

- To discover the factors that affect managing earnings.
- To analyse how CG practices affect the management of earnings.
- To study the financial information of 101 companies listed as the FTSE 100 on the LSE from 2019 to 2022 and determine whether CG practices introduced in the UK impact or hinder EM within these firms.

Similar to other research, the following inquiry is used to assess this study's hypotheses (Francis and Yu, 2009; DeAngelo, 1981; Gul, Fung, and Jaggi, 2009; Dechow, Sloan, and Sweeney, 1996; Becker *et al.*, 1998; Francis and Wang, 2008; Mrabure and Abhulimhen-Iyoha,

2020). Most of this previous research did not use UK-listed firms in their data sample. This study uses FTSE 100 companies as a data sample to test the hypotheses.

Question 1. How do current CG mechanisms improve investor trust?

Question 2. Do CG mechanisms help to reduce EM activities?

Question 3. Are CG mechanisms mandatory for the company to follow, or can they be avoided?

1.4. Motivation and Contribution of the Research

As one of the first countries in the world to introduce CG mechanisms, it is assumed that businesses within the UK have sound CG mechanisms to restrict EM activities. Since the launch of the Corporate Governance Code, it has been updated regularly to maintain its suitability and meet investor's needs. The 2018 Corporate Governance Code (the Code) is the latest of its kind for businesses to follow. The primary motive of this research is to discover the link between CG elements and EM. The size of the company board, audit committee size, board independence, an independent chairman, and the existence of female directors are just a few of the numerous CG issues associated with EM explored in this research. Company governance was formed in many nations; however, because of inadequate CG practices, profit management and fraudulent actions still occur (Demaki, 2011; Larcker and Tayan, 2020). Numerous studies have investigated how different elements of the company governance structure relate to EM (Jiang and Anandarajan, 2009; Berthelot, Coulmont, and Serret, 2012; Demirkan and Platt, 2009).

Users use data provided by financial experts as a tool. The financial accountant delivers financial statement information to various consumers. Many of these consumers have a wide range of information requirements. Accounting data would have been subjected to several

procedures before reaching readers (mostly shareholders and investors), ranging from management staff engagement to the board of directors' responsibilities to guarantee that the firm's accounts are finalized. Financial managers do not always adhere to the fairness established by the firms' standards when making this financial information available to different users. As indicated earlier, cosmetic accounting or EM describes how some renowned companies' financial reports have exaggerated information (Maduagufor, 2008; Ejaz, Jalal, and Fayyaz, 2022). This accounting violation frequently aims to mislead stakeholders, particularly investors and financial experts.

Earnings smoothing, creative accounting, and window dressing are all synonyms of cosmetic accounting (Amat, Gowthorpe, and Perramon, 2005; Griffiths, 1986; Merchant and Rockness, 1994; Karim, 2021). Accounting tricks rather than authentic economic growth were to blame for a large portion of the business enterprises' apparent gain in profits in the United Kingdom during the 1980s, according to Smith (1992). Smith used the example of a private business called Brentford Nylon, which failed soon after declaring a profit of £130,000 but was eventually acquired by another organisation called Lonrho. This is one of several scenarios found in EM. How can a company that declared financial success at one point in time suddenly fail? This is the question that immediately pops into everyone's heads.

CG is required due to agency issues caused by the partition of management and ownership. Good CG is characterised by openness in company activities, prompt disclosure of accurate information, management and board of directors accountability to shareholders, active cooperation between firms and stakeholders, and corporate responsibility to stakeholders.

Previous studies assert that reasonable CG procedures can aid in limiting how corporations manage their earnings (Xie, Davidson, and DaDalt, 2003). The proportion of independent board members is an effective alternative for evaluating the efficiency of board performance and internal CG. Independent directors are more qualified to monitor and control

the management of the business, which lowers the possibility of managers misappropriating funds against the interests of shareholders. More active boards and audit committees function as effective watchdogs of the company's financial statements, deterring EM, as earlier writers had discovered. CG is mainly focused on the board of directors, and the board's organisational structure affects how well it performs its duties (Fama and Jensen, 1983). External directors, they argue, are more competent at supervising management and will not collude with it.

Outside directors support the governance activities of the board due to the division of ownership and control. Earlier research on the board's duties focuses on the connection between business success and board attributes. Management buyouts with outside directors in charge result in increased value for shareholders (Lee *et al.*, 1992; Arena, Dewally, and Peck, 2020). Outside directors can reject the suggestion and prevent a takeover (Kosnik, 1987 and 1990). When challenged by outside directors, the directors appear to be more inclined to retire owing to substandard performance (Weisbach, 1988), and director remuneration negatively correlates with the number of outside directors (Brickley and James, 1987). An effective board of directors can dramatically lower agency expenditures. What motivates managers to invent false reports? For the benefit of shareholders, financiers, auditors, financial experts, and legislators, what are the best techniques to spot fake earnings reports? The effective operation of the capital markets depends on finding answers to these questions. Positive responses will safeguard people.

Investors may see improved returns, auditors may avoid expensive lawsuits, analysts may avoid reputational damage, and regulators may see improved investor protection and fewer catastrophic investments. The degree to which managers manipulate reported profitability for their gain is a critical problem in accounting studies. Several studies examined the factors influencing accounting choices in the 1970s and the early 1980s. They produced data that supported managers' decisions to report earnings in ways that were advantageous under contractual and regulatory requirements (Holthausen and Leftwich, 1983; Watts and

Zimmerman, 1978). Studies on the motivations of managers to manipulate profits have mostly focused on accruals since the 1980s. Managers are likely to use a range of techniques to carry out EM tasks, such as accrual-based EM (AEM).

Three factors may be responsible for the increase in research on AEM. Initially, as accruals are the main focus of accounting rules, they are more likely to be influenced by EM. Cash flow components are less probable. Secondly, understanding accruals lessens the impact of problems brought on by the challenge of determining how different accounting decisions affect profits (Watts and Zimmerman, 1990; Michalkova, 2021). Finally, investors are less likely to tell how EM affects reported results if it is an unobservable component of accruals.

The inability of academics, investors, or other interested parties to monitor or quantify the accruals component of EM is a fundamental difficulty for academics studying EM. Increasing compensation, avoiding covenant default, generating capital, or influencing a regulatory result are examples of managerial accounting actions that are typically unobservable. Given the weak estimates of managerial discretion provided by the current models of anticipated accruals, it is unclear if unobservable EM operations occur. Despite issues with the research design, a growing body of evidence suggests EM.

The contribution of this study is to comprehend more in-depth EM and the mechanisms underpinning earnings manipulation. Discretionary accrual approaches have been extensively used in empirical research on EM. However, specific accruals and how they might be used to identify earnings manipulation have received very little attention. It is somewhat surprising, given the adverse effects accompanying the revelation of a corporation that manipulates earnings. This study intends to close this knowledge gap by learning more because a firm is thought to have broken accounting regulations in significant EM scenarios.

The term 'earnings management' or 'earnings manipulation' is not well defined by current research or auditing standards. The line between managing earnings and manipulating earnings is, therefore, unclear. According to the findings of this study, EM involves using managerial decisions to approve accounting judgements and estimates that are in line with the accurate and fair view concept. This study defines EM as the outcome of executives' actions that contravene the accurate and honest viewpoint principle and ignore the applicable accounting standards. The literature review chapter comprehensively examines CG and EM from various points of view.

Many academics have tried to determine how certain elements of CG and EM relate to one another. For instance, Orazalin (2020) examined board gender diversity; Francis (2011) examined the quality of the audit; Beasley (1996) examined the makeup of the board; Piot and Janin (2007) examined the audit committee; Leuz, Nanda, and Wysocki (2003) examined investor protection; Betzer and Theissen (2009) examined insider trading; and Agrawal and Chadha (2005) examined the reputations of the auditors. Studies by Peasnell, Pope, and Young (2005), Beasley (1996), Marra, Mazzola, and Prencipe (2011), and Klein (2002), among others, have shown that firms with more independent non-executive board members tend to engage in less EM. The earlier finding comes from studies among US and UK enterprises. Companies from the UK that are registered on the LSE were used to collect samples for this study.

Many studies have been conducted since the introduction of CG mechanisms. However, most recent studies did not use UK-listed companies as a sample to conduct their analysis. For example, Al-Haddad and Whittington (2019) used Jordan-based firms; El Diri, Lambrinouidakis, and Alhadab (2020) used US-based firms; Orazalin (2020) used Kazakhstan-based firms; Puni and Anlesinya (2020) used Ghana-based firms; and Saona, Muro, and Alvarado (2020) used Spain-based firms as a sample in their study. UK firms as a sample seem absent from most of the current research. This study intends to reduce this gap by using UK-

listed firms as a sample to analyse and discover if the latest CG mechanisms (2018) help reduce EM activities.

1.5. Overview of the Research

The structure of this study begins with an abstract, followed by an acknowledgement and declaration. Chapter 1 introduces the study. It addresses the research background, problem, aims, objectives, questions, motivation, and contribution of the research. Chapter 2 addresses the literature associated with this investigation and discusses the findings of previous researchers. The chapter also describes CG, CG mechanisms, EM, and ways of EM. The hypotheses used in this research to explore the relationships between CG mechanisms and EM are discussed. Also outlined is the research gap this study intends to reduce. Chapter 3 outlines the research approach. It discusses the data or sample that was used to assess the hypotheses. This chapter summarises the overall research approach and technique used in this research. It also includes explanations of the models, formulas, and variables used in the study. It includes access and ethical issues of this research and how they were considered to maintain the rules and regulations set by the university. Chapter 4 addresses the findings of this study and discusses them in the context of other researchers' findings. It addresses the problems or limitations encountered during the research. Chapter 5 concludes this research paper. It discusses the strategy, methods, and findings throughout the study to compare it with similar existing research. This chapter includes the study's shortcomings and recommendations for future investigation. The references used in this research are listed alphabetically at the end of the paper.

Chapter 2

Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

2.1. Introduction

This chapter aims to highlight the literature explored in this study and assess whether academics have discovered links between CG practices and EM. The chapter also inspects the relationship between CG practices and EM within the study by others. Arthur Levitt, the (former) Chairman of the United States Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), criticised the methods of some public businesses for managing their revenues and smoothing out their income (Levitt, 1998). This chapter examines the findings and a conceptual framework for EM and manipulation. Turner and Godwin (1999) discussed some of the measures being undertaken in the SEC Chief Accountant's Office to help achieve the goals mentioned in Chairman Levitt's statement more than a decade ago.

According to Benston and Hartgraves (2002), the Enron crisis brought attention to accounting manipulation for everyone, including the general public. CG is a technique that helps businesses operate better and produce reliable financial reporting. Various stakeholders used it later on in the decision-making process. Effective CG procedures boost investor trust, while investor trust might be lowered by applying a lower degree of CG (Leng, 2004; Rahman and Haniffa, 2005). Prior researchers have mainly employed AEM to analyse earning manipulation (Liu, 2020).

Managers frequently employ a range of ways to achieve their objectives but in many different ways. When managing real activity-based earnings, managers usually subtract the actual costs incurred from the earnings for the financial year (Roychowdhury, 2006). Many investigations were conducted into this topic. This study examined the connection between EM

and the mechanisms of CG using listed companies on the LSE. There have been many different results in the past. For instance, some scholars contend that board independence and profits management have a negative relationship (Davidson, Goodwin-Stewart, and Kent, 2005; Klein, 2002; Saona, Muro, and Alvarado, 2020). Others claim they have no meaningful connection (Park and Shin, 2004). Later in this chapter, these discrepancies are explained.

2.2. Theoretical Framework

An agent's and a principal's goals are not the same. Managers are employed to serve the interests of the shareholders, who seek dividends from their investments. However, the reality of the situation suggests that directors could act in their best interests, which would harm shareholders. Managers may meet their objectives without enhancing the performance of their companies by using a different accounting approach, either GAAP or IFRS. A CG framework was implemented to stop such behaviour and boost business success.

This study aims to examine how CG practices affect the UK's tradition of using discretionary accruals to regulate earnings. The rising global attention on excellent CG mechanisms and EM is what prompted this study. Previous studies suggested that management might use accounting decisions that boost revenue to hide unfortunate results (Orazalin, 2020; Habib, Uddin, and Islam, 2013; Campello, Graham, and Harvey, 2011). Furthermore, any company's management can use the flexibility of both IFRS and GAAP to select from various accounting procedures for computing profit and other accounting performance outcomes, which may decrease financial reporting quality (Makar, Alam, and Pearson, 2000).

A deeper comprehension of CG and its workings is necessary. The relationship between EM and CG mechanisms received less attention in recent UK-based research. The current study seeks to fill this gap in the literature by proving the impact of CG mechanisms on EM in the

UK. The motivation for this study is the CG standards that sustain users' trust in the accuracy of financial reporting.

2.2.1. Foundational Theories

Many theories describe the contractual arrangement between the management and the owner, including their respective obligations, how conflicts of interest arise between them, and how to reduce them. This study, guided by agency and ethical theory, aims to discover the effects of CG mechanisms, including audit committee size, board size, board independence, independent chairman, and female board members on EM.

2.2.1.1. Agency Theory

Agency theory describes how the owner or investor wants the management or agents to maximise their financial returns and how managers desire to pursue their interests (Raimo *et al.*, 2021). That leads to agency problems. This theory is generally recognised in accounting, auditing, and other social science subjects. According to Jensen and Meckling (2019), managers may make choices that are in opposition to corporate shareholders' interests, and there may be conflicts of interest between investors and corporate managers. The market constantly reacts to conflicts of interest between shareholders and management, which causes agency equity costs to rise. The loss of company value that impacts the market price of stock can be referred to as agency cost of equity.

The connection between shareholders and management is established under the agency concept. The connection arising when investors or shareholders hire managers to execute part of their duties for them is what Jensen and Meckling (2019) call the theory's main principle. The need for managers and owners to pursue distinct interests results in agency costs. The issue arises when the owner grants the manager decision-making power in the belief that the manager would work to further the interests of the shareholders. The principal's aims

may not be the only objectives managers seek, which frequently causes issues for the organisation.

The asymmetry dilemma emerges between shareholders and managers because the agent has access to knowledge that shareholders do not. Since managers can fabricate reports on company activities entrusted to them by shareholders, it is challenging for shareholders to foresee the behaviour and actions of their managers. To make a profit before the term ends, managers provide false information regarding the assets, obligations, and risks taken in the company. Likewise, as indicated by previous writers, agency conflicts develop between owners and managers due to disparities in the aims to be attained.

The basic conflict of interests between shareholders and the governing body causes agency costs to increase. Monitoring costs are the monetary value used to ensure that directors behave in the best interests of shareholders (Deegan, Rankin, and Voght, 2000). Expenses incurred to prevent directors from acting dishonestly include the cost of the audit committee's work and CG structures. Bonding expenditures are benefits realised when management takes actions that benefit shareholders. The value that owners and management would be required to pay if the monitoring and bonding procedures are ineffective is known as residual expenditure.

To put it another way, it is the agency loss caused by managers' actions that causes a decline in the value of shareholders because of conflicts between them. The dispute between owners and managers can undoubtedly affect the accuracy of the accounting information, directly affecting the company's worth.

2.2.1.2. Ethical Theory

According to the ethical theory of business, managers often adhere to a high level of behaviour because they have a purpose to be sincere, genuine, and ethical in their commercial actions (Jamnik, 2019). According to academic research on ethical conduct or corporate social responsibility, a manager has an ethical obligation to “do the right thing” (Jones, 1995; Carroll, 1979; Phillips, Pincus, and Rego, 2003; Donaldson and Preston, 1995). For instance, the local communities (operating environment) may demand greater social responsibility spending from a corporation if it reports a big profit. Similar to how reported corporate profit may be influenced by ethical theory, theoretical studies indicated earlier suggest that managers should “do the right thing” if the business reports significant profits since investors would anticipate higher dividend payouts. This will help to reduce EM.

2.2.2. Corporate Governance (CG) Definition

The Cadbury Report led to the implementation of the Corporate Governance Code in the UK in 1992. As in other countries, this system was launched as a guideline for companies to follow and avoid corporate failure, and it was introduced with two goals in mind. Maximisation of long-term prosperity for the organisation and generating long-term value for the country’s stakeholders, stockholders, and employees (Larcker and Tayan, 2020). The strategy addresses the rising lack of trust in some areas of financial reporting before looking at methods to raise CG standards. More efficient governance processes and practices are thought to enhance company performance. To do this, the committee outlined recommended governance methods in a code of best practices included in its report. Such a system exists in several nations globally under various names. The architect of the Cadbury Report, Sir Adrian Cadbury, defines CG as “*the system by which companies are directed and controlled*” (Cadbury, 1992).

Comparing this, the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) defined CG as “*a set of relationships between a company’s management, its board, its shareholders and other stakeholders. Corporate governance also provides the structure through which the objectives of the company are set, and the means of attaining those objectives and monitoring performance are determined*” (OECD, 2004). These definitions help explain the primary motivation behind creating corporate governance regulations. According to some evidence (Conyon and Mallin, 1997), UK corporations have generally followed the recommendation of the Cadbury Report about specific governance arrangements.

Promoting outstanding CG among the top publicly listed UK companies is the primary goal of the code of best practices (Cadbury Committee, 1992). The failure of a few well-known companies, such as Polly Peck and the Bank of Credit and Commerce International (BCCI), exposed issues with director supervision and led to the creation of the Cadbury Committee. The Cadbury Committee extensively consulted with the board of directors, trade groups, institutional shareholders, and other interested parties.

Businesses are under great pressure to follow its regulations. Although compliance is voluntary, companies listed on the LSE are required to explain any violations in their annual reports. The principal-agent theory justifies Cadbury’s policy (Jensen and Meckling, 2019). The agency hypothesis contends that directors or managers may make decisions that do not improve profitability due to the division of owners and management. According to the agency concept, internal control systems will aid in ensuring directors make decisions that maximise shareholder wealth. These include dividing the position of chairman and CEO. Duality would result if the chairman and CEO responsibilities were merged since they were found to be the two most significant boardroom seats (Weir and Laing, 2001).

Independent non-executive directors oversee the decisions made by the executive directors (Jaggi, Leung, and Gul, 2009; Bencomo, 2021). Executive directors work

for the firm full-time, whereas independent directors work part-time. Independent directors have the same voting rights as executive directors at board meetings. As a result, they have the right to object to initiatives they think would hurt shareholders' interests. Following a period of subpar performance, independent directors could try to have some of the executive directors removed. Sometimes, executive directors of other publicly listed companies also serve as independent or non-executive directors.

Therefore, to preserve their reputation, it is in their best interests to guarantee that all decisions are made with shareholders' interests in mind. Cadbury states there should be at least three non-executive board members in large UK-listed firms. According to this concept, the board's decision will be impacted by a sizeable enough group of individuals. Cadbury suggests the formation of various board committees, such as remuneration and audit committees. He also suggested that non-executive or independent directors participate in the committees and report their findings to the board because they offer an unbiased perspective on crucial choices.

On the other hand, the remuneration committee's main duty is to recommend the executive directors' salaries and other forms of remuneration depending on their performance. The compensation committee has to be allowed the independence to make choices on its own to create adequate pay plans that would attract and inspire executive directors and safeguard shareholders' interests. The audit committee is in charge of supervising the balance sheet's external audit and any new auditing concerns. Audit and compensation committees are believed to motivate the board to perform better since they monitor the board's effectiveness, thus increasing investors' confidence in the accuracy of the accounting records.

The codes address both the company's internal and exterior aspects. Their monitoring and goal-achieving methods are employed to monitor activity. Agency theory highlights a conflict of interest involving the company's directors and stockholders. The

corporation is regulated and overseen through CG mechanisms to prevent managers from acting opportunistically. As suggested by La Porta *et al.* (1997), CG is “*a set of mechanisms through which outside investors protect themselves against expropriation by the insiders*”.

In contrast, CG was identified by Arsoy and Crowther (2008) as the link between the firm, its stakeholders, and its shareholders. At first, the difference between ownership and control of CG appeared to lessen possible conflicts between shareholders and management (Baydoun *et al.*, 2012). The agency framework demonstrates how internal control strategies, such as having more non-executive directors, reducing dual roles, and forming board subcommittees, help directors effectively implement plans to boost shareholder wealth.

CG provides improved stakeholder interactions and safeguards the interests of the company’s investors (La Porta *et al.*, 2000; Arsoy and Crowther, 2008). Owner-manager conflicts of interest are avoided through CG by separating ownership and control, according to Baydoun *et al.* (2012). CG is an internal framework of policies, practices, and personnel that directs and controls managerial activities in a fair, unbiased, and ethical manner to satisfy the requirements of shareholders and other stakeholders, as defined by O’Donovan (2003). A robust board culture that upholds guidelines and procedures is essential for excellent CG, as is outside legislation and market commitment. CG safeguards stakeholders’ interests (Shleifer and Vishny, 1997). CG is described by La Porta *et al.* (2002) as an additional set of protections offered by CG for external shareholders to stop insiders from taking benefit of them. These processes encompass a wide range of applicable rules, standards, and functions.

CG is an important subject from a practical aspect (Shleifer and Vishny, 1997; Almashhadani and Almashhadani, 2022). Easterbrook, Fischel, and Romano rated the American CG system favourably in their 1991 and 1993 evaluations, respectively. Previous studies, such as that of Roe (1993) and Charkham (1994), recommended substituting German and Japanese systems for American and British CG procedures. Italian companies’ CG is less

developed than other European nations with superior CG regimes (Barca, 1995; Pagano *et al.*, 1995). Many emerging economies have no CG structures at all, according to Boycko *et al.* (1995). Improvements in CG are not essential since companies might adopt corporate governance due to competition to minimise their cost of capital, as suggested by Alchian (1950) and Stigler (1958).

The research on market competitiveness mentioned above appears accurate, whereas this new method could require more effort. This process could harm stakeholders who have already invested in the company and may lose their investment. These stakeholders also seek to guarantee that they get certain returns from businesses. Regulations must be imposed in addition to market competition to improve CG. Thanks to poor CG, insiders can get funding from markets and governments (La Porta *et al.*, 2000). Law improvements may impede insiders' special interests if CG is effective. For instance, the US government enacted securities market legislation to promote company disclosure in 1933. Inadequate disclosures of asset fair values brought about the US Great Depression in 1929. According to Beaudreau (2005), this factor also had a small role in the 1929 stock market crash while passing the Smoot-Hawley Tariff Act.

Additionally, contracts between managers and shareholders may specify that the managers must provide accounting data so that the financial providers may keep an eye on their interests and wealth. According to Watts and Zimmerman (1986), the managers who provide this information can opt to use their predictions and accounting principles to artificially inflate the financial statement results. With the aid of CG, contracts may be more effective, and the agency issue between shareholders and managers could be lessened (Gompers, Ishii, and Metrick, 2003). This agency problem can result in higher expenses for shareholders, even in businesses in wealthy nations.

According to Makar *et al.* (2000) and Hlel, Kahloul, and Bouzgarrou (2020), managers can choose between IFRS and GAAP accounting standards, which offers them more freedom in calculating earnings. Prior research also revealed that managers might use accounting flexibility to conceal the company's bad performance by inflating income figures (Habib *et al.*, 2013; Campello *et al.*, 2011). It is anticipated that the Corporate Governance Code will guarantee financial reporting integrity and emphasise the board's fiduciary responsibility to give shareholders accurate financial information (Peasnell, Pope, and Young, 2000; Ananchotikul, Kouwenberg, and Phunnarungsi, 2010).

The significance of internal governance procedures, particularly those related to the composition of the board and subcommittees, has been highlighted in several earlier studies looking at the governance of UK corporations (Greenbury, 1995; Hampel, 1998; Cadbury, 1992). Publicly traded companies must use the internal governance frameworks recommended by a Code of Best Practice, according to Cadbury. Even though it was voluntary, companies were expected to apply the governance frameworks suggested by the Corporate Governance Code. Additionally, the LSE requires all listed businesses to include information about Corporate Governance Code compliance in their yearly reports. If management chooses not to use the proposed structure, the board must provide shareholders with clear information. Furthermore, most of the board-related governance measures in the UK are prescriptive.

Since ownership and control are divided in today's economic climate, some form of CG is required. Through this framework, managers are monitored and controlled to cut down on agency expenses and match managers' priorities with those of shareholders. According to Messier, Glover, and Prawitt (2008), CG is a system "*consisting of all the people, processes and activities to help ensure stewardship over an entity's assets*". However, there is no definition that everyone can agree on. A strong CG framework can enable management to

use the company's resources in the best interests of its owners. Additionally, to openly report the business's financial and operational results.

Unfortunately, the link between usefulness measures for CG and EM has received little support from quantitative research (Black *et al.*, 2023). As an illustration, studies by Peasnell, Pope, and Young (2005) and Park and Shin (2004) that looked for a connection between board independence and EM turned up nothing. However, Klein (2002) and Davidson, Goodwin-Stewart, and Kent (2005) assert a very negative association. Empirical data on the connections between EM and other board performance components in terms of keeping an eye on management in the accounting information system also demonstrate this gap. The board of directors regularly assign significant projects to other committees. For instance, the audit committee oversees the accounting processes.

2.2.3. Mechanisms of Corporate Governance

The UK's CG system includes a Code of Best Practice (2018) that focuses on suggested internal governance mechanisms (Solomon, 2020). Giving individual businesses more opportunity to select the governance mechanisms that work best for their unique situations would be an alternative strategy, such as in the USA. Companies choose the best internal governance arrangements if given the opportunity (Agrawal and Knoeber, 1996). Unfortunately, reduced flexibility will result in a standardisation of internal governance mechanisms, making it more challenging to determine which is the most appropriate. Fundamental public policy issues brought up the benefits of establishing internal governance processes.

Therefore, it will be difficult to identify internal governance weaknesses that might lead to poor performance if firms adopt Cadbury's strategy and implement comparable internal controls. This paper discusses the problem of little research being done to evaluate the

effects of subcommittee structure on performance. This contrasts with Dalton *et al.* (1998) and Bhagat and Black (1998). In the UK context, there must be empirical data given the importance that the Code of Best Practice accords board subcommittees.

Internal corporate governance mechanisms, such as insider holdings, board composition, independent director representation, director qualifications, audit and compensation committees, and ownership structures, all influence internal business operations. According to the earlier study, numerous academics examined various CG mechanisms to assess EM. For example, Orazalin (2020) conducted a study using board gender diversity as a proxy; Park and Shin (2004) and Liu and Lu (2007) conducted a study on the board of directors; Saleh and Iskandar (2007) and Nelson and Devi (2013) conducted a study on the audit committee; and combined research on ownership concentration, audit committee, and the board of directors was conducted by Siregar and Utama (2008). There are more internal CG procedures that help the organisation avoid failing.

The two top board seats should not be held by the same person, as per the organisation of the corporate board; for instance, Cadbury's proposed chairman and CEO positions. Cadbury noted that two more structural processes are particularly significant. First, there should be enough non-executive directors to influence board decisions significantly. Lastly, the board subcommittees are necessary for the company. He also highlighted the need for non-executive and independent directors. The committee's proposals, notably those regarding establishing board subcommittees, have received widespread acceptance (Conyon and Mallin, 1997).

Additional adjustments to board-related mechanisms have been made due to compliance, as observed by Young (2000) and Laing and Weir (1999). They show that listed businesses in the UK have raised the number of board subcommittees, lowered the prevalence of dualities, and grown the amount of non-executive board members since the publication of

the Cadbury Report. For instance, remuneration committees and audit committees are frequently seen. The UK Corporate Governance Code consequently prioritised the internal structure of CG mechanisms. Studies like those by Kini, Kracaw, and Mian (1995) and Rediker and Seth (1995) offer evidence that CG measures are not autonomous but rather function as an alternative. According to Agrawal and Knoeber (1996), this interconnection is missed if the importance of just one governance mechanism and a small group of governance mechanisms is highlighted.

Studies on CG frequently overemphasise the significance of internal CG practices at the expense of external CG procedures. The market for corporate control is one external mechanism of CG. The composition of the board structure is an important instrument since it allows non-executive directors to monitor executive directors' activities and confirm that they pursue plans in the best interests of shareholders (Fama, 1980). Peasnell, Pope, and Young (1998) state that non-executive directors comprise 44% of UK boards, compared to independent directors' 31% share. Furthermore, Vafeas and Theodorou (1998) estimate that non-executive directors make up an average of 39% of UK boards, with independent directors making up 33% of those boards. As a result, executive directors represent a definite dominance on the UK boards.

On the other hand, outside directors are more common in US corporations, with an average of 76% recorded by Bhagat and Black (1998) and 77% by Klein (1998). Due to these distinctions, outside directors in the USA appear to be in a better position than their counterparts in the UK to monitor executive director actions; hence, care would need to be taken when extrapolating findings from the US study to the UK. Non-executive directors can perform their monitoring duty because they have two qualities. First, their autonomy (Cadbury, 1992) and second, they are concerned with maintaining favourable labour-market sentiment (Fama and Jensen, 1983).

2.2.3.1. Mechanisms Related to the Company Board

The corporate board of the firm is accountable for overseeing management. The board is an excellent CG structure, in principle. Top management was given authority by the company's board, which the shareholders elected to represent them. Along with overseeing management performance, the board also gave its approval for any actions that went against its duty to treat shareholders with reasonable care. Shareholders can remove and replace board members who fail to control managers' activities adequately. This research concentrates on the size of the company board, board independence, an independent chairman, audit committee size, and the proportion of female board members as per common-law nations, which are thought to have stronger CG.

In the USA, there are several concerns, including the size and makeup of the boards, the participation of independent directors, and whether the CEO and Chairman are identical people. Prior research has been done on board structure measurement in CG worldwide. When considering stock returns, operating performance, and sales growth, external directors can stabilise and somewhat improve business performance (Kaplan and Minton, 1994). Turnover increased in the UK when the Corporate Governance Code went into effect, which required that a different person hold the positions of chairman and CEO. Additionally, there was a rise in the responsiveness of turnover to production, as supported by Dahya *et al.* (2002). Hossain *et al.* (2001) discovered a connection between better performance in New Zealand and the ratio of outside directors.

The CEO duality is another essential internal CG mechanism referenced in many studies. Many authors define CEO duality as the sharing of liabilities between the chairman and the CEO of the firm (Dahya and Travlos, 2000; Weir and Laing, 2001; Cadbury, 1992). The chairman is in charge of managing the board's activities, while the CEO is in charge

of carrying out board decisions and managing the business daily. Because of this, dualistic businesses could have a firm figure with the authority to make choices that do not continuously optimise shareholder wealth. As a result, the positions of chairman and CEO should be divided. However, according to stewardship theory, the CEO's dual role might enhance a strong and cohesive leadership rather than undermine the board of directors' independence from management and its oversight role (Al-Rahahleh, 2017; Sheikh *et al.*, 2013).

News of new CG compliance in Spain triggered a positive market response (Rodriguez and Anson 2001). A significant CG measure that can help a company reduce managers' opportunistic behaviour and minimise EM is creating a board of directors. The board comprises executive and non-executive members (including independents) assisted by the audit committee, remuneration committee, nominating committee, and other committees. It also contains information about the qualifications, competency, and skillsets of the board and the proportion of female members. Internal CG practices, for example, board meeting frequency and the percentage of independent board members, were also considered (Bertrand and Mullainathan, 2003). Independent directors act as a watchdog to keep an eye on the company's managers and prevent them from stealing money from shareholders.

Better CG would result from more independent directors controlling the management. The NYSE has defined the term "*independent*". The listed company may not pay independent directors more than \$120,000 in remuneration each fiscal year (Man and Wong, 2013). They must not be connected in any way, either directly or indirectly, to the firm, its shareholders, or any offices of affiliated groups with the listed company. A further requirement for independent directors is that they cannot be employed now or have previously worked for the listed firm within the last three years. The auditors of the firm should not be linked to independent directors. Furthermore, a listed company executive officer participating on the

remuneration committee who is not employed by a company that paid the listed company more than \$1 million in the previous three years should not be an independent director.

There are comparable definitions of independence in other common-law countries. The researchers have suggested that the frequency of board meetings and board composition are appropriate indicators of how well CG mechanisms work to control managerial behaviour (Adams, 2000). The board must continue to enforce laws effectively. Independent directors must carry out their responsibilities of overseeing managers' behaviour to prevent managers from acting in a way that is different to the benefits of the shareholders. Board meeting frequency is a reliable indicator for assessing the efficiency of internal CG and board performance. Adams (2000) contends that the consistency of board meetings significantly impacts the board's efficacy in carrying out its responsibilities, such as monitoring managers' behaviour. The presence of a nominating committee would ensure that each candidate for director has the necessary training and expertise, which is anticipated to enhance the calibre of financial statements (Ruigrok *et al.*, 2006). On boards, women are becoming increasingly represented.

The Catalyst (2007-2012) data reveal that among US Fortune 500 companies, women held 16.6% of board seats in 2012 compared to 16.1%, 15.7%, 15.2%, 15.2%, and 14.86% in 2011, 2010, 2009, 2008, and 2007, respectively. In Australia's ASX200 firms in 2012, women controlled over 12.3% of board seats compared to 8.4% in 2010 and 8.3% in 2007. According to figures released by EOWA (2010), in 2009, females held around 14% and 9% of the board seats of the major companies, respectively, up from 13% and 8.5% in 2007. Compared to 11.7% in 2010, from the data published by EPWN (2010), females held around 8.0%, 8.5%, and 9.7% of the board member positions in the top 300 European companies in 2004, 2006, and 2008, respectively. From 2004 to 2010, Norway had the highest number of female board members in the EU.

Canada, Australia, India, Italy, Malaysia, and other nations have supported or passed legislation and policies to encourage the growth of women's representation on boards (Man and Wong, 2013). Female directors have a greater chance of being nominated to monitoring committees that oversee CEO turnover and remuneration and impact a company's governance. They can also better monitor managers' behaviour by using board input, such as attendance at meetings, to determine their behaviour (Adams and Ferreira, 2009). According to Srinidhi, Gul, and Tsui (2011), the fact that female directors are typically better at communicating, conducting informed discussions, and exercising independent thought tends to raise the earning quality of businesses. It improves management oversight, according to research by Adams, Gray, and Nowland (2010), Adams and Ferreira (2009), and Terjesen, Sealy, and Singh (2009).

2.2.3.2. The Audit Committee

An audit committee usually has oversight over an objective assessment of the precision of financial reports, the efficiency of internal controls, and the actions of external auditors. The audit committee also keeps an eye on how applicable rules and regulations are followed, how ethically internal and external matters are managed, how well-functioning fraud control procedures are maintained, and how conflicts of interest are managed (Yang and Krishnan, 2005). The board, both internal and external auditors, and the relevant authority can all communicate with one another through the audit committee. This study has concentrated on common-law nations because they are thought to have greater CG, and the USA has more severe standards for audit committees. The creation of the audit committee was required by the US Sarbanes-Oxley Act of 2002 (SOX) to monitor the companies listed on the NYSE and NASDAQ to develop the truthfulness of business records (Benoit, 2006).

SOX 2002 develops the observing position of the audit committee within organisations. Except in certain situations, Section 202 requires the auditor's approval of non-audit services disclosed in regular reports and the audit committee of the firm's preapproval of any additional services that the audited company provides. Following Section 204, the audit committee now needed to receive timely notifications on any alternate methods of treating financial data compliant with GAAP. Direct accountability rests with the audit committee for the nomination, remuneration, and supervision of the firm's auditor, which is mentioned in Section 301. Although Subsection (3A) defines "*independence*", it also mandates that all committee members be independent board members. The committee is instructed under Section 302 to oversee management's evaluation of internal control functioning.

Bedard *et al.* (2004) indicate that the US SEC mandates that committee members have financial knowledge, which is an excellent approach to restrain managers' self-interest. The audit committee's independence is crucial for firms and stakeholders. Before SOX 2002, audit committee members might be chosen by the CEO, who would give them responsibilities and set the agenda for committee meetings. Senior management has, nevertheless, been complicit in several scams. Committees are unaware of the problems when there is a lack of independence. By giving the board additional accounting and financial advice and by more closely monitoring internal control systems, an audit committee's financial knowledge may increase the veracity of financial data and the correctness of the company's financial statements (Cohen *et al.*, 2014; Dhaliwal, Naiker, and Navissi, 2006).

Several researchers agree with the findings of audit committees that have financial expertise and trustworthy information (Krishnan, 2005; Bedard, Chtourou, and Courteau, 2004). The UK CG Code also recommends the audit committee as a vital internal company governance structure. The audit committee oversees the external audit of the company's financial accounts. The oversight of the board's performance by the compensation

and audit committees is designed to drive the board to perform better. Investors will have an increased level of trust in the company's financial statements (Laing and Weir, 1999).

2.2.3.3. The Compensation Committee

Ideally, executives' remuneration is supposed to be decided by the shareholders (Harris, Karl, and Lawrence, 2019). In reality, the compensation committee has the power to determine compensation for the executive directors. The NYSE and NASDAQ mandated in 2003 that listed businesses establish a compensation committee to handle this duty, and that committee members must be independent directors. They even proposed in 2012 to bar companies from going public if their compensation committee independence violated SEC regulations (SEC, 2017). The compensation committee's primary responsibility is to provide executive incentives and remuneration to draw in, retain, and inspire company managers. This committee is responsible for restraining managers who act in self-serving ways, such as paying themselves exorbitant salaries.

Base wages, incentives, restricted shares, options, and share options are the types of compensation systems particularly likely to minimise opportunistic behaviour. A majority of independent board members must agree to or recommend that top executives' compensation contracts be approved for listed companies under US SEC standards. The committee controls the creation and administration of retirement programmes and establishes executives' remuneration. Thus, the committee carries fiduciary obligations to shareholders to guarantee the fairness and motives behind executive remuneration. To determine competitive pay for senior executives, the compensation committees of big companies typically use external consultants to gather sector compensation statistics. Critics have voiced concerns about the excessive remuneration offered to top executives in recent years, the apparent lack of oversight of executive compensation by the committee, and the deteriorating link between CEO pay and

financial achievement. The Corporate Governance Code in the UK requires independent directors in the committee to restrict unrealistic compensation for the board's executives.

2.2.4. Earnings Management (EM) Definition

The term “earnings management” refers to a broad range of accounting strategies employed by management to meet a predetermined profit target. However, EM does not have a single accepted definition. Several methods in accounting literature explain the technique. EM is “*a purposeful intervention in the external financial reporting process, with the intent of obtaining some private gains*”, according to Schipper (1989). Llukani (2013) and Siekelova *et al.* (2000) described EM as “*Achieved economic result can be considered as a tool for measurement of the company performance during the year. It is set as the difference between revenues and costs of the fiscal year. There are many situations in which achieved economic results are intentionally influenced by managers. These initiatives on the accounting earnings are also known as earnings management*”. These definitions have one thing in common: management intentionally manages reported data.

Some authors defined EM as “*difficult to operationalise simply using aspects of reported accounting figures*” since the management's goal is “*in observable*” (Dechow and Skinner, 2000). Accounting standards that are unclear and subjective increase the likelihood of EM. Management can use discretion or judgement when determining the reported accounting figures once these standards have been applied. According to Athanasakou *et al.* (2009), UK businesses may control their profitability by classifying core expenses as non-recurring expenses. Restructuring expenses and EM are linked, as per Bens and Johnston (2009). In a random sample, Somnath, Shroff, and Zhang (2009) discovered that earnings adjustment reversals occur at a greater frequency than anticipated by year's end.

Healy and Wahlen (1999) provided the following thorough description of EM: “*Earnings management occurs when managers use judgment in financial reporting and in structuring transactions to alter financial reports to either mislead some stakeholders about the underlying economic performance of the company or to influence contractual outcomes that depend on reported accounting numbers*”. According to Fischer and Rosensweig (1995), EM is “*actions by division managers which serve to increase (decrease) current reported earnings of a division without a corresponding increase (decrease) of the long-term economic profitability of the division*”. As a result, the effects and goals are recognised as two core parts of EM in this definition.

However, the definition of “mislead” determined by Healy and Wahlen (1999) seems to “*preclude the possibility that earnings management can occur to enhance the signal in reported earnings*”. In contrast, Schipper’s (1989) definition also permits EM to inform investors. Most past research focused on an opportunistic strategy for controlling earnings, and their findings did not consider the information viewpoint (Beneish, 2001). The suggested lack of openness and dependability of the financial reporting is another common assumption that EM is carried out at the expense of shareholders.

Even though it would not be practicable to provide managers unlimited discretion, investors may suffer if management’s judgement were eliminated (Healy and Wahlen, 1999). According to agency theory, managers should have some freedom in how results are presented because they are in the ideal position to determine which reporting method will serve the shareholder’s interests. Additionally, EM facilitates the market’s access to insider knowledge, assisting outsiders in making wise decisions (Scott, 1997; Arya *et al.*, 2003).

Research-wise, detecting EM necessitates figuring out if accounting accruals depart against assumptions and determining if the divergence is consistent with the motivations of managers. Specific accruals or aggregate accruals may serve as the foundation for accrual

models, according to Dechow, Sloan, and Sweeney (1995); Healy (1985); and Jones (1991). Despite the broad usage and study of accrual models, current research has called into doubt the model's accuracy and analysis (Thomas and Zhang, 2000; McNichols, 2000). A study on accruals management found that depending on the management's goals, several methods (or accruals) are employed to manage earnings (Marquardt and Wiedman, 2004).

The manipulation of financial statements as a result of routine business activities is allegedly caused by management's desire to trick shareholders into guaranteeing the performance of the business, according to Roychowdhury (2006), Gajevszky (2014), and Healy and Wahlen (1999). Individuals within the organisation may use their influence over financial statements and their financial skills to conceal or falsify earnings as a result of the gap between insiders and outsiders of the firm.

In agreement with this viewpoint, managers may use a variety of strategies, such as reducing profit volatility and disguising changes in financial performance by laying away cash for future times (Abadi, Hijazi, and Al-Rahahleh, 2016; Leuz, Nanda, and Wysocki, 2003). Managers may cleverly tamper with accounting reports by carefully regulating accruals. However, the accruals of everyday company operations are less likely to provide insight into management's opportunistic behaviour (Kaplan, 1985). The most likely indicator of any accounting information manipulation will be "abnormal" accruals. Researchers employed a variety of methods to categorise accruals as normal or abnormal (Dechow, Sloan, and Sweeney, 1995). The Modified Jones Model was demonstrated to be the most efficient method for determining EM.

2.2.5. Earnings Management (EM) Motives

Healy (1985) found the earliest instance of a contractual motive to EM. Since they have insider knowledge, managers can control net income to optimise their compensation. Managers are, therefore, more inclined to boost current-period earnings. Although Brown and Higgins (2001) implied that managers are driven by remuneration to manage earnings, this is not always the case. The research of Jiang, Petroni, and Wang (2010) showed that top managers' compensation is associated with greater EM and is correlated with a company's performance. DeFond and Park (1997) assert that managers may sacrifice potential earnings to protect job security by raising present earnings. Earlier research also shows that top management changes offer incentives for managing earnings in a way that reduces income. To take a 'Big Bath', new managers seem more inclined to participate in EM by reducing profit and raising their chances of receiving a reward later.

Covenants related to debt are another influence. Covenants are typically included in long-term loan agreements to safeguard creditors. Companies will suffer further if they disobey financial obligations. Directors are, therefore, more prone to control incomes to violate agreements. Companies close to collapse started implementing new accounting rules to boost profits, as suggested by Sweeney (1995). Similar findings are seen in studies by DeAngelo, DeAngelo, and Skinner (1996) and Shores, Bowen, and DuCharme (1995). By controlling earnings, companies are often more inclined to prevent declaring losses. According to a study by Hayn (1995) and Burgstahler and Dichev (1997), if they do not, they risk breaching covenants and paying extra money.

As indicated above, managers could be encouraged to exaggerate results due to exceeding or achieving analyst expectations or pay agreements (Healy and Wahlen, 1999). Businesses that publish profit projections are often more inclined to control results to satisfy

the expectations of shareholders. Studies showing this include Kasznik (1999), Chin *et al.* (2009), Barton and Mercer (2005), Das *et al.* (2009) and Matsunaga and Park (2001). According to other previous research, management controls earnings to keep them from falling short of analysts' projections, supported by Matsumoto (2002) and Kasznik (1999). Companies experience approximately 14% damaging abnormal returns when they continuously fail to meet forecasts, according to DeAngelo, DeAngelo, and Skinner (1996).

More importantly, the conditions of deals are generally more beneficial for businesses with positive earnings growth, whereas those with unfavourable earnings growth are more likely to be driven to manage their results due to increased management utility (Kahneman and Tversky, 1979) and lower transaction costs with stakeholders (Bowen *et al.*, 1995). Thus, managers have a solid incentive to control profitability to satisfy investors. Directors are more inclined to falsify results to match analysts' expectations before selling their shares (McVay *et al.*, 2006). To benefit from listing, companies are more willing to maximise their earnings to establish higher share prices. Nasiri and Ramakrishnan (2020), Clarkson *et al.* (1992), Hughes (1986), and Teoh *et al.* (1998) found that companies tend to reverse managed earnings after being listed.

In France, companies engaged in increased EM activities after their initial public offering due to poor CG (Cormier and Martinez, 2006). Similarly, Louis (2004) suggests that businesses may manipulate profits to boost stock prices and cut acquisition costs before an acquisition. Due to bad debt, EM may occur, as indicated by Beaver *et al.* (2003) and Beaver and Engel (1996). Moreover, research has revealed that some companies modify their research and development (R&D) expenses to control earnings, while others engage in hedging tactics, according to Bushee (1998) and Barton (2001). EM could be understood as an example of the opportunism of managers from the scenario above.

According to Abbadi, Hijazi, and Al-Rahahleh (2016) and Leuz, Nanda, and Wysocki (2003), corporate investors run the risk of making bad decisions and suffering losses because of insufficient financial information. To do this, management may employ various strategies, such as setting aside funds for potential future expenses. The opportunistic behaviour could involve manipulating earnings through controlling accruals even though accruals resulting from the firm's regular operations have no impact on the company's success, according to Kaplan (1985).

As per Suh (1990), Stocken and Verrecchia (2004), and Lambert (1984), EM might help expose business insiders. It might be a signalling tool to open communication channels between various stakeholders. Additionally, to manage profitability in the banking industry, the market reacts favourably to higher loan loss reserves (Beatty, Chamberlain, and Magliolo, 1995; Wahlen, 1994; Beaver *et al.*, 1989). However, Hanna (1999) and Dechow *et al.* (1996) hypothesised that managers' opportunistic behaviour is primarily responsible for EM.

The objectives of EM include meeting analysts' expectations, encouraging staff to earn incentives, and holding onto competitiveness in the corporate sector. Financial results that are modified following reporting rules are defined as lawful EM. False financial reporting occurs whenever EM departs from accepted accounting principles. Therefore, organisations tend to use EM when the benefits outweigh the costs and risks. In line with Suda and Shuto (2006), the ability to control earnings is aided by a consistent dividend and a thriving firm. To prevent a negative market response to unfavourable earnings news, companies with strong growth prospects are rewarded for manipulating results.

Since their revenues have less value relevance, executives seem less likely to alter results to fulfil goals in loss-making firms, as per Matsumoto (2002). Past investigations have revealed many reasons for managing earnings, such as those connected to the incentive

stock options, hiding information, political costs, self-interest, institutional reasons, executive compensation, financing contracts, and compliance reasons (Rahman *et al.*, 2013).

2.2.6. Earnings Management (EM) Approaches

Accrual-based Earnings Management (AEM)

AEM and real earnings management (REM) are the two main methods for controlling profits, as suggested by multiple studies, such as Valaskova, Kliestik, and Kovacova (2018), Hsieh *et al.* (2018), Kovacova and Kliestik (2017), Sadaf *et al.* (2018) and Belas *et al.* (2018). Discretionary accruals arrangements that GAAP permits might affect reported results. AEM is another name for this. After an accounting period, when most operational tasks have been completed, AEM may become noticeable. Discretionary accruals are not based on the company's ongoing financial activities, in contrast to non-discretionary accruals. The latter mainly depends on managers' discretion and may suffer from opportunistic behaviour. AEM affects the total accounting accruals and directly affects the company's cash flow.

According to the previously provided definition of EM, several possible methods exist for managing earnings. Consequently, several models can be used to identify EM. Dechow and Dichev (2002); Jones (1991); Peasnell, Pope, and Young (2000); and Dechow, Sloan, and Sweeny (1995) claim that the method most frequently used to determine discretionary accruals, also known as abnormal or unexpected accruals, measures the difference among actual and predicted accruals determined using firm-specific criteria. Although the methods used to compute discretionary accruals vary slightly, a measure of accruals is often normalised on a few independent elements in the first stage, including property, plant and equipment (PPE), revenues, and other things that are presumably beyond the management's control.

They establish a “normal” level of accruals by applying the estimated coefficients derived from the previous stage regression; the difference is referred to as “abnormal” accruals used as EM proxy. It is possible to identify one sort of EM using the abnormal accruals model, where management alters reported outcomes by exerting influence over the accounting processes. One of the most commonly used techniques for recognising EM is suggested by Jones (1991). Jones uses time-series data to determine each organisation’s discretionary accruals. The survivorship bias and potential structural changes in the link between principles and accrued expenses over time make this strategy susceptible to criticism.

A cross-sectional strategy is suggested by DeFond and Jiambalvo (1994) as a means of easing these worries. By taking credit sales into account, which are a portion of total sales that are at the manager’s discretion, Dechow, Sloan, and Sweeny (1995) significantly enhance the Jones model. According to their experiments, the modified Jones model is the utmost accurate detection method for successful EM. For the UK market, the same result is reached by Peasnell, Pope, and Young (2000). They also recommend the “margin model”, which works better when there is severe cash flow performance. There are few arguments over the most appropriate way to characterise the modified Jones model, although it is frequently cited in the research.

According to Young (1999), concerns regarding using depreciation as a tool for managing earnings form one side of the debate. As a result, working capital accruals instead of total accruals are often used in studies that also eliminate gross PPE from the right side of the Jones model. The possibility for accruals estimated using the balance sheet approach to contain inaccuracies in “non-articulation” activities, including mergers and acquisitions or rearrangement, is another concern mentioned by Hribar and Collins (2002). Researchers began estimating accruals using the cash flow technique following this study. Unfortunately, Gore,

Pope, and Singh (2007) suggest that other authors contend that the cash flow technique has issues.

Kothari, Leone, and Wasley (2005) propose a performance-matched approach to consider the connection among performance and accruals. Unfortunately, Dechow, Ge, and Schrand (2010) found that the residual accruals' noise level may increase and the model's predictive strength decrease due to the performance matching technique. The modified Jones model is often applied in modern literature. However, the best way to explain the concept is not commonly acknowledged.

Real Earnings Management (REM)

In contrast, EM may occur from structural changes in actual activities (Kliestik *et al.*, 2020). REM is the name given to this. To hit certain revenue goals, the time or volume of core operations within the accounting period may be controlled by factors including sales, finance, investments, and factory production. The timing of functions, including increasing output, reducing discretionary spending, delaying expenditures, and so forth, can occasionally impact the economic outcomes attained.

REM often reduces reported spending by reducing R&D costs. EM via actual activities manipulation by Roychowdhury (2006) is a key piece of research regarding REM. The research intends to gather evidence that managers conceal the company's yearly losses by engaging in genuine EM operations. It also discusses the notion that price reductions temporarily enhance sales, that reduced prices of sold goods or services are reported because of overproduction, and that reducing discretionary spending might be regarded as improving reported margins. REM may be carried out using three different methods, according to Roychowdhury: manipulating sales, cutting back on discretionary spending, or increasing

output. This EM strategy has the advantage that REM activities are harder to spot for regular investors, auditors, or regulators.

REM activities influence present and future cash flow. One unfavourable perception of REM operations is their potential to negatively affect a company's future financial flow. Stakeholders need to be aware of these practices since they jeopardise the company's ability to survive. According to Kim, Udawatte, and Yin's (2019) proposal, REM decisions have an impact on the CEO's pay, while AEM remains unaffected. In contrast to AEM, REM is not yet thoroughly studied. This study looks at the assumption that when it comes to managing financial outcomes, managers preferred REM activities rather than an accrual-based method. This may be done, for example, by lowering discretionary spending (Svabova *et al.*, 2018; Fanelli and Ryden, 2018; Graham *et al.*, 2005; Belas, 2018).

EM also refers to a manager's purposeful choice of accounting methods, such as voluntary accruals computation, disclosure, and revenue projection. Research on EM is essential because it can potentially jeopardise the validity of financial reports, which give important decision-making information to stakeholders. The majority of focus in EM research has been on the two primary forms of EM: accrual management and the alteration of actual financial activity. When determining discretionary accruals, a corporation can take into account "Provisions for Credit Losses" (PCL) (Ahmed, Takeda, and Thomas, 1999), warranty expenses (Cohen *et al.*, 2011), stock values and the frequency and quantity of uncommon items. The reverse effect of managing accrual is possible, claim Dechow *et al.* (2012).

Utilising real variables that might be costly to affect the company's long-term interests is another sort of EM. Most participants would instead use real variables to control earnings (Graham *et al.*, 2005). Another researcher claims that figuring out managers' strategies for EM is quite expensive (Schipper, 1989). Earlier researchers also believe that even more apparent EM strategies, such as alterations to accounting principles and timeline of

capitalisation, are challenging to recognise. The motivations behind EM were searched for in several previous studies (Holthausen *et al.*, 1995; Houmes and Skantz, 2010; Gaver *et al.*, 1995; McNichols and Wilson, 1988). Compensation packages are one such factor.

Someone might argue that managers could alter actual operational choices instead of accounting methodologies and estimations, like sales strategy, level of productivity, and expenditure on discretionary items, to transform reported profitability. According to Graham, Harvey, and Rajgopal (2005), US financial managers would control profitability by altering operational choices. According to a UK study of financial analysts, REM is favoured (Choi, Walker, and Young, 2006) whenever it needs to reach or exceed standard analyst forecasts. As a result, REM, instead of just AEM, has been a separate focus of EM research since the late 2000s.

To identify REM, the current study often looks at the difference between the amount of real activity occurring and the level anticipated using unique firm-specific data. In-depth research by Roychowdhury (2006) concluded that companies enhance sales by offering larger discounts, more accommodating credit conditions, increasing production, and reducing discretionary spending to increase earnings and hide losses. Roychowdhury models the “normal” cash flow stages, manufacturing costs, and discretionary spending as a function of basics like the volume and variability of sales. The actual levels’ deviations from the “normal” levels are then used as a REM proxy, as when discretionary accruals are anticipated.

According to previous researchers, businesses with low irregular cash flows, higher cost of production, and little discretionary spending are managing their earnings more. The Roychowdhury model has been frequently used to portray REM in the study that follows. Using much the same techniques used for calculating discretionary accruals, Gunny (2010) presents three indicators of unusual R&D costs: selling, administration expenditure, and profits on asset sales. Zang (2012) claims that managers decide between real and accruals depending

on each technique's proportional costs and advantages. According to Cohen, Dey, and Lys (2008), given the expanding financial reporting restrictions, REM has also grown in popularity.

REM has generally received much attention, leading to many models identifying it. However, because such models were created similarly to the models for discretionary accruals, they are vulnerable to the same problems. There are also issues with measurement inaccuracies brought on by an absence of a concept to describe what a "normal" level of actual activity might be within the context of managing real earnings. The data gathered using existing REM models may be the consequence of measurement mistakes and should, therefore, be viewed with great caution.

2.2.7. Earnings Management (EM) Measures

According to Gajevszky (2014), Roychowdhury (2006), and Healy and Wahlen (1999), the motivation for misleading shareholders by giving them inaccurate financial information comes from management (reaching objectives, receiving bonuses, and realising capital gains). The term "earnings management" is used in this study to describe aggressive accounting methods that adhere to GAAP guidelines. The key flaw with accruals models is that they cannot distinguish between accruals brought on by managers' choices and those caused by shifts in the company's financial outlook (McNichols, 2000). This makes matters worse because it is unclear how ex-ante value-maximising operating actions will affect EM metrics. It is unclear if EM estimates represent effective operational choices or reporting factors. For instance, Beneish (1997) asserts that a company's financial reporting strategy should be assessed ex-ante rather than ex-post and is dependent on its business plan.

Imagine, for instance, that a manufacturer of personal computers is aiming to surpass a competitor by raising output and paying distributors who increase demand before the holidays. The manufacturer might be prosecuted, and its reports could be challenged if the

strategy fails, resulting in lower profits and a fall in price. The company operates more as a competitor for customers rather than an earnings manager, regardless of whether its strategy results in the company having more discretionary accruals. However, this company cannot be distinguished from one that purposefully forced sales on its distributors to increase profits. If managers do have an incentive to suppress profits, they may do it in a way that is hard to notice, which makes it much more challenging to develop an accurate model based on aggregate accruals.

Studies have observed that many methods were used to detect EM. A graphical technique based on time-series data was used by Archibald, Gordon, and Dopuch (Kliestik *et al.*, 2020). Malcolm, Dascher, Copeland, Barefield, White, and Comiskey used a mathematical model based on specific accruals (Siekelova, 2021). Based on time-series data, total accruals were used by another group of researchers to identify EM, including Watts, Young, Kothari, Jones, Dechow, Wilson, Beneish, Kaplan, Healy, and DeAngelo (Siekelova, 2020). Cross-sectional abnormal accruals were used by Pope, Subramanyam, Jimbalvo, Young, and DeFond (Mangala, 2019).

Models of aggregate accruals have received much criticism while being widely used. According to McNichols (2000) and McNichols and Wilson (1988), research findings are confused when the incentive setting under examination is associated with performance. Guay, Kothari, and Watts (1996) claim that some “accrual models” inappropriately split incomes into “discretionary and non-discretionary” elements and exaggerate “discretionary accruals”. Previous studies have shown that unexpected accruals are widely used as a measure for EM. Legislatures and governing bodies may be interested in learning about the specific accruals or reporting methodologies used for EM. In their investigation of first public offerings, Teoh, Welch, and Wong (1998) looked at bad debt provisions and depreciation estimates. They discovered that sampling companies have a higher likelihood to use income-increasing

depreciation practises and bad debt allowances throughout the year of the IPO and years after, compared to a comparable sample of non-IPO firms. Adams *et al.*'s (2009) prior research produced similar results.

Investigation into particular accruals used to control earnings has flourished in the banking and insurance industries. Banks and insurers' largest assets and liabilities are directly tied to their "loan loss reserves" and "claim loss reserves", both of which may be big in contrast to "net income" and "equity book values" and are heavily reliant on manager's judgement. Research on bank "loan loss provisions" was carried out by the following researchers: Beaver *et al.* (1989); Moyer (1990); Beatty *et al.* (2002), and Wahlen (1994).

According to several of these research, financial institutions control their profitability by timing when gains and losses on investment securities are realised. These investigators include Moyer (1990) and Collins, Shackelford, and Wahlen (1995). These studies ultimately show that banks influence their profitability, most likely (in part) because of stock market goals. Few of these studies, however, assert that the market is aware of this type of profit management. Beaver and McNichols (2006), Anthony and Petroni (1997), and Petroni *et al.* (1999) found that insurers control their earnings. However, whether regulatory concerns or stock market incentives are behind this is unclear.

Deferred tax valuation allowances were discussed in other recent EM studies that use particular accruals. Managers with deferred tax assets must foresee tax advantages that are not anticipated to be used under Financial Accounting Standards Board (FASB) No. 109 (FASB, 2022). One complaint is that this guideline allows too much administrative reporting flexibility. Badertscher *et al.* (2009) and Cook *et al.* (2008) all examined this theory and reached the same outcome. There is little evidence that managers manipulate results by abusing their reporting judgement on the valuation reserve. However, because these researches have not particularly examined instances when managers have significant market incentives to control

profitability (meet analysts' expectations or before an equity offering), their evaluations may be inadequate.

Only a few studies have used specific accruals to regulate profits, indicating that this would most likely be an interesting topic for future study, as recommended by McNichols (2002). Researchers may directly demonstrate to governing bodies and regulators the precise accruals showing where standards are practical and where they might need improvement. Such investigations could create more robust accrual models as a drawback. Models for predicting the likelihood of earnings manipulation are based on recent research on particular accruals. The inaccuracies in the financial statements or the factors which may motivate organisations to take such action are supposed to be captured by a model (M-score) put out by Beneish (1997, 1999). The results indicate a consistent association between the potential for manipulation and some accruals by contrasting this model's resistance to the Jones model and using a sample of businesses with extraordinary business success.

It has been discovered that models that account for managers' motivations are more inclined to detect discretionary accruals. Usually, academics use four models—including discretionary accruals—to determine EM. The most frequently used strategy for spotting EM is to divide the accrual into normal and abnormal categories. However, different models have been employed in several earlier research. Such studies were conducted by Petroni (1992), McNichols and Wilson (1988), Haw *et al.* (2011) and Beatty, Chamberlain, and Magliolo (1995).

2.2.7.1. Discretionary Accruals

This study used discretionary accrual as a proxy to explore the link between EM and CG practices. Using discretionary accruals has upsides and downsides. Researchers criticised discretionary accruals for identifying EM. In reality, determining an estimation, test period, and company-year data with unmanaged profits are necessary for estimating discretionary accruals (Wali and Masmoudi, 2020). While the estimating phase does not involve EM, the test phase does. In research, it may be challenging to sustain the premise that directors can control earnings either upwards or downwards. Accrual can indicate management objectives while also helping to eliminate timing and matching problems.

Investors will possibly use the financial data to make decisions. Since investors want to increase their wealth, they specifically focus on earnings. Investors often use profits to assess company performance and modify their investment choices in light of new facts. Managers can, however, employ accruals to be involved in EM to fulfil financial objectives or achieve financial market expectations. The study of using accruals was started by Healy in 1985. Healy measures accruals using the accrual of working capital. Unfortunately, the Healy model does not take into account the elements that impact non-discretionary accruals. Since previous studies assumed that the level of non-discretionary accruals remained unchanged., as DeAngelo (1986) suggested, this model could have been utilised with minimal adjustments. Kaplan (1985) and McNichols (2000) indicate the statement is incorrect, nevertheless, because non-discretionary accruals needs to be adjusted whenever company activities change, which shows that firms' characteristics are connected to discretionary accruals (McNichols, 2000). It was also shown that the total accruals model may be misjudged, as indicated by Dechow *et al.* (2012), as it does not consider long-term revenue expansion.

This suggests that differences in accruals may be linked to corporate characteristics rather than being a result of incentives for EM. To assess the effectiveness of managers while managing the company's regular accrual, Jones created a model in 1991 which considers variations in revenue and PPE. The most-used EM proxy concerning abnormal accruals is the 1991 Jones model. One can forecast and explain the typical accruals by looking at the number of accruals accounted for and variations in revenue and PPE. According to Jones, the primary driver of current accruals might be revenues; meanwhile, PPE is the primary motivator of noncurrent accruals. This approach is very straightforward, as claimed by researchers (Beaver, 2002). Once current and noncurrent accruals are under control, the outstanding unaccounted standard errors are viewed as discretionary accruals, an indicator of EM.

Regrettably, this approach might not be accurate enough to determine non-discretionary accruals. If the whole non-discretionary accrual was not estimated, the error term might also include overall discretionary accruals (including non-discretionary). As in the study by Ecker *et al.* (2011), the regression outcomes, particularly in a cross-section analysis study, could disregard the key problem, such as firm size. The business size most likely affects the number of accrual features, including corporate success, complication, and supervision. The technique was used until Sloan (1996) and Dechow, Sloan, and Sweeney (1995) updated Jones' model by computing the difference in net accounts receivable to exclude credit sales from the drivers of non-discretionary accruals since the business might influence credit sales. Due to its most probable reduced capacity to identify discretionary accruals, this modified model is ineffective, particularly in situations of exceptional results (Dechow *et al.*, 2012).

To solve this issue, Dechow and Dichev (2002) offer a different method. To determine discretionary accruals, they use a unique approach: they count non-discretionary variables as those that impact operational cash flow in the present, past, and future. Non-

discretionary accruals must have a negative relationship to the cash flow at present and a positive connection to the cash flow in the future. This strategy is similarly controversial, according to Wysocki (2009). Kothari, Leone, and Wasley (2005) also created a “performance-matched” discretionary model to assess EM. The impact on discretionary accruals is managed by return on assets and the industry. According to Dechow *et al.* (2012), the issue of misspecification can be lessened using this paradigm. Unfortunately, it achieves this at the price of the model’s test power.

Fields *et al.* (2001), and Breuer and Schütt (2023) claim that present accruals models face issues with inference. In the lack of the ability to change the behaviour of accruals, this model cannot be theoretically justified, (McNichols, 2000). For this reason, Dechow and Dichev’s model and the Jones model should be combined, according to McNichols (2002). As previously stated, when earnings are managed, the models cannot identify economically plausible magnetite, which may make up to 5% of total assets. This model will not work correctly when the company’s performance is higher. To solve the migratory misspecification problem and increase test power, Dechow *et al.* (2012) present a strategy that uses accruals to identify EM and boost test power. EM must be flipped between two periods. As a going concern, a company should maintain non-discretionary accruals throughout time.

To enhance the accuracy of detecting EM, this model may assess the amount of discretionary accrual reversal while continuing non-discretionary accrual. Studies on IPO by Ball and Shivakumar (2008) and reflections on breaches of loan covenants by Defond and Jiambalvo (1994) were also tested by the author. The test power of EM has significantly improved, according to their findings. The dependent variable’s transformation from total accrual to working capital, which is calculated through a shift in current assets subtracted from a change in current liabilities and cash and added by a modification in “short-term loans”, is one of the differences between the 1991 Jones model and the 2012 Dechow model.

The amortisation variable was excluded because it pertains to “long-term capital” spending instead of working capital, and independent variables are additionally comprised of factors to measure the EM reversal with drivers of non-discretionary accruals. Accrual-based models for managing earnings have inadequate explanatory power, claim Dechow *et al.* (2012). Given the model test’s lack of linked variables for non-discretionary accruals, it has various misspecified difficulties. They contend that the model to use is dependent upon the particular investigation. For instance, academics should apply the model proposed by Dechow if they are drawn to the idea of turning around EM. If the inaccuracy of missing items is not corrected, applying the Jones and modified Jones models also risks associated with the invalid classification of discretionary accruals as non-discretionary.

Depending on the state of the economy, the causes of non-discretionary accruals should be identified to assess whether or not EM is involved. Dechow and Dichev advise against using the performance-matching approach unless the missing related variables have previously been found. On the other hand, the problem with the estimating strategy is that Jones (1991) estimated the relationship between total accruals and explanatory variables using a company-specific model. A good time series is needed to evaluate company-specific parameter estimations. Most studies need sample firms to include data with a minimum of ten years, and those lacking enough data are often eliminated. Companies with fewer than ten years of trading experience are disqualified under this strategy. Employing a cross-sectional estimate strategy without needing a time series for every organisation is possible. Nevertheless, the sample’s other firms’ accounting practices determine the baseline for each company’s accruals. This may lead to inaccurate results that might not truly represent EM (Bagnoli and Watts, 2000).

Previous studies have mostly concentrated on discretionary accruals and non-discretionary earnings to assess if organisations employ discretionary accruals to meet

earnings targets. For instance, Jamadar *et al.* (2022), DeFond and Park (2001) claimed that businesses adopt discretionary accruals to reach profit targets. Cheng (2000) offers insight into the connection between discretionary accruals and unexpected earnings and discovers that businesses that report non-discretionary earnings that are below expectations frequently have positive discretionary accruals. In contrast, non-discretionary revenues above projections typically report negative discretionary accruals. More enterprises should use EM to cross thresholds from below to above than the other way around if the identified inconsistencies in earnings distributions are explained by EM.

Additionally, the strength and specificity of several methods of computing discretionary accruals are assessed by Peasnell, Pope, and Young (2000) using information from the UK and contrasted with the Jones (1991) model. They observed that other models now in use do not typically beat the Jones (1991) model in regards to their capacity to pinpoint appropriate levels of EM. The approach used in this study to estimate discretionary accruals is quite similar to the one they used.

2.2.8. Earnings Management (EM) and Corporate Governance (CG)

According to an earlier study that has demonstrated the influence of CG on EM, a high degree of CG hampers EM techniques (Roreng, 2021; Cheng, 2000). However, the nature of this relationship has led to inconsistent findings in earlier investigations. According to Klein's analysis from 2002, businesses with independent members on their boards or audit committees are now less likely to experience significant accruals. The report adds that boards with greater separation from the CEO could be better equipped to monitor the company's financial accounting process. Agency problems, particularly conflicts between the minority and

the largest shareholders, are decreased by excellent corporate governance, claim Liu and Lu (2007).

The board's governance directly impacts management's decisions and activities, selection, employment, and the audit committee's supervision of internal control systems and external auditors. However, tacking manipulative financial performance is made possible by enhanced board governance via the internal control mechanism (Brickley, Coles, and Terry, 1994; Carcello *et al.*, 2006). Previous studies have shown that board independence can restrict EM (Dechow and Dichev, 2002). This is because independent directors are not primarily concerned with their interests by seeking executive remuneration, improperly using assets, or misleading investors to further personal objectives.

A prior study by Williamson (1981) indicates that the board's independence is essential for monitoring organisational operations and preserving investors' interests. According to Roe (1991), board independence can stop managers from abusing their positions of authority. Similar findings were made by Beasley (1996), who discovered that having numerous independent outside directors helped lessen the risk of managers acting opportunistically. Peasnell, Pope, and Young (2000) assert that in the UK, a greater percentage of outside directors can more successfully prevent income-increasing discretionary accruals from evading earnings control. The suggestion made by Klein (2002) that there is a negative link among EM and independent boards in the USA furthers this argument. In light of this, there is a negative association between the levels of EM and board independence, as claimed by Xie, Davidson, and DaDalt (2003).

While conducting a test on companies in China, it was noted from a variety of literature that, to gain from the stock market, businesses are most likely to perform better. Examples include issuing new shares, conducting an IPO, maintaining their position on the stock market, and other actions (Liu and Lu, 2007; Aharony, Lee, and Wong, 2000). The board

of directors decides the company's best course of action that increases shareholder value (Weisbach 1988; Fama and Jensen 1983). The three topics that generated the most controversy in earlier research were EM, management compensation, and firm value (Sanchez-Marin *et al.*, 2011; DeJorge and Laborda, 2011).

According to several studies, different mechanisms of CG enhance the credibility of financial information (Wang, Zhou, and Wang, 2020; Ahmed and Duellman, 2007), mechanisms of CG are related to abnormal accruals of EM (Xie, Davidson, and DaDalt, 2003), and earnings manipulation is connected to CG structure (Beasley and Salterio, 2001). This research examined the audit committee, board makeup, and board director characteristics. These are the CG procedures used to manage conflicts of interest. Previous studies have also demonstrated a connection between the composition of the board and corporate fraud, indicating that organisations with fewer independent directors on their boards are more prone to engage in profit manipulation.

A substantial correlation between board structure and financial standard infractions was also discovered. Another research examining board composition and EM discovered a contradiction between independent audit committees and EM (Klien, 2002). Additionally, the audit committee having the CEO as a member shows increased EM. As a result, the quality of the financial statements and reports is influenced by the audit's quality, the audit committee's objectivity, and the board's independence. Establishing an effective accounting method would be easier for firms if the CEO did not dominate the company's board as much. Xie, Davidson, and DaDalt (2003) assert that the board of directors is crucial in minimising EM.

Prior research found that the board's sizes, how often board meetings are conducted throughout the fiscal year, the existence of independent non-executive board members, and the presence of board directors with financial competence all negatively affected

EM. The impartiality of the audit committee or more frequent meetings also have a detrimental impact on managing profitability. Others have discovered various outcomes as well. According to Choi, Jeon, and Park (2004), there is no connection between EM and the audit committee, although Koh, Laplante, and Tong (2007) assert that a reduction in EM may result from creating an audit committee for organisations. In most situations, earlier research employed discretionary accruals as a tool to identify EM. Adding independent directors to audit committees was shown to aid organisations, including less effective handling of earnings.

However, only a few empirical investigations have been undertaken to discover earnings smoothing using actual REM. According to studies by Herrmann, Inoue, and Thomas (2003), and Bartov (1993), management may abuse their authority to sell investments or fixed assets to avoid breaking a debt covenant or slowing the company's growth. This is a straightforward actual EM technique when actions are difficult to notice and pertinent to the regular business operations of the corporation. Graham, Harvey, and Rajgopal (2005) have stated in their recent research that CEOs are now more interested in using REM as the watchdog, external auditor, or regulatory body may be able to recognise AEM easily.

Among these include price reductions to boost sales, overproduction, and improving profitability by cutting flexible expenses. This investigation examines how AEM and CG practises relate to one another. To profit personally, managers participate in earning management (Healy, 1985; Asghar *et al.*, 2020). However, this can be curbed by CG measures. Several factors can improve the organisation's success: incorporating diversity and inclusion and women's representation on the board, a larger proportion of independent directors, the autonomy of the audit committee, split chairman and CEO roles, and board independence. The company's likelihood of financial success is highest when there are women in the management, according to various researchers (Adams, Carow, and Perry, 2009; Carter, Simkins, and Simpson, 2003). To better understand these relationships, this study looks at how board

independence, audit committee size, board size, independent chairmanship, and female board representation relate to EM.

According to a different study by Bedard *et al.* (2004) and Setiawan *et al.* (2020), audit committees in the USA may be able to limit EM if they have a financial background. Furthermore, according to Agrawal and Chadha (2005), the use of audit knowledge may stop cheating and profit manipulation, two behaviours that influence EM. Gaver and Gaver (1998) only reveal a noteworthy and favourable connection among earnings and remunerations with positive earnings. Baber *et al.* (1998) contend that firms with stronger compensation functions have more resilient elements of profitability, which is in line with this point of view. As the director's last year drew near, Cheng (2004) showed a strong correlation between variations in option pay and variations in R&D spending. Furthermore, when establishing cash remuneration for directors, it was found that the compensation committee minimises compensation when management makes decisions on accruals and discretionary spending in the director's last year (Man and Wong, 2013). In other words, companies with better CG practices control their earnings at a lower level. Similar conclusions, namely that CG and EM have a positive relationship, were published by Ali Shah *et al.* in 2009.

According to Epps and Ismail (2009), companies with yearly board elections, smaller boards, and fully independent nominating and compensation committees had fewer discretionary accruals. As per Ghosh *et al.* (2010), board experience, structure or other committees affect how earnings are managed. On the other hand, board size, the size or activity of the audit committee, and tenure are all connected to EM. Alongside the proportion of insider ownership, the proportion of independent members and duality, Abed, Al-Attar, and Suwaidan (2012) claim that a company's board size is the sole factor that significantly influences control of earnings. However, Liu, Harris, and Omar (2013) suggest that the audit committee's independence, board meeting frequency, and the existence of the nominating

committee are all harmful to the management of earnings. Nonetheless, a favourable correlation exists between business size and board independence in managing earnings.

As stated by Swastika (2013), EM and the board of directors are highly correlated and have a substantial connection between audit quality and firm size. Another study by González and Garcia-Meca (2014) indicates that a negative relationship exists between managerial ownership, institutional ownership, size of the board, board involvement, and discretionary accruals (a proxy of EM). However, there was no statistically significant correlation in terms of ownership concentration, dualism, family ownership, and the overall amount of discretionary accruals. Furthermore, Iraya, Mwangi, and Wanjohi (2015) discovered that EM is positively related to the activity of the board and dualism but adversely related to the board size, ownership concentration, and board independence.

Similarly, Patrick, Paulinus, and Nympha's (2015) study shows how CG norms, including board independence, the effectiveness of the audit committee, and firm size, greatly impact how businesses manage their profits. Likewise, Ramachandran *et al.* (2015) observed that the motive for EM grows when the nominating committee directly or indirectly impacts the compensation committee. According to an earlier study by Dechow, Sloan and Sweeney (1996), insufficient managerial supervision is a crucial motivator for EM. Many authors studied the link between several modest cases of AEM and CG, in contrast to earlier writers who concentrated on extreme occurrences of financial fraud (Mather and Ramsay, 2003).

It has been demonstrated by Klein (2002) that boards with a higher number of independent directors may help reduce EM, which boosts profitability. More evidence is provided by Xie, Davidson, and DaDalt (2003), showing independent directors with business skills are often motivated to limit EM. According to Dechow, Sloan, and Sweeney (1996), and Buchholz, Lopatta, and Maas (2020), organisations employing EM are unlikely to be monitored by outside blockholder administration and are expected to be managed by the chairman or CEO,

who is also the founder of the business. Lower EM is linked to more regular board meetings and short contracts for independent directors.

Interestingly, studies show that small businesses usually report larger discretionary accruals, supporting the notion that small enterprises can sometimes handle their revenues more extensively and are subject to very little attention. Large shareholders having significant shares in a firm would monitor the financial decisions made by managers and try to minimise profit management, according to Chung, Firth, and Kim (2002). Koh's data from 2003 shows that, in contrast, significant long-term shareholders actively participate in CG and impose limitations on the authority of executives to control earnings. Even though Peasnell, Pope, and Young (2000) could not locate any proof to support the assumption that audit committees actively restrain EM, they concluded that audit committees affected EM by facilitating external director supervision.

Instead, they discovered that the interaction between the existence of an audit committee and external members had a substantial negative coefficient. On the other hand, no connection was detected between discretionary accruals and the ratio of independent members in the audit committee (Xie, Davidson, and DaDalt, 2003). However, they found a connection between lower levels of EM and audit committee membership by corporate members or bankers with investment experience. Thus, these participants assist the committee's monitoring function. The ratio of outside audit committee members and abnormal accruals was shown to be negatively correlated by Peasnell, Pope, and Young (2000) and Klein (2002). Although an audit committee comprised of only independent directors might be considered independent as per NASDAQ and NYSE, Klein (2002) could not discover any proof linking an independent audit committee to abnormal accruals.

2.2.9. External Corporate Governance (CG) Mechanisms and Earnings Management (EM)

2.2.9.1. The Regulatory Framework vs EM

The protection of outside investors is influenced by the rights provided to them and how those rights are legally enforced. The institutional architecture of a nation affects the degree of EM. Research by Burgstahler, Hail, and Leuz (2006) suggests that less EM is related to extra strong legal regimes. Leuz, Nanda, and Wysocki (2003) claim that larger levels of EM are often found in nations with weaker investor protection, which gives insiders more incentive to misrepresent business performance. The three clusters employed by Leuz, Nanda, and Wysocki in their 2003 study to group the sample countries are similar to those used in Ball *et al.*'s 2000 and 2003 studies. They organised countries according to common law.

They discover a considerable difference in EM ratings across the three clusters. Those nations with less EM have more robust investor protection under the law. More vital legal protection makes managers less likely to shift assets or revenues (Nenova, 2003). Additionally, evidence from recent investigations is consistent. According to Chin, Chen, and Hsieh (2009), foreign-owned enterprises with strong shareholder protection in Taiwan have given up EM to achieve the necessary level of profits. Ball, Robin, and Wu (2003) contend that a country's institutional structure is essential in stopping managers from acting in their own self-interest, eliminating aggressive EM and boosting the integrity of accounting information.

However, as noted by earlier writers, common law nations like Malaysia, Hong Kong, and Singapore report revenues that do not capture the success of their legal systems (Fan and Wong, 2002). According to another research by Defond *et al.* 2007, institutions with inadequate investor protection have aggressive EM and low earnings information quality.

2.2.9.2. The Market for Corporate Control vs EM

Executives have a greater incentive to adopt strategies to lessen the chances of being taken over or losing control, according to Billet and Xue (2007) and Comment and Schwert (1995). They are also more willing to buy their shares when this is the case. According to this, these businesses are more likely to manipulate profits to appear to perform better as a takeover resistance and to drive up the share cost. This increases the cost to potential buyers while making it much more challenging for them to conclude the sale. During management buyouts, for management to buy more shares of the business at a lower price, companies tend to control earnings downward (Wu, 1997; Perry and Williams, 1994).

Alternatively, businesses will manipulate earnings higher to lessen or completely prevent the possibility of a successful takeover (Braga-Alves *et al.*, 2009). The earlier author also discovered that businesses with market capitalisations of more than 10 billion dollars in the USA lack the capacity to manage their acquisition and profitability. In a unique informational environment, it was contended that EM is more immediately recognisable. According to O'Brien and Bhushan (1990) and Linck *et al.* (2005), larger organisations are easier for financial analysts to monitor and can afford to pay less to comply with stricter corporate governance regulations. So, managing earnings is indeed more complex. According to Shen (2007), it is increasingly probable that businesses would adopt more careful accounting principles to lower their takeover risk.

2.2.10. Internal Corporate Governance (CG) Mechanisms and Earnings Management (EM)

2.2.10.1. The Board Committees vs EM

Compensation Committee vs EM

Managers are primarily driven by their compensation to participate in EM tasks (Kanapathippillai *et al.*, 2019). By lowering discretionary spending (for example, R&D) or by modifying discretionary accruals, managers are motivated to increase profitability and receive more significant incentives. The compensation committee's primary responsibility is to create incentive programmes for the company's senior managers. To do this, Dechow *et al.* (1994) suggest that the committee may occasionally use its discretion in unique circumstances. To limit managers' interest, Cheng (2004) claims that stock markets across the USA, UK, and other nations demand that traded businesses have a particular number of independent directors inside a compensation committee (for example, paying themselves excessive salaries or lowering R&D spending). The previous author only considers a few sectors and concentrates on one real EM measure. Hence, these results are inadequate and can not be relied on.

EM and stock option pay-outs do not correlate with one another, according to studies by Cornett, Marcus, and Tehranian (2008); Cohen, Dey, and Lys (2008); McAnally, Srivastava, and Weaver (2008); and Coles, Hertzal, and Kalpathy (2006). It was discovered that when determining CEO cash remuneration, the compensation committee steps in to control costs when managers build up accruals and choose discretionary spending in the last year of the executive (Huson *et al.*, 2012). It is more possible that the unusual managerial changes will take place suddenly and out of the blue. This limits the governing board's and investors' efforts to organise the CEO transition to decrease aggressive EM in the last year

(Pourciau, 1993). However, the results disproved the findings. A well-run compensation committee might be able to spot the manager's opportunistic behaviour.

Nomination Committee vs EM

The task of suggesting candidates for the company board falls under the purview of the nominating committee (Efenyumi, Nwoye, and Okoye, 2022). The company's board of directors is assisted in its endeavour by the nomination committee, which performs the function of nominating directors. It is hoped that by separating the board from the nomination procedure, other board members-including the CEO-will be less involved in this kind of nomination. This separation will make it more likely that people eager to represent shareholders' interests will be selected, which is a good thing (Petra, 2005). According to empirical data provided by Shivdasani and Yermack (1998), businesses are more likely to submit candidates who are likely to follow the CEO's lead if they do not have a nominating committee or if the CEO sits on it.

Even though each nominee must be put to the vote by shareholders, these processes are typically only formalities. According to Latham (1999), the CEO makes appointments rather than the nomination committee. Evidence provided by Shivdasani and Yermack (1998) also suggests that nomination committees with outside independent directors seem more prone to propose candidates who oppose management's decisions. The nomination of persons who will function as shareholder advocates by an impartial nomination committee can enhance company boards. In contrast to WorldCom and Enron, when they made up the majority of the committee, just 25% of Global Crossing's nominating committee members were external independent directors (Petra, 2005). It did not lead to persons being on the boards of the businesses who would question the CEO's judgements, although outside independent directors were present on these committees.

Audit Committee Size vs EM

Auditors must have “*an attitude of professional scepticism to determine whether management has intentionally misstated certain items (possibly by amounts below the materiality level) to manage reported earnings*” concerning EM (FRC, 2021). “*Fraudulent financial reporting involves intentional misstatements or omissions of amounts or disclosures in financial statements to deceive users. Fraudulent financial reporting may be accomplished by the following: manipulation, falsification (including forgery), or alteration of accounting records*” according to “*The Auditor’s Responsibility to Consider Fraud in an Audit of Financial Statements*” (IFAC, 2004). The consequence is that auditors should not worry about whether deliberate misstatements are used because they are efficient or motivated by opportunistic goals. Both lead to the financial disclosure of the firm being unclear.

Nevertheless, auditors must examine individuals in charge of the institution’s administration following legal and professional standards, even though it's sometimes difficult to distinguish between proper and improper accounting methods (Almasria, 2022). In addition to meeting legal obligations, a decent level of trust in the fairness and accuracy of financial reporting depends on restricting excessive EM by auditors. Some prominent corporate scandals have highlighted the necessity for the auditor to deliver reliable and honest financial information. However, researchers have shown that investors feel that the reliability of certified financial data and the quality of reported results have usually worsened (Hodge, 2003). These results seem to imply that auditing constraints on profit management may be more crucial now than ever.

The current study suggests that auditors can limit profit management to varying degrees. According to various research, auditors working for leading consultancies are more expected than those employed by minor consultancies to demonstrate more reporting

conservatism (Krishnan, 2003; Bartov, Gul, and Tsui, 2000). In addition, auditors with industry experience are more likely in top-tier accounting firms to restrict EM than auditors without the necessary knowledge. According to studies by Hackenbrack and Nelson (1996), when the accounting standards are weak and management is required to use significant judgement, auditor support for clients' extreme EM becomes prevalent. The financial health of the client (Braun and Rodriguez, 2008), the client's importance or size (Wright, Shaw, and Guan, 2006), and the potential for the auditor to face legal consequences (Farmer, 1993) are all factors that auditors consider when deciding whether to permit aggressive reporting.

Other research has looked at how auditors choose less aggressive financial reporting solutions in response to severe EM (Johnson *et al.*, 2002). Despite substantial research on auditor constraints of EM, there is insufficient information to distinguish between earnings manipulation and ambitious accounting. The audit committee fulfils a variety of needs for the administration, owners or shareholders, creditors, and other interested parties of a company. One of these responsibilities is enhancing the dependability of the financial data that stakeholders use to make choices. When ownership and management are divided, agency theory is critical. Managerial objectives could not be combined with those of the shareholders, and this might result in resource misuse.

Executives frequently manage earnings to disguise their fraudulent activities. To enhance the quality of the financial statement, the audit committee might select exceptional outside auditors and closely watch internal auditors' work. Another responsibility of the committee in the USA is maintaining effective internal control by following Sarbanes-Oxley Act requirements. Improving financial information and decreasing EM can be achieved by maintaining better internal control. Maintaining efficient internal controls may reduce EM and enhance financial data. If the audit committee has limitations, it may be less able to confirm

that accounting information is accurate (Song and Windram, 2004). Corporate governance recognises an audit committee as a vital mechanism that helps reduce EM.

A predetermined percentage of independent directors who are not engaged with the company's daily activities are required by the UK, US, and HK stock markets, giving the audit committee a strong obligation to watch external auditors' work and examine financial reports. This requirement is mentioned in the earlier section. Businesses with a significant number of outside members on their committees are better at managing their income. If audit committee members own stock in the company, their capacity to successfully keep track of managers who engage in high-level EM may be affected (Chtourou, Bedard, and Courteau, 2001). Abbott, Parker, and Peters's (2004) earlier studies have demonstrated the value of audit expertise in reducing the risk of fraud and earnings restatement, two elements that affect EM. Effective EM and the audit committee's diversity are significantly related, claim Carcello *et al.* (2006). Accounting and financial skills might minimise EM for companies with other insufficient CG measures.

These authors also demonstrate that independent audit directors with financial expertise make up the audit committee's most effective composition for resisting opportunistic EM. The limited definition of financial competence creates a compromise between financial knowledge and other corporate governance tools. However, they did not discover a connection between real EM and the existence of a person on the audit committee with financial knowledge. Although the financial knowledge of the audit committee has a big influence on businesses with other poor corporate governance practices, it does not significantly lower EM. Because of this, the UK and Hong Kong SECs mandate that every company's audit committee should include at least one independent person with financial experience.

The audit committee provides a framework for monitoring the fraudulent practices of management to avoid informational misstatements and improve the calibre of

financial reports (Klein, 2002; Davidson, Goodwin-Stewart, and Kent, 2005). Ownership-concentrated businesses are more expected than organisations with an audit committee to underestimate errors or restrict earnings growth (DeFond and Jiambalvo, 1991). Furthermore, McMullen and Raghunandan's (1996) research showed that organisations with audit committees composed of "Certified Public Accountants" (CPA) have a lower likelihood of being enforced by regulatory or watchdog organisations. Listed companies also needed the audit committee's independent members who had experience in finance for effective supervision.

For instance, the audit committees for publicly listed companies must include three independent directors, according to the UK Combined Code and the NYSE Standards. Previous studies have also backed up the benefits of many executives serving on the audit committee (Klein, 2002). Furthermore, research conducted in the USA revealed a substantial and unfavourable association between EM and independent non-executive members who sit on the audit committee. (Davidson, Goodwin-Stewart, and Kent, 2005). Similar findings have been reported by Crutchley, Jensen, and Marshall (2007), who discovered that organisations are more inclined to use EM when the audit committee has few independent members.

The ratio of audit committee members that are independent non-executives and the quality of financial reporting are positively connected, according to a second study conducted among Spanish publicly listed companies by Pucheta-Martínez and De Fuentes (2007). The professionalism of the audit committee significantly impacts the accuracy of the company's business records. When there is a minimum of one finance specialist on the committee, there is proof of an adverse link between EM and audit committees; the sample used in this study was made up of S&P 500 companies (Anderson and Reeb, 2004). When studying US-based corporations, Bedard, Chtourou and, Courteau (2004) discovered a favourable

correlation between EM and the audit committee. Furthermore, they assert that extreme EM is inconsistent with the audit committee's independence and financial knowledge.

The likelihood of financial misstatements in businesses is decreased by any independent audit committee having a minimum of one member with knowledge of finance. The audit committee bears significant responsibility for maintaining audit quality, which was established by the board to supervise internal and external audits of the company. Improvements are made to the company's performance and audit quality as a result. According to prior research (Lin and Hwang, 2010), the impartiality, capability, and regularity of meetings of the audit committee throughout the year all play crucial roles in assuring the company's financial performance and audit quality. To prove this connection, the unfavourable correlation between audit quality and firm performance was analysed in this study.

According to research done on US companies by Bedard, Chtourou, and Courteau (2004), having audit committee members who are knowledgeable in finances reduces the need for EM. However, they failed to discover a link between EM and the audit committee's size. According to past studies, say Turner and Vann (2010), independent audit committees may reduce opportunistic profit manipulation. Scholars like Cohen, Dey, and Lys (2005) indicate that the Sarbanes-Oxley Act have significantly negative impacts on EM; as a result, legal requirements for companies are stringent in the USA. However, the earlier research found no impact on EM even after Sarbanes-Oxley was implemented.

Auditors are crucial in preventing managerial opportunism that might lead to creative financial reporting (Atu *et al.*, 2016). Auditors will ensure that customers offer as much information as feasible in their yearly reports and accounts since they incur fees when signing contracts with clients (Watt and Zimmerman, 1990). The resources the audit committee or auditors have access to might be the auditors' capability. The entire participation of the audit committee is used to describe its size. According to previous studies, an auditor's size can

influence its assessment (Jensen, 1993; Lin, 2006; Soliman and Ragab, 2013; Yermack, 1996). According to Bedard, Chtourou, and Courteau (2004), as they are more likely to provide the power, variety of viewpoints, and expertise required to ensure efficient oversight and reporting processes, there is less of a chance that the Big 4 audit companies will try to curb profits. Instead, it is more probable that small audit companies will be unable to spot and fix possible issues with the financial reporting process.

Going concern reports from audit practises are less common for economically troubled organisations where the audit committee lacks independence, as shown by Carcello and Neal (2003), and Saeed *et al.* (2022). Additionally, Klein (2002) found that organisations with higher anomalous accruals possess a higher likelihood of boards and audit committees with a smaller number of independent directors. However, Davidson *et al.* (2005) contend that organisations with more independent members on their audit committees and boards of directors exhibit less EM. As mandated by IFRS, the audit committee and the firm's independent directors are best able to deter managers from acting opportunistically while controlling earnings (Marra, Mazzola, and Prencipe, 2011).

Therefore, reputable and large audit firms discourage companies from manipulating their earnings. This is because bigger audit companies and auditors have more at stake when it comes to their reputations and the number of customers they may lose if their reports are not seen as reliable, accurate, and consistent. According to Atu *et al.* (2016), big audit firms have more wealth risk as a result of any ligations. They are probably more precise. Independent directors must serve on the audit committee under the UK CG rules. Thus, having more members on the audit committee leads to less EM. This investigation aims to determine whether the audit committee's size has a relationship with EM. The overall membership of the audit committee for the whole fiscal year will serve as a proxy for this.

H₁, EM is unfavourably correlated with the audit committee's size.

2.2.10.2. Mechanisms Related to the Company Board vs

EM

The external auditors and internal control mechanisms are subject to selection, employment, and oversight by the audit committee. Similarly, board governance may impact management's actions and decisions on business activities, investments, and financial affairs. According to Rahman, Faff, and Oliver (2021), Brickley *et al.* (1994), Carcello *et al.* (2006), Byrd and Hickman (1992), and Klein (2002), a superior board of directors may then employ the internal control mechanism to restrict opportunism.

Board Size vs EM

While testing CG mechanisms against EM, researchers suggest various conclusions. The independence of the board and board sizes are the two most-used CG strategies, for example, examining the connection between EM and the board's size of the business. Academics, including Saleh, Iskandar, and Rahmat (2005); Siregar and Utama (2008); and Gulzar and Wang (2011) have concluded that there is no relationship between board size and EM. While Chaharsoughi and Rahman (2013) discovered a substantial unfavourable link between board size and EM, subsequent research by Swastika (2013) indicated a favourable correlation. The overall number of boards of directors was used as a proxy in each of the studies described above to assess the size of the boards.

The fundamental CG mechanism is board size, which was crucial in earlier research (Zeitlin, 1976; Wang *et al.*, 2020). The individuals on the board, percentage of independent non-executive members, non-duality, and non-multiple members all affect the size of the board and other factors (Jaggi, Leung, and Gul, 2009; Dhaliwal, Naiker, and Navissi, 2010). Accurate financial reporting to the stakeholders is their responsibility. The number of board members for each sample business during a specific accounting year is referred to as the

board size of the company. This figure includes the CEO and chairman. Executive and non-executive directors, also known as outside directors, are included in this (Shakir, 2008). Problems with the company's board of directors may occasionally spark EM motives. Businesses can indeed suffer when they perform poorly.

However, according to Fortin *et al.* (2011) and Sun *et al.* (2013), even though it has previously predicted its goals and revealed earnings that differed from what was anticipated, executives and the board may decide to artificially inflate earnings to protect their reputation, their positions, to be adequately compensated, and to increase their prospects in the professional world. Ashiq and Weining revealed that new managers and freshly selected boards raise the outcome to enhance their competitiveness in their 2015 study on EM during the first years of an executive's employment. Most CEOs control their results to avoid disappointing investors and to enhance their reputation.

Insiders' desire to maintain and sustain the company's reputation by carrying out their stakeholder obligations serves as another motivation to manage earnings. Many elements related to the firm and the board may impact how earnings are managed. Four primary goals might motivate managers to manipulate profits, as suggested by Mard (2003). This includes managerial salary, regulatory and capital market incentives, and incentives from external contracts. The board's principal responsibility is reducing agency expenses brought on by partitioning ownership and control (Fama and Jensen, 1983; Rauterberg, 2020).

The supervision level of the company board decreases as the board size increases. When the board grows, members find it significantly harder to communicate efficiently. Therefore, when the number of members grows, the board's function becomes less important. A weak board increases the likelihood that management would manipulate earnings (Jensen, 1993). The board size is more extensive for companies using EM than for companies not using it, as suggested by Dechow, Sloan, and Sweeney (1996). A negative link exists

between board size and firm value, as shown by Fuerst and Kang (2004), and Harun *et al.* (2020).

Other researchers indicate that large boards have the resources necessary for efficient and successful board functioning with the required skills, network, and competency (Xie, Davidson, and DaDalt, 2003). Resource dependency and agency theory suggest a link exists between company success and board size, as claimed by Ghosh, Marra, and Moon (2010) and Davidson, Goodwin-Stewart, and Kent (2005). However, substantial empirical data supports the opposite. Larger boards are not always more resourceful, mainly if their makeup does not correspond to the company's needs (Pfeffer, 1972). Others have shown that bigger boards negatively impact the standard of business performance and its reporting due to "free riding" or directors' reliance on the scrutiny of other directors, and diminishing efficacy (Jensen, 1993; Firth, Fung, and Rui, 2007; Ahmed and Duellman, 2007).

According to the study by Lublin (2014), using data from 2011 to 2014, businesses with smaller boards generate higher shareholder returns than those with giant boards. There are mixed results, with some studies-including those by Jackling and Johl (2009), Sahu and Manna (2013), and Shrivastav and Kalsie (2016)-pointing to a connection between board size and business performance. Other researchers, like Kumari and Pattanayak (2014), Gulzar (2011) and Beasley (1996), also pointed to a negative association at the same time. The association between EM and board size is the subject of expanding empirical study. There is no precise consensus about the identification of a relationship. Other researchers claim that smaller boards are more successful at reducing managers' opportunistic conduct. Some studies claim that a big board size helps monitor managers. According to Chtourou, Bedard, and Courteau (2001), larger company boards are more productive. They claimed that larger committees had the authority to impose limitations on EM measures. Theoretically speaking,

more big boards should have substantially less discretionary accruals, according to Xie *et al.* (2003).

The conclusions are validated by other scholars who demonstrated that a bigger board of directors is connected with a significant level of knowledge, enhancing its ability to regulate and monitor managers' activities (Dalton *et al.*, 1999; Peasnell, Pope, and Young, 2005). However, the size of the board has a considerable influence on how well it performs. It has been shown by Jensen (1993) that the ability of the CEO to handle finances is facilitated by boards with more than 7 to 8 members. As a result, the findings imply that compact boards can effectively regulate the CEO's behaviour and improve corporate performance. In a similar vein, it was asserted that businesses with bigger boards would have greater control over their profits (Dechow, Sloan, and Sweeney, 1996).

Beasley (1996) shares this conclusion. To compare the structure of the boards of directors of 75 fraudulent and 75 non-fraudulent firms publicly listed in the USA between 1980 and 1991, the scholar performed a linear regression cross-sectional analysis and discovered that companies with superior boards are more prone to reveal false financial figures. The findings demonstrate that a smaller board size lowers the risk of material misstatements. A corporate board with too many members on it is less effective in monitoring than fewer ones, according to Loderer and Peyer (2002), Lipton and Lorsch (1992), Yermak (1996), and Andres, Azofra, and Lopez (2005). They will, therefore, be linked towards less EM behaviour.

As noted by Baysinger and Zardkoohi (1986), the company's governing body is recognised as the most essential governance tool in the banking sector. Its responsibility is to monitor and regulate the behaviour of banks. As a result, it could influence how earnings were managed. Inconsistent results are also found in the literature on how banks' reported earnings are impacted by board size. Omri, Ajlani, and Rbia (2005) discovered that company boards with many members are linked with increased EM in Tunisian banks. On the other hand,

Quttainah, Song, and Wu (2013) contend that a big board of directors can decrease profits fraud in Islamic banks.

These studies imply that one of the key board characteristics influencing EM is board size, although, due to the contradictory results seen in past studies, it is challenging to evaluate the nature of the connection between EM and board size. Therefore, this study's goal is to investigate the following hypothesis. The board's total size will be used as a proxy during the test. This covers every director, including the chairman and CEO, as well as non-executive and executive directors.

H₂. The size of the corporate board and earnings management are inversely correlated.

Board Independence vs EM

Non-executive independent directors are thought to benefit shareholders by decreasing aggressive EM and acting in their best interests (Lamoreaux, Litov, and Mauler, 2019; Srinivasan, 2005). Financial fraud is inversely connected with complete number of non-executive members on an organisation's board (Beasley, 1996). A company is less vulnerable to experiencing enforcement action from the US SEC for alleged GAAP breaches if it has a significant portion of non-executive members (Dechow *et al.*, 1995). To comply with the UK Corporate Governance Code, both executive and non-executive board members would be in equal numbers for businesses. The company board selects non-executive members by carefully examining each candidate's credentials, background, and reputation. They are independent of the corporation. Therefore, independent non-executive directors are more inclined to care about their obligations and responsibilities. Karamanou and Vafeas (2005) state that independent non-executive directors correlate well with a company's financial disclosure quality.

It is often assumed that the management team has little chance of influencing independent non-executive members. Most independent board members are probably successful in controlling managers' opportunistic behaviour. Research carried out through businesses from Europe, the United States, and the United Kingdom with the proportion of independent non-executive members provides proof that there is less financial wrongdoing, according to Marra, Mazzola, and Prencipe (2011) and Beasley (1996). Much of the existing literature has looked at the connection between EM and CG mechanisms. However, most of those studies' test subjects were corporations from developed countries.

Those nations, however, offer very substantial investment protection. Since corporate governance in underdeveloped countries is either non-existent or minimal, this research also evaluates literature that employs companies from those nations. In developing nations, most businesses lack robust investor protection and have highly concentrated ownership. Because they are improperly governed and unaware of the value of independent directors and high-quality audits in lowering financial fraud, these companies do not understand their need for these things. Minority shareholders in publicly listed corporations are typically adversely affected by management's information asymmetry (Park and Shin, 2004; Holderness and Sheehan, 1991).

The researchers Bradbury, Mak, and Tan (2006) discovered no connection among independent non-executive members and EM. However, they did discover a connection between an increased percentage of independent directors and wiser corporate judgements. This study aims to advance existing research and acquire an understanding of the connection between EM and board independence. Compared to studies undertaken by companies in underdeveloped nations, studies by developed companies may be misleading. Due to the disparities in legal and structural conditions, CG methods' efficacy varies (LaPorta *et al.*, 1999; Fan and Wong, 2002).

The inclusion of independent board members of the firm is required for efficient CG and improving efficiency (Hermanson, 2003; Wang *et al.*, 2020). To ensure the effectiveness of the top management's monitoring facility, the board should be strengthened by outside directors who are independent to the business (Fama and Jensen, 1983). They tend to avoid things that might harm their reputation. There should be no history of interactions between independent directors and the firm. Otherwise, the insider may influence or corrupt their service (Beasley, 1996). Numerous studies also contend that the creation of financial reports is favourably connected with the ratio of independent non-executive members.

An independent board member might be vital in preventing financial fraud, increasing monitoring effectiveness, and improving complete management control. Several researchers have also discovered relationships between management and financial disclosure requirements for the argument of EM. Lower EM activities are expected as a result of the independent directors' effective oversight (Peasnell, Pope, and Young, 2000). Earlier research exposed a negative connection between EM and the proportion of independent non-executive members serving on the board after the post-Cadbury era. Per Fama and Jensen's (1983) study, independent directors act as qualified arbiters to ensure that shareholder value is maximised and to restrain management's opportunistic behaviour.

A non-executive independent director might improve the monitoring facility, claim Jaggi *et al.* (2009). The Cadbury Committee recommended having a minimum of three independent or non-executive board participants of publicly traded firms. The board's choices should thereafter be subject to independent influence from non-executive directors. Since non-executive members are intended to serve as excellent watchdogs for executive directors, a committee's success ought to be positively correlated with the amount of non-executive board members. The outcomes of earlier investigations on the connection between corporate success and the number of independent directors are conflicting. In contrast to

Yermack (1996) and Klein (1998), who found the opposite, Vance (1964) and Pearce and Zhara (1992) discovered a favorable correlation between them. However, the findings of separate research by Daily and Dalton (1992) do not support the hypothesis that board structure and profitability are related. As a result, as with duality, there does not seem to be much consensus regarding the connection between corporate performance and non-executive director representation.

Board independence has reportedly been demonstrated in prior research to decrease EM, according to Dechow and Dichev (2002), Jensen and Fama (1983), and Peasnell *et al.* (2000). Because they do not pursue self-interests like CEO remuneration and asset theft, independent directors do not contribute to this. In addition to maintaining a professional image, they are under no shareholder pressure to perform at or above the standards set by the company. The company's board independence is necessary to regulate managerial activity and safeguard investors' interests (Williamson, 1981). Roe (1991) suggests that board independence can also stop managers from abusing their positions of authority and diminish investor interest. Shareholders can decide whether independent directors will be appointed again, which is an essential factor. As a result, independent directors are under pressure to supervise management.

Prior studies have shown that organizations that actively manage their earnings are more likely to be governed by insiders than by outsiders (Dechow, Sloan, and Sweeney, 1996). The danger of the theft of financial information can be compact by having a substantial quantity of independent board members (Beasley, 1996). According to Agrawal and Chadha (2005), the business lacks independence and has a greater likelihood of misrepresenting accounting facts when the CEO is a founding family member. To prevent EM, companies in the UK can benefit from having more independent directors by better limiting income-increasing

discretionary spending (Peasnell, Pope, and Young, 2005). Other research also support the previous statement (Uzun *et al.*, 2004).

In Australian businesses, the dual role of the CEO is linked to a higher incidence of fraud than in businesses with higher degrees of board independence and intuitive ownership (Sharma, 2004). Xie, Davidson, and DaDalt (2003) claim that the intensity of EM and board independence are correlated. Employing discretionary accrual to minimize earnings loss is more common in businesses with more non-executive board members, according to Peasnell, Pope, and Young, (2000). However, Xie, Davidson, and DaDalt (2003) found the opposite to be true. Australian companies with more robust board independence have more motivation to control profitability, according to research by Davidson, Goodwin-Stewart, and Kent (2005).

Although CG is a dynamic mechanism that cannot guarantee a ‘failure-free’ environment, Dixon, Mousa, and Woodhead (2005) contend that the independence of the board is an essential component of effective CG systems. As a result, governing bodies with a large proportion of independent members whose monitoring is more motivated to be accurate possess fewer opportunities to manipulate results, which improves earnings quality (Alves, 2014; Swai and Mbogela, 2016; Vafeas, 2000; Beasley, 1996; Marra, Mazzola, and Prencipe, 2011). Firth, Fung, and Rui (2007) used the earnings response coefficient to demonstrate a link between effective EM and board independence. Furthermore, the same results were suggested by Bushman, Chen, and Engel (2004) when using responsiveness and informativeness measures.

While Ahmed, Hossain, and Adams (2006) indicated no connection between board independence and profits management, Fuzi, Halim, and Julizaerma (2016) uncovered contradicting evidence. According to Van den Berghe and Baelden (2005), the efficacy of board independence depends on skill, commitment, and the environment as a

whole. Alternatively, it was found that China's independent director system was inadequate due to significant promoter influence and the directors' lack of understanding regarding their roles (Kakabadse, Yang, and Sanders, 2010). Due to their limited involvement and personal interests in the company, independent directors could not be sufficiently concerned with the company's performance over the long run. According to the Law of Reciprocity (Caliendo, Fossen, and Kritikos, 2012), people frequently strongly desire to repay favours.

In some cases, the reciprocation is even more kind-hearted than the initial good act. It was seen that the board appoints independent directors in India rather than through an impartial procedure. According to Chen and Li (2009), reciprocity may be used to propose that directors follow board decisions even if they disagree with them. The majority of these studies take into account discretionary AEM. Unfortunately, this model's usefulness is debatable since it has a modest strength in establishing associations involving dependent and independent variables. The associated factors for non-discretionary accruals were ignored, which led to an incorrect specification of the model's test. Future research on EM may need to use the model by Jansen. Its profit margin vs asset turnover ratio assessment can increase the test's explanatory power. The makeup of the board affects how successful it is, according to Morck, Shleifer, and Vishny (1988) and Williamson (1988), among others. An inside executive who is also a manager will have better access to company information to monitor management. The likelihood of inside directors working with management to blackmail outside shareholders is higher.

Outside directors may more effectively supervise the management team because they are not members of it, as stated by Fama and Jensen (1983) and Fama (1980). Having independent board members has been found to lower the chance of financial misconduct (Beasley, 1996). As a result, outside directors will probably enhance the board's involvement in oversight. Previous studies on the ideal board of directors' structure have shown conflicting

conclusions. According to Taktak and Mbarki (2014) and Liu (2012), boards with inside managers are a successful control method. Klein (1998) also claims that insiders have an advantage over outsiders because of their position within the organisation. They are more familiar with business details and have easier access to knowledge that will make them more effective decision-makers.

Research supports the notion that boards with independent directors are superior to insider director-only boards in improving internal control within corporations. Outsiders can successfully oversee managers' behaviour since they are not beholden to management and can act independently and impartially during their supervisory terms. When considering the effect of the composition of a board, earlier research has revealed that management of earnings and board independence had a negative association (Liu and Lu, 2007; Klein, 2002). It is possible to claim that boards with a majority of outsiders have a superior ability to monitor and control management behaviour, according to Ching, Firth, and Rui (2006). Beasley (1996) also suggested that board independence is a superior approach to management monitoring to minimise EM tactics and avoid financial statement fraud.

In a research he conducted on Thai banks, Anuchitworawong (2004) found that the only people who can stop EM strategies are independent board members. These findings have also been validated in a banking setting. Similar results were made by Cornett, McNutt, and Tehranian (2009), who discovered a poor correlation between board independence and discretionary loan loss provision in US banks. Studies support similar results for Islamic banks and claim that independent company boards are linked to lower discretionary accruals (Quttainah, Song, and Wu, 2013). Because independent members generally think that they are better at supervision than internal members, it is believed that businesses having more independent directors on their corporate boards will have less EM. Because of this, the study

suggests testing the following assumption. The proxy for the test will be the total number of independent members of the company's board of directors.

H₃. The board's inclusion of independent directors negatively impacts earnings management.

Independent Chairperson vs EM

An additional crucial component of boards is the division of the CEO's and chairman's functions. Corporate governance principles presumptively hold that when the board chair is also the CEO, it is more challenging for the board to carry out its oversight responsibilities, as recommended by the Standards Australia International (2003), ASX (2003), and Cadbury Committee (1992). Arthur and Taylor (1993) observe that the fundamental economic factors determining their separation are not understood. Beasley (1996) claims that the CEO being nominated as chairperson can result in a monopoly of authority. The level of oversight is thereby reduced by potential conflicts of interest.

Control over the corporate board rests with the chairman. In many companies, the CEO also acts as the chairman of the board of directors. As a result of their dual roles, the CEO of these companies is in a solid spot to oversee the daily operations of the business and the future course it will follow. The board is controlled by the CEO. In that capacity, they are in charge of defining the agendas for meetings and presiding over the selection, evaluation, and compensation of senior executives, alongside their role as CEO. There can be a conflict of interest when the board chair is also the CEO. A position of self-evaluation held by the chairman or CEO makes it unrealistic for them to conduct this evaluation unbiasedly.

Some have argued for separating the CEO and chairman roles by having an independent external director occupy the chairman post to prevent these potential conflicts.

However, empirical studies by Molz (1988) and Daily and Dalton (1992) have demonstrated that keeping the CEO and board chair separate does not improve an organisation's performance. Still, one may assert that management governs company boards and that having an external, independent chair seems to have no meaningful influence on business choices. For instance, in the past, Enron's CEO functioned as both the firm's CEO and the board chairperson, in contrast to WorldCom and Global Crossing, which split the responsibilities of the chairman and CEO. Although being the chairperson of the firm's board is undoubtedly a vital position inside a company, it seems that in all three instances, the person in charge of that position was unable to prevent misbehaviour at the workplace. The board of directors frequently takes advantage of committees to fulfil their duties and obligations. The usage and objectives of various committees differ in each organisation, even while many businesses support the board of directors with audit, remuneration, and nominating committees (Petra, 2005).

Another factor in enhancing board effectiveness is the chairperson's role. According to several studies, independent non-executive chairpersons improve firm performance (Marashdeh *et al.*, 2021; Rechner and Dalton, 1991; Donaldson and Davis, 1991). Executive chairs do not affect company performance, as suggested by Chaganti, Mahajan, and Sharman (1985). Independent chairs may promote further accountability compared to a dual role. Haniffa and Cooke (2002) assert that non-executive directors, who make up the majority of chairpersons in Malaysian firms, may be obliged to offer more facts due to their independence.

Companies with a different CEO and board chairman often have more voluntary disclosure, according to Cheung, Jiang, and Tan (2010). Research by Chau and Gray (2010) shows the appointment of an independent chairman and voluntary disclosure in Hong Kong are positively correlated. In cases when the CEO also chairs the board, the board's ability to carry out its governance duty is likely to suffer because of the chairperson's increased power.

One of the key CG mechanisms is the non-duality of the position. Examining the relationship between EM and the chairman, who is not just independent of the board but also does not serve the company as CEO, is the purpose of this research. To test the theory, if the company's chairman is also independent, the proxy will be set to one, otherwise, it will be zero.

H₄. The independent chairman of the board affects earnings management.

Female Directors on the Board vs EM

The board's capacity and activity may rise if there are more female board members, as per Adams and Ferreira (2009), and Cruz *et al.* (2019). According to Srinidhi, Gul, and Tsui (2011), gender diversity among the directors of the board might limit management opportunism and improve the quality of profits. Directors are more likely to detect financial fraud, such as EM, if they have sufficient financial knowledge and abilities (Xie *et al.*, 2003). Director diversity and financial expertise have not been linked in any prior studies.

According to prior studies, women are less prone than men to act immorally at work for their own profit (Betz, O'Connell, and Shepard, 1989). Similarly, Gul, Fung, and Jaggi (2009) assert that appointing female board members will probably help reduce knowledge inequalities among the other board members. According to popular belief, women are less assertive than males and more cautious when making decisions (Byrnes, Miller, and Schafer, 1999). When making financial decisions, they tend to steer clear of danger (Powell and Ansic, 1997). It is, therefore, predicted that having female board members will lead to less EM (Gul, Fung, and Jaggi, 2009).

Companies with more female members on their boards will have much greater profit quality compared to those with more men, and they are also more likely to avoid unethical behaviour and evaluation (Krishnan and Parsons, 2008). There are conflicting results

on the link between EM and female audit committee members. Thiruvadi and Huang (2011) revealed a substantial unfavourable connection between EM and audit committees with female directors. Few studies have looked at the link between diversity of gender among board members and EM, although many have looked at the consequence of CG and the audit committee on EM (Xie, Davidson, and DaDalt, 2003).

Compared to companies with a male Chief Financial Officer (CFO), researchers identified fewer EM efforts in companies with female CFOs on the board. Additionally, Peni and Vahamaa (2010) found that women in CFO positions are more likely to adhere to traditional reporting norms and employ discretionary accruals in the event of a decline in revenue. Nonetheless, researchers discovered no link between the CEO's gender and the control of profits. Another study (Gavious, Segev, and Yosef, 2012) discovered an adverse connection between EM and the participation of female board members. It showed that companies with female CEOs had less effective EM than those with male CEOs.

The audit committee and EM are also unrelated for companies with women on the board, according to data from another study that included companies in the USA and France (Arun, Almahrog, and Aribi, 2015). Agreeing with Gavious, Segev, and Yosef (2012), there is a bad association between companies that manage their earnings poorly and those with a more significant proportion of female directors. Female directors are also beneficial for lowering earnings manipulation. According to Cox (1994), gender diversity aids businesses in monitoring and decision-making operations. Previous academic publications (Pfeffer and Salancik, 1978) showed that gender diversity was likely to assist firms in terms of resource reliance and agency theory. As a result, this study also searches for negative connections between EM and the proportion of female board members.

Earlier studies have focused on various criteria, including the percentage of women serving as board members. Other factors include earnings quality and its

management. A corporation's board is more likely to include active female directors who try to demand and monitor managerial performance (Adams and Ferreira, 2009). According to Carter, Simkins, and Simpson (2003), women on the board demonstrate independent thought and oversee executives' actions more successfully compared to male directors. Female directors are also better able to think independently and efficiently supervise executives, as suggested by Adams, Gray, and Nowland (2010). Because businesses with more women on the board typically provide higher-quality results and require less EM, this is an important control for controlling profits. Independent thoughts are essential for preventing opportunistic behaviour and producing better financial details. The likelihood of protest to management's opportunistic behaviour is higher among female directors than among male directors, according to Krishnan and Parsons (2008) and Thorne, Massey, and Magnan (2003).

In the USA and Canada, female auditors frequently outperform their male colleagues in moral reasoning, according to Lampe and Finn (1992), Etherington and Schulting (1995), Sweeney (1995), Bernardi and Arnold (1997), and Shaub (1994). According to research that explicitly examines the relationship between gender and tolerance for opportunistic behaviour, female auditors tolerate inappropriate behaviour less than their male colleagues (Thorne, Massey, and Magnan, 2003). The top executives' experiences, attitudes, and positions should be reflected throughout a company, as Hambrick and Mason (1984) claim that senior management teams' decisions depend on these factors. Therefore, by taking part in senior management team decision-making, executives may affect the performance of businesses. According to the investigation of Hambrick, Nadler, and Tushman (1998), the management team's dynamics and interconnectedness substantially impact both business outcomes and corporate governance. Female directors' aspirations and actions may help companies create a culture of trust by employing transformational tactics, including team

member empowerment, objective setting, and managing one's reputation for the benefit of both the business and the person (Klenke, 2002).

According to Trinidad and Normore (2005) and Klenke (2003), female executives are likelier to use a trust-based management style. This statement is also supported by other authors, such as Carter *et al.* (1997) and Powell (1990). Managers must provide more information to female directors because of this trust-based leadership. As shown by Sunden and Surette (1998) and Powell and Ansic (1997), women make less risky decisions than men. Consequently, female directors make risk-averse decisions (Hinz, McCarthy, and Turner, 1997; Bajtelsmit and VanDerhei, 1997). Therefore, female board members are less expected to let management control profits since doing so puts them in danger of legal action and damages their image. According to Hunton *et al.* (2006), EM would harm a company's reputation.

Companies are more likely to be sued during initial public offers of shares if there is EM (DuCharme *et al.*, 2004). As a result, according to Srinidhi, Gul, and Tsui (2011), female directors are more concerned about the prospect of legal action and reputational harm. As a result, female directors have a greater tendency to select internal and external auditors with care and to keep a closer check on them. By increasing board participation, communication, and CEO oversight-aspects that are expected to enhance compensation quality-board governance can be improved by female directors. Therefore, for numerous reasons, having more women on the board may result in less effective EM. The earlier authors found a positive connection between EM and female board representation by applying several criteria of EM. Previous authors also tested whether there is a connection between the ratio of female participants on the company board and opportunistic EM. They also investigated the connection between EM and female audit committee members. The outcome indicates a statistically significant positive link. To test the following hypothesis, the total number of female board members of the business is used as a proxy.

H₅. The ratio of female board members has a substantial effect on how earnings are managed.

2.3. Research Gap

It was discovered during this study that many studies have been conducted on this subject since the introduction of CG mechanisms. However, most recent studies did not use UK-listed companies as a sample to conduct their analysis. For example, Saona, Muro, and Alvarado (2020) used Spain-based firms, Al-Haddad and Whittington (2019) used Jordan-based firms, El Diri, Lambrinouidakis, and Alhadab (2020) used US-based firms, Puni and Anlesinya (2020) used Ghana-based firms, and Orazalin (2020) used Kazakhstan-based firms as a sample in their study. The UK firms as a sample appear absent from most of the current research. This study intends to reduce this gap by using UK-listed firms as a sample to analyse and discover if up-to-date CG mechanisms (2018) help to reduce EM activities. As a front runner on the introduction of CG mechanisms, businesses in the UK are thought to have fewer EM activities than businesses in developing countries. This study intends to discover the connection between CG mechanisms and EM within UK-listed companies. This is to understand if current CG mechanisms are effective.

2.4. Conclusion

There are various outcomes from prior research. However, most of the authors of prior studies suggest having fewer EM activities in businesses with a better CG framework in place. The UK Corporate Governance Code has been updated to be in line with the needs of businesses and investors. This study investigates the relationship between EM and CG mechanisms within UK-listed businesses. This is to discover if current CG mechanisms help to reduce EM from occurring.

Chapter 3

Research Methodology

3.1. Introduction

The research methodology chapter included a description of the data sample used in this study and the variables and formulas utilised to test the hypotheses. In prior studies, various methodologies were used to test similar hypotheses. However, the relationship between CG mechanisms and EM was tested mostly by detecting the absolute value of discretionary accruals and then compared with independent variables. This is to determine how significant the relationship between them is (Al-Haddad and Whittington, 2019).

3.2. Research Data

This research explores the connection between various CG mechanisms and EM. Two different categories of data sources were employed to accomplish this. To calculate the discretionary accruals, historical financial information from the firms was primarily collected and utilised. The UK's LSE has an index called the FTSE 100 (pronounced 'footsie'). The FTSE 100 included the top 101 companies in the UK. The information required for this study was gathered from the financial reports of these firms during the years 2019 to 2022. Financial Analysis Made Easy (FAME), Bloomberg Terminal, Refinitiv, and other sources via the university library were used to gather the annual reports of these businesses.

Although the firms in this index come from a variety of industries, they are all required to operate by the same rules and guidelines established by the LSE. Companies must maintain high standards in their financial reports to keep their listing status. Most CG mechanisms are set for the companies to comply with or clarify the details for non-compliance. Studies have shown that listed companies adhere to the LSE's rules and guidelines (Elmghaamez and

Akintoye, 2021; Alabi, Olaoye, and Ojo, 2022). These businesses must abide by the CG rules and their mechanisms. For example, they had an audit committee with independent directors, a nomination committee, and a compensation committee. The UK Corporate Governance Code restricts CEO duality. The data from the yearly reports of these companies are used to evaluate the research's hypotheses, following the lead of other researchers.

Finally, considerable amounts of literature on the topic of this study was evaluated. The results of this research are compared to the outcomes of other researchers from the past. However, many studies have shown conflicting results. For instance, as stated in the literature review chapter, EM and the size of the audit committee have not been found to be correlated by several researchers, although some stated the opposite. According to several studies, the board's capability expands as board size increases, resulting in less EM. A few studies also discovered no correlation between the size of the company board and EM. The proportion of independent board members results in increased executive scrutiny. Hence, it improves the earnings quality. Some studies show no relationship between them.

3.3. Research Design

The positivist school of thinking is a foundational part of this research. The positivist approach works with the logical, quantitative, scientific, and experimental framework (Park, Konge, and Artino, 2020). Academics use this technique to find regular, measurable observations and often test ideas using experiments and statistics (Neuman, 2005). An archive examination of published sources is the most effective technique for the positivism approach (Clark, 1998). The board size, the board's independence, the chairman's independence, the audit committee's size, and the proportion of female board members are all explained using the deductive method in this study. The main goal of this study is to discover the role of CG mechanisms in identifying, deterring, and limiting EM using company data in the UK. The

association between the dependent variable (absolute value of discretionary accruals - proxy for EM) and independent variable (the board size, board independence, independent chairman, size of the audit committee and female director - proxy for CG) is measured in this study using a quantitative methodology.

Financial data from UK-based companies was used to perform the study. The UK was a pioneer in this area when it enacted the Corporate Governance Code in 1992. There are several processes in its regulation that firms must abide by. The mechanisms were introduced to safeguard the shareholder interests. To test their consequences, this study proposes to test five hypotheses. This study determined EM using discretionary accruals as a proxy, initially generated using the modified Jones model. Three equations altogether were employed to accomplish this. Net income is deducted from operating cash flows to determine total accruals for a given financial year. Equation two was then utilised to measure parameters particular to the industry using the Jones model. The total accruals are then subtracted from the non-discretionary components of accruals to arrive at the discretionary accruals. A total of five corporate governance mechanisms were tested to identify if they have any relationship with EM. These mechanisms are audit committee size, the board size, board independence, independent chairperson and the ratio of female executives.

The main objectives of this study were measured by using an empirical model to evaluate the association between EM and CG mechanisms. This involves doing regression analysis utilising 'IBM SPSS' (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) software to examine dependent and independent variables. The analysis employed "corporate governance-related mechanisms" as an independent variable and "the absolute value of discretionary accruals" as a dependent variable. The size of the audit committee, the ratio of female executives, the size of the governing board, an independent chairperson and the independence of the board are all independent factors. This study also includes descriptive statistics of the data used and a

correlation matrix. The outcomes of this study, compared with the findings of others, are found in the result analysis chapter.

3.3.1. Quantitative Research Approach

This study used a quantitative approach to its investigation. Comparing qualitative and quantitative research methodologies, the former uses surveys and interviews to do research, but the application of mathematical or statistical data is not required (Ahmad *et al.*, 2019). The quantitative research method is used when statistical or mathematical data, equations, and variables are used to test the hypotheses (Kandel, 2020). Furthermore, quantitative research aims to measure the data collection and processing process. Positivism and objectivist ideas have an impact on it, and it is grounded on a logical method that emphasises the confirmation of an assumption (Bryman, 2012).

This research technique supports the objective empirical investigation of recognisable incidences to assess and recognise relationships. It applies to many fields. This is achieved using a variety of quantifying methodologies and processes, illustrating the approach's widespread use as a research methodology over many subject areas. Developing and using mathematical concepts, models, and hypotheses related to phenomena is the aim of quantitative research (Given, 2008). This study utilised the method to get the necessary data using the businesses' yearly financial reports and test the hypotheses using variables and models.

3.4. Variables

Since different researchers have defined EM in different ways, there is no commonly recognised definition, claims Beneish (2001). Schipper (1989); and Davidson, Goodwin-Stewart, and Kent (2005) described EM as “*the act of taking purposeful efforts within the limitations of GAAF to achieve the desired level of reported income*”. Several authors suggest

other definitions. Corporate managers manage earnings by using discretion while doing tasks like creating financial documents. Healy and Wahlen (1999) contend that personal gain is the main driver, and this affects the company's and its shareholders' interests.

Managers may steer a company's profitability in several ways. Among the examples provided by McNichols and Wilson (1988) are changes to certain transaction structures, such as AEM, REM, and accounting procedures. In this study, various CG mechanisms were employed as the independent variable. In contrast, the dependent variable was determined by utilising discretionary accruals' absolute value as a proxy. Below is a more in-depth description of these variables. The goal is to determine the relationship between EM and CG mechanisms, which was then put to the test using the findings from the variables.

3.4.1. Dependent Variables

This research used the accruals-based technique to assess EM, which was frequently employed by earlier researchers (Siekelova *et al.*, 2021; Dakhllalh *et al.*, 2020; Mitra, 2002). There are two main kinds of accruals: discretionary accruals and non-discretionary accruals. In contrast to discretionary accruals, which are cash flow adjustments made by business management, non-discretionary accruals adhere to norms established by regulatory agencies, according to Rao and Dandale (2008). "Total accruals" is a phrase used to describe the difference between a company's cash flows for a given fiscal year and net income. Healy (1995) provides additional confirmation of using total accruals to look for EM.

Managers frequently transfer earnings data across years using discretionary accruals. Real earnings of the company may be determined by separating non-discretionary accruals from total accruals, although managers are incapable of controlling this process. "Absolute value of discretionary accruals" is used in this investigation to evaluate EM, like in other studies (Jones, 1991; Subramanyam, 1996). A "cross-sectional" variant of the modified

Jones Model was utilised to compute discretionary accruals in this investigation (Jaggi and Leung 2007), as described by Dechow, Sloan, and Sweeny (1995).

3.4.2. Independent Variables

An improved CG structure will help to lessen the managers' profit management efforts (Abbadi, Hijazi, and Al-Rahahleh, 2016). To evaluate the hypotheses, this study employed CG techniques as independent variables to identify the connection between CG mechanisms and EM. The proportion of female executives, size of the audit committee, the size of the company's board, the percentage of independent board members (also known as board independence), and the independent chairperson are examples of CG mechanisms that are used as independent variables.

Numerous academics have considered the topic of board size and hypothesised that smaller boards may be more effective than bigger ones (Githaiga, Muturi, and Caroline, 2022; Al-Azeez, Sukoharsono, and Andayani, 2019; Jensen, 1993; Lipton and Lorsch, 1992). However, other research has establish a relation between a board's size and effective EM (Kao and Chen, 2004). According to Dechow, Sloan, and Sweeney's (1996) theory, a bigger board size may be related to increased cases of EM. All the female board members were compared against the overall quantity of the company's board members to assess the board's diversity (Torchia, Calabro, and Huse, 2011).

Research has shown that organisations are more likely to manage their profitability when the ratio of financial leverage is higher. To analyse the total debt to total assets ratio, financial leverage was used as a control variable in this study. The financial leverage of a corporation, which signifies its reliance on debt and equity, may be used to assess its capacity to satisfy financial obligations. Managers mostly rely on discretionary accruals to fulfil debt covenants. Thus, this research used financial leverage as a control variable.

According to Sweeney (1994) and DeFond and Jiambalvo (1994), companies that practice EM are more likely to have higher leverage ratios.

3.4.3. Control Variables

Control variables utilised are leverage, debt-to-asset, and return on asset. To avoid misspecification problems, control variables are used consistent with independent and dependent variables while calculating discretionary accruals. Leverage, debt-to-asset ratio, and return on asset ratios were used in this study as control variables.

CG measures such as audit committee size, size of the board, ratio of non-executive board members, independent chairperson, and percentage of females on the board are used as independent variables. The absolute value of discretionary accruals is utilised as the dependent variable. Debt-to-asset ratio, leverage, and return on asset are used as control variables. In identifying EM, proxies might include measurement errors. It is assumed that measurement errors could be avoided by including control variables. For example, big companies tend to be monitored more closely by interested parties, which might lead to less earnings management. However, these companies often have more complex managerial structures and numerous economic transactions that can be managed opportunistically. As a result, the connection between a company's size or board size and the incentive for management to manipulate earnings is uncertain. This study used the leverage ratio, which is explained as the sum of short- and long-term debt divided by total common equity (Saona, Muro, and Alvarado, 2020).

Dependent Variables	Absolute Value of Discretionary Accruals
Independent Variables	Size of the Audit Committee Board Size Number of Independent Directors Independent Chairperson Women Board Members
Control Variables	Leverage Debt to Asset Ratio Return on Asset

3.5. Different Approaches to Measure Discretionary Accruals

Discretionary accruals are calculated to detect EM. This study used the Modified Jones model for this purpose, although there are many approaches used by various researchers. Two ways to compute total accruals are the cash flow approach and the balance sheet approach (Acar and Coskun, 2020). Previous researchers have used various models to calculate discretionary accruals, depending on the goal of the study or the data sample. Some have utilised total accruals as a proxy (Kothari *et al.*, 2005; Dechow *et al.*, 1995), while others have used specific accruals (Beaver and McNichols, 1998). The main goal of most of these models is to detect discretionary accruals as a way to measure EM.

Healy Model (1985)

This model considers non-discretionary accruals as unobservable and calculates the EM element by comparing total accruals between the last two accounting periods (Bilan and Jurickova, 2021).

De Angelo Model (1986)

This calculates EM similarly to the previous model except it considers the first variance as null or zero (Bilan and Jurickova, 2021).

Jones Model (1991)

This model aims to mitigate the impact of economic fluctuations on non-discretionary accruals, which remain consistent over periods. Changing discretionary accruals also affects accruals, and these may change based on managerial decisions or economic conditions. This approach takes into account fluctuations in income and PPE in the EM estimating model (Strakova, 2020).

Industrial Model by Dechow and Sloan (1991)

Their model suggests that non-discretionary accrual factors vary between enterprises within the same industry while measuring EM (Siekelova, 2021).

Modified Jones Model (1991)

The Jones Model was modified by Dechow, Sloan, and Sweeney (1995). The key difference between this model and the Jones Model is the inclusion of changes in accounts receivable elements when calculating non-discretionary accruals. This model is widely used by researchers and is believed to be the strongest at detecting earnings management (Indriani and Pujiono, 2021).

3.6. Models

The most popular method for spotting EM is still the modified Jones' (1991) Model as it is the most effective (Bilan and Jurickova, 2021; Dechow, Sloan, and Sweeny, 1995; Guay, Kothari, and Watts, 1996). Similar to other researchers, such as Garcia *et al.* (2012),

discretionary accruals are generated by deducting non-discretionary accruals. Higher discretionary accruals suggest a company is engaged in EM activities. Davidson *et al.* (2005) indicated that the modified Jones model was the best option available for calculating discretionary accruals, and they used it in this study to detect EM.

The model and formulae are described in the paragraphs that follow.

Formula 1: $TACC_{it} = NI_{it} - CFO_{it}$

This formula is used to determine the total accruals. To do this, the total cash flow from the operation in the same financial year is subtracted from the net profit.

$TACC_{it}$ refers to the Total Accruals of the company.

NI_{it} refers to the Net Income before extraordinary items of the company.

CFO_{it} refers to the Cash Flows from the operations of the company.

$it = i$ refers to a specific company, and t refers to a particular financial year of the same company.

Formula 2:

$$\frac{TACC_{it}}{A_{it-1}} = \alpha_0 \left(\frac{1}{A_{it-1}} \right) + \alpha_1 \left[\frac{(\Delta REV_{it} - \Delta REC_{it})}{A_{it-1}} \right] + \alpha_2 \left(\frac{PPE_{it}}{A_{it-1}} \right) + \epsilon_{it}$$

The Jones model is utilised to evaluate industry-specific parameters of each firm's total accruals (TACC).

A_{it-1} refers to the company's total assets.

ΔREV_{it} relates to fluctuations in the company's revenue.

ΔREC_{it} refers to the changes in the Receivables of the company.

PPE_{it} refers to the Total Property, Plant and Equipment of the company.

ε_{it} refers to the cross-sectional uncorrelated and normally distributed data with a mean of zero for the regression error terms.

$it-1 = i$ refers to a particular firm, while t refers to a specific fiscal year for the same firm., and -1 refers to the deduction of 1 (as a current year) from the specific firm's financial year.

Formula 3:

$$DACC_{it} = (TACC_{it}/A_{it-1}) - [\alpha_0(1/A_{it-1})] + \alpha_1[(\Delta REV_{it} - \Delta REC_{it})/A_{it-1}] + [\alpha_2(PPE_{it}/A_{it-1})]$$

The difference between TACC and the non-discretionary components of accruals is what this method uses to compute discretionary accruals, which is the last step. The discretionary income components from accounts receivable were removed by Dechow, Sloan, and Sweeney (1995), who modified the Jones model. Possessing anticipated discretionary accruals signifies that the company's managers actively managed earnings. Once interest, taxes, and other expenses have been subtracted, the amount of the reported profits is known as the company's net earnings.

3.7. Measuring Earnings Management

Independent variables such as the audit committee size, company board size, independent board members, independent chairperson, and proportion of female board members and control variables such as leverage, debt, and return to asset ratios were compared against the dependent variable (absolute value of discretionary accruals as $ABSDACC$) to measure the significance. An empirical formula was created to evaluate how corporate governance frameworks affected the management of earnings and accomplishing the primary goals of this research. The empirical formula is as follows.

$$ABSDACC_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 SIZEAUDITCOM_{it} + \beta_2 BOARDSIZE_{it} + \beta_3 BOARDIND_{it} + \beta_4 INDEPCHRPRSN_{it} + \beta_5 WOMBOARD_{it} + \beta_6 LEVERAGE_{it} + \beta_7 DEBT_{it} + \beta_8 ROA_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

ABSDACC= refers to the company's "absolute value of discretionary accruals" or the factors that affect EM.

SIZEAUDITCOM= relates to total audit committee members.

BOARDSIZE= refers to overall company board members, including independent non-executives, the chairman, and the CEO.

BOARDIND= relates to the proportion of independent board members of the firm.

INDEPCHRPRSN= refers to the board chairperson being independent.

WOMBOARD= refers to the ratio of women as board members.

LEVERAGE= refers to the liabilities to total assets ratio of the company.

DEBT= refers to the total debt to total company assets ratio.

ROA= refers to the return on assets ratio of the company.

3.8. Access Issues

This study uses two resources to test the hypotheses. First, financial information was collected using Bloomberg Terminal, Refinitiv, FAME and other data sources provided by the university. Among the financial data acquired are earlier yearly reports of 101 firms traded on the LSE as part of the "FTSE 100" index. Secondly, the literature related to the topic of this study was reviewed to understand the views of others and to compare their outcomes with the findings of this study. The works of literature were collected via the university library website. University student login IDs were used to gain access.

3.9. Ethical Issues

The research was carried out following the ethical criteria for research established by the University of the West of Scotland. This study does not use any surveys or interviews. This study did not use human interference nor harm anybody during the test period. Hence, ethical approval was not required. Financial statements of firms in the UK were collected via Bloomberg Terminal, Refinitiv, FAME, and other sources provided by the university. All the related literature reviewed while conducting this research was accessed from the university library website using the student login ID. Additionally, this material is original to the researcher and free of plagiarism and copyright violations.

3.10. Conclusion

This study used data from UK-listed firms. Discretionary accruals were used to identify EM activities, with a greater level of discretionary accruals indicating a higher level of EM. The Modified Jones Model was utilised to compute discretionary accruals, using various types of variables such as independent, dependent, and control variables. Discretionary accruals were the dependent variable, while CG mechanisms were used as independent variables. Additionally, leverage, debt-to-asset ratio, and return on assets were used as control variables.

Chapter 4

Results

4.1. Introduction

This research intends to detect the relationship between CG mechanisms and EM. Much prior research has been conducted on this subject. The UK is one of the first countries to introduce CG mechanisms to safeguard businesses and their investors. This study used UK-listed companies as data samples, as most current research seems to have avoided them while conducting similar investigations. For measuring EM, discretionary accruals appear to be the best solution. The Modified Jones Model is used to calculate discretionary accruals. Then, an empirical model was used to verify the connection between discretionary accruals and CG mechanisms.

4.2. Analysis

The impact of CG mechanisms on EM was assessed using SPSS statistical software. Descriptive statistics shown below are generated to help the readers understand the data gathered from the firms' annual financial reports:

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics				
Variables	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
ABSDACC	.00	.12	.0367	.03375
Board Size	5.0	21.0	10.916	2.5415
Number of Independent Directors	3.0	16.0	7.443	2.1860
Board Chair Independent	.0	1.0	.599	.4907
Size of Audit Committee	2.0	8.0	4.260	1.1530
Women on the Board	.0	8.0	2.319	1.3785
Leverage	.00000	241.15278	9.6715543	26.28274569
Debt Assets Ratio	.000	69.602	23.24015	15.405884
Return on Assets	-21.538	45.551	6.59325	7.701252
Independent, dependent and control variables				

The minimum and maximum absolute values for discretionary accruals are 0.00 and 0.12, respectively, with a mean value of 0.0367. The standard deviation of the discretionary accruals' absolute value is 0.03375. Board size values range from a minimum of 5 to a maximum of 21, with a mean value of 10.916. The board size's standard deviation value is 2.5415. This indicates that most FTSE 100 firms have relatively large company boards. However, these companies are among the biggest in the country. This result is comparable with Saona, Muro, and Alvarado's (2020) research using data from Sapis companies.

With a mean value of 7.443, the total of independent directors ranges from 3 to 16 at most. The amount of independent directors' standard deviation is 2.1860. According to the mean value of the independent directors' number, the FTSE 100 companies have a comparatively more significant percentage of independent directors. However, the descriptive value of board independence goes opposite with previous study and is also similar to El Diri, Lambrinouidakis, and Alhadab (2020). The mean value for the independent chair of the corporate board is 0.599, with the minimum and maximum values ranging between 0 and 1. The independent chair of the corporate board's standard deviation is 0.4907. This indicates that many companies in this study do not have an independent chairperson on their board.

With a mean value of 4.260, the total of audit committee members differs from a minimum of two to a maximum of eight. The audit committee size's standard deviation figure is 1.1530. These statistics indicate that many firms have an audit committee with only two members, probably impacting the accuracy of financial data. Minimum and maximum values for the ratio of female executives are between zero to eight, respectively, with a mean value of 2.319. The ratio of female to male directors on the company board has a standard deviation of 1.3785. These statistics indicate that many companies employed in this study do not have female board members and are expected to suffer from diversity issues. As shown in the

literature review chapter, several authors suggest that having more female members on the company board improves supervision capability.

The minimum and maximum value of leverage is .00000 to 241.15278 respectively, with a mean value of 9.6715543. The standard deviation value of leverage is 26.28274569. This result indicate companies using higher debt compared to companies in Saudi Arabia as suggest by Abdalkrim, G. (2019). The minimum and maximum value of debt to asset ratio is .000 to 69.602 respectively, with a mean value of 23.24015. The standard deviation value of debt to asset ratio is 15.405884. The minimum and maximum value of return on asset is -21.538 to 45.551 respectively, with a mean value of 6.59325. The standard deviation value of return on asset is 7.701252.

Table 4.2: Regression Analysis

Model Summary					
Multiple R	.702				
R ²	.493				
Adjusted R ²	.223				
Standard error	.02975				
ANOVA					
	Sum of square	DF	Mean square	F	Sig.
Regression	.013	8	0.002	1.826	.150
Residual	.013	15	0.001		
Total	.026	23			
Coefficients					
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	<i>t</i>	Sig.
	B	Std. error	Beta		
(Constant)	.074	.047		1.586	.134
Board Size	.002	.006	.197	.393	.700
Number of Independent	-.006	.004	-.455	-1.597	.131

Directors					
Board Chair	.020	.028	.308	.727	.478
Independent					
Size of Audit	-.003	.008	-.136	-.396	.697
Committee					
Women on	-.005	.009	-.279	-.536	.600
the Board					
Leverage	.001	.002	.206	.560	.584
Debt Assets	.000	.001	.103	.288	.777
Ratio					
Return on	-.003	.001	-.437	-2.066	.057
Assets					

A regression analysis was created with SPSS and used to accomplish the study's key goals. To summarise the outcomes, value of multiple R is 0.702, and its R-squared value is 0.493. The value of standard error is 0.02975, while the adjusted R square value is 0.223. The outcomes of the regression are shown in Table 4.2. As stated in the methodology chapter, all elements linked to corporate governance are used as an independent variable, and the dependent variable is the total amount of discretionary accruals. The sum of squares regression value shows 0.013, with a degree of freedom (df) of 8 and a mean square of 0.002. The f value was 1.826, and the significant value was 0.150. That is more than the test's significant level of value. It must be 5% to qualify as significant. Thus, it is assumed that this regression outcome is not statistically noteworthy.

The coefficient results of the regression in Table 4.2 indicate a mixed result when analysing the effects of CG measures on EM. As indicated above, there are unfavourable relationships between three CG measures and the absolute value of discretionary accruals.

However, an adverse link is apparent between the other three CG mechanisms and the absolute value of discretionary accruals.

An unstandardised coefficient B value of 0.074 and a standard error of 0.047 are shown as the value for discretionary accruals. The discretionary accruals' absolute value shows a significance figure of 0.134 with a t value of 1.586. The significant figure exceeds the 5% necessary substantial level. Although this result indicates a positive correlation, the coefficient findings lack statistical significance. The independent variable here is the size of the board, and its unstandardised coefficient B value is 0.002, which is a 0.006 standard error. The standardised coefficients' B value is 0.197, and their t-value is 0.393. The significant level of the board size indicates 0.700. That exceeds the 5% threshold for significance. Though this result positively affects EM components, the coefficient results are not statistically significant.

As an independent variable, the unstandardised coefficient B value for the ratio of independent directors is -0.006 with a standard error of 0.004. The standardised coefficients' B value is -0.455, and their t value is -1.597. The ratio of independent directors at the substantial level is indicated by 0.131. This is greater than the 5% threshold for significance. The coefficient values are not statistically significant even though this outcome shows that a bad association exists between the proportion of independent executives and EM. The independent chairperson on the corporate board is another independent variable with a value of 0.020 unstandardised coefficient B and a standard error of 0.028. Standardised coefficients have a B value of 0.308 and a t value of 0.727. The significant level of the independent chairperson indicates 0.478. That exceeds the threshold of 5%, which is considered significant. However, the results are not statistically significant, even if they show positive influences on EM.

The audit committee's size has an unstandardised coefficient B value of -0.003 and a standard error of 0.008 as an independent variable. The standardised coefficients' B value is -0.136, and their t value is -0.396. The significant level of the size of the audit committee is

0.697. This is more than the 5% level of significance. The correlation results are not statistically significant. However, this result does indicate a negative link with EM. The unstandardised coefficient B value for the proportion of female board members is -0.005, with a standard error of 0.009. The standardised coefficients' B value is -0.279, and their t value is -0.536. The ratio of female board members shows a significance level of 0.600. This is greater than the 5% threshold for significance. The coefficient results are not statistically significant, even though this result reveals a bad correlation with the total amount of discretionary accruals.

Table 4.3: Correlation Matrix						
	ABSDACC	Board Size	Number of Independent Directors	Board Chair independent	Size of Audit Committee	Women on the Board
ABSDACC	1					
Board Size	-0.240	1				
Number of Independent Directors	-0.370	.704**	1			
Board Chair independent	-0.028	-.107*	0.090	1		
Size of Audit Committee	-0.191	.330**	.317**	.150**	1	
Women on the Board	-0.108	.387**	.362**	.381**	.271**	1
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).						
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).						

The correlation matrix above shows different findings. Although, the results are not statistically significant. The size of the company board has a Pearson correlation value of -0.240, indicating an adverse link between the board's size and the total value of discretionary accruals. This is similar to Saona, Muro, and Alvarado's (2020) result. Although, both results

indicate a negative relationship but are not statistically significant. The value of the ratio of independent directors is negatively correlated with discretionary accruals' absolute value, as indicated by the figure of -0.370. The independent chairperson's Pearson correlation score of -0.028 indicates a bad link with the absolute amount of discretionary accruals. An unfavourable relationship between the audit committee size and the elements of the EM system is shown by the value of -0.191. Similarly, a value of -0.108 is conducted by the ratio of women as board members, indicating an adverse correlation with the absolute amount of discretionary accruals. Although correlation indicates an adverse association with EM, significant levels are higher than 5% and statistically insignificant.

4.3. Discussion

Company executives primarily engage in opportunistic behaviour to help themselves rather than serve the best interest of shareholders. Company managers mislead stakeholders with unreliable financial information (Mortas, 2019; Healy and Wahlen, 1999). This investigation aims to identify managers' EM behaviours and investigate if corporate governance tools may help to prevent such behaviour. In the UK, the term "earnings management" is used to describe managers' opportunistic behaviour. Managers appear to have managed earnings following widely accepted accounting principles. The link between EM and CG mechanisms is examined in this research using the modified Jones model. The dependent variable was the discretionary accruals' total value, while a total of five CG mechanisms served as the independent variables during the analysis. The test was conducted using SPSS software, which produced regression results. The result shows statistically insignificant outcomes, although independent variables (CG proxies) indicate a negative relationship with EM.

According to past studies, good corporate governance rules may assist in limiting how businesses manage their revenues (Xie, Davidson, and DaDalt, 2003; Al-Haddad and Whittington, 2019). Since independent directors are better suited to oversee and regulate the

company's managers, there is a lower chance of managers misappropriating funds in opposition to shareholders' interests. As a result, the ratio of independent board members serves as a valid proxy for assessing the success of internal CG and board performance. For this reason, this research uses the ratio of independent directors as a proxy to determine its association with EM. Statistically speaking, the findings were not significant. The test included 101 businesses listed on the LSE as part of the FTSE 100 index. Their annual reports from 2019 to 2022 were collected to gather the required information.

Independent directors are outsiders who have no past ties to the firm. As a result, their presence increases the board's oversight of management (Lee *et al.*, 1992). They are more inclined to seek to further the stockholders' interests in the business. The number of independent directors and EM were shown to be negatively correlated in this study. The outcome was insignificant, but it did suggest that independent directors would probably contribute less to EM effort. Kapoor and Goel (2019) also suggest similar findings while analysing companies in India. The firm's board is held back from misconduct, such as preventing or rejecting a takeover (Kosnik, 1990), by having more independent directors. The administration will likely be under pressure from the independent directors and may resign (Weisbach, 1988; Fogel, Ma, and Morck, 2021).

According to Brickley and James (1987), the directors' remuneration is inversely connected with the ratio of independent members and independent board members who prevent managers from receiving excessive compensation. The agency cost of an organisation is likely to decrease because of independent directors, who guarantee that executive managers continue operating in the stockholders' best interests by being on the company board. Companies are also obliged under the UK Corporate Governance Code to ensure that the board of directors have an appropriate percentage of independent board members. By doing this, executive directors are prevented from faking financial data for their gain. The Corporate Governance

Code also restricts non-duality roles in the listed firms. As the board is governed by the chairperson, that helps limit the influence of the company's CEO. In contrast, the CEO runs the day-to-day business. Jaggi, Leung, and Gul (2009) contend that monitoring facilities over management increases after independent directors are included on the company board. The outcome of this study also indicates a adverse relationship between board independence and the management of earnings by the executive (Fogel, Ma, and Morck, 2021).

Numerous studies, like those by Kao, Hodgkinson, and Jaafar (2019); Ezzamel and Watson (1993); Vance (1964); and Pearce and Zhara (1992), concur with the discoveries from this research that independent directors have a favourable impact on corporate performance. However, authors finding opposite results include Yermack (1996); Klein (1998); and Agrawal and Knoeber (1996). Moreover, Daily and Dalton (1992) indicate no relations at all. Board independence grows when the firm's board has more members who are independent. That makes it easier to prevent managers from carrying out EM activities, as suggested by Dechow and Dichev (2002); Jensen and Fama (1983); and Peasnell, Pope, and Young (2000). This is so they can avoid pursuing self-interests like CEO pay and asset theft. They must maintain a professional image while meeting or exceeding business performance standards without shareholder pressure.

The firm's board must be independent to control management's behaviour and protect investors' interests (Saona, Muro, and Alvarado, 2020; Williamson, 1981). Roe (1991) asserts that board independence can shield managers against abuse of authority and a decline in investor interest. An important consideration is that shareholders can select whether independent directors will be reappointed. Independent directors are thus under pressure to oversee management. Insiders are more likely to govern organisations with severe EM than outsiders are (Dechow, Sloan, and Sweeney, 1996). By having a significant ratio of independent directors, the risk of financial information theft can be decreased (Beasley, 1996).

When a member of the founding family holds the position of senior executive officer, the business lacks independence and is more likely to provide incorrect accounting information (Agrawal and Chadha, 2005). Companies in the UK can benefit from having more independent directors by better managing income-increasing discretionary spending, which can help prevent EM (Peasnell, Pope, and Young, 2005). Evidence from the USA indicates an inverse relationship between EM and board independence (Klein, 2002). Additional research confirms this (Uzun *et al.*, 2004). Compared to organisations with higher levels of board independence and intuitive engagement, Australian enterprises with a dual function for the CEO have a higher incidence of fraud (Sharma, 2004). According to Xie, Davidson, and DaDalt (2003) and Peasnell, Pope, and Young (2000), EM and board independence are related.

Other authors acknowledge the significance of board independence. Board independence is a crucial element of efficient CG systems, according to Dixon, Mousa, and Woodhead (2005), even if corporate governance is a continually evolving mechanism and cannot ensure a “no failure” environment. Boards with a higher ratio of independent board members will have a lower tendency to control their profits and are therefore more likely to conduct accurate monitoring, which raises the quality of earnings (Alves, 2014; Swai and Mbogela, 2016; Vafeas, 2000; Marra, Mazzola, and Prencipe, 2011). A favourable connection between board independence and EM was shown by Firth, Fung, and Rui (2007) using the earnings response coefficient. Bushman, Chen, and Engel (2004) reported the same results using the measures for responsiveness and informativeness.

Fuzi, Halim, and Julizaerma (2016) found contradictory evidence to Ahmed, Hossain, and Adams' (2006) findings that there is no connection between EM and board independence. The success of board independence depends on competence, dedication, and the environment as a whole (Van den Berghe and Baelden, 2005). On the other hand, it was discovered that China's independent director structure was insufficient due to substantial promoter influence

and the directors' ignorance of their tasks (Kakabadse, Yang, and Sanders, 2010). Independent directors could not adequately worry about the firm's performance in the long run because of their limited engagement and personal interests in it. People usually have a great desire to repay favours, according to the Law of Reciprocity (Caliendo, Fossen, and Kritikos, 2012).

Most of these studies concern the managing of discretionary accrual-based earnings. Unfortunately, the value of this model is unclear since it is only slightly good at establishing correlations between dependent and independent variables. Due to the exclusion of the linked components for non-discretionary accruals, the model's test was incorrectly specified. The model developed by Jansen may be required in future studies on EM. The test's explanatory power can be improved by evaluating its profit margin on the asset turnover ratio. Among others, Williamson (1988), and Morck, Shleifer, and Vishny (1988) assert that the board's composition affects its performance. A manager who is also an inside executive will have easier access to corporate data to keep tabs on management. The likelihood of inside directors working with management to blackmail outside shareholders is higher (Trautman *et al.*, 2022).

According to Fama (1980), since external directors are not management team members, they may be able to monitor it more successfully. It has been determined that increasing the number of independent board members decreases the likelihood of financial misconduct. The outside directors will probably expand the board's oversight responsibilities. There have been conflicting results from earlier research on the arrangement of the ideal board of directors. Boards with internal managers are a good control strategy, claims Liu (2012). In addition, insiders have the edge over outsiders due to their position inside the organisation, according to Klein (1998). They are more familiar with the specifics of the business and have ready access to information that can help them make better decisions.

Numerous studies claim that independent board directors outperform insider directors; only the board enhances internal control inside firms. Since outsiders are not bound to

management and are free to behave impartially and independently during their supervisory mandates, they can successfully monitor managers' behaviour. According to earlier studies, the effect of board composition is inversely connected with board independence and EM (Liu and Lu, 2007; Klein, 2002). Fama and Jensen (1983) argue that boards with a majority of outsiders are better able to keep an eye on and regulate managers' behaviour. Board independence is a preferable strategy for management monitoring, according to Beasley (1996), who also recommended minimising EM strategies and avoiding financial statement fraud. According to Anuchitworawong (2004), independent board members would be the only ones with the authority to forbid EM techniques.

These results have also been confirmed in a financial environment. A weak association between board independence and discretionary loan loss provision in US banks was also found by Cornett, McNutt, and Tehranian (2009). Quttainah, Song, and Wu (2013) discovered that independent boards are linked to lower discretionary accruals. Businesses with more independent directors on their corporate boards tend to have reduced EM activities because independent board members are thought to be more willing to monitor than inside directors. This is backed by research from Ianniello (2015) and Heirany, Sadrabadi, and Mehrjordi (2013).

The test results regarding the audit committee's size are identical to those mentioned previously. The audit committee's size was shown to be adversely correlated with EM, although this research's regression was statistically insignificant. These writers contend that the audit committee is crucial to the operation of the business (Alzoubi, 2019; Ngo and Le, 2021). They are there to guarantee accurate financial data. It has been demonstrated that boards and audit committees with higher levels of involvement perform as efficient gatekeepers of a company's financial statements, discouraging EM. Fama and Jensen (1983) suggest that the company's governing body is the foundation of CG, and how it is structured influences how successfully

it fulfils its tasks. They contend that since they will not interfere with management, outside directors are perfectly able to oversee it. The necessity for the auditor to give trustworthy and transparent financial information has become known due to current noteworthy company failures. However, the reliability of certified financial data and the quality of reported results are perceived by investors as typically declining (Hodge, 2003).

These findings suggest that audit restrictions on earning management become more critical. According to the current study, auditors have different levels of control over earning management. Auditors employed by large accounting firms are likelier than those working for smaller accounting firms to show stronger reporting conservatism (Bartov, Gul, and Tsui, 2000). Compared to auditors without the appropriate expertise, auditors in major accounting firms are more willing to restrict the management of earnings (Krishnan, 2003; Alvarado, De Fuentes, and Laffarga, 2019). Researchers Hackenbrack and Nelson (1996) discovered that auditors are more inclined to endorse clients' plans for extreme profit management when accounting rules are flexible and management is asked to use extensive judgement. When evaluating whether to allow aggressive reporting, auditors take into account the client's economic situation, significance, and the chance that the auditor may be sued (Becker *et al.*, 1998). According to the UK's corporate governance law, businesses are advised to establish a board of independent directors-led audit committee. As previously stated, independent directors are not tied to administration. They are expected to prevent managers from engaging in aggressive, opportunistic behaviours.

Auditors suggest less aggressive financial reporting options discovered by Johnson, Khurana, and Reynolds (2002) and Fuller, Joe, and Luippold (2021) when confronted with aggressive EM. The claim that earnings manipulation is distinct from aggressive accounting is not well supported by evidence, although extensive investigation has been done on the auditor restrictions on EM. The audit committee meets the requirements of the management, owners,

creditors, and other stakeholders in the firm in various ways. Enhancing the trustworthiness of financial data used by stakeholders to make decisions is one of these requirements. Agency theory is essential when ownership and administration are split. The shareholder's and management's interests cannot overlap since doing so might result in resource misuse.

Managers routinely manage earnings to cover up their opportunistic behaviour. The audit committee may aggressively supervise the work of internal auditors and elect top-notch auditors from outside to boost the calibre of financial reports. The committee also has this obligation in the USA to ensure internal control performance following Sarbanes-Oxley Act requirements. Better internal control may be maintained to increase financial information and decrease EM. Keeping internal controls in good working order may lessen EM and improve accounting information. If the audit committee has constraints, it may be less able to ensure that financial accounting is accurate (Song and Windram, 2004; Ashraf, Michas, and Russomanno, 2020). Corporate governance acknowledges an audit committee as a key device that lowers EM.

To give the audit committee a specific responsibility for monitoring financial information and external auditor actions, many trading exchanges such as the UK, US, and HK demand a considerable ratio of independent directors (non-executive) who are not taking part in the company's day-to-day tasks. This condition was specified in the literature review chapter. Businesses with significant outside directors on their committees are better at managing their income (Chtourou, Bedard, and Courteau, 2001; Saona, Muro, and Alvarado, 2020). Audit committee members may not be able to adequately supervise managers who participate in high-level profitability management if they have shares in the company. According to Abbott *et al.* (2004), audit expertise can assist in avoiding corruption and profit reversal, two issues that influence EM.

Accounting and financial expertise may minimise EM for organisations with other inadequate CG mechanisms (Al-Haddad and Whittington, 2019). Furthermore, Carcello, Hollingsworth, and Neal (2006) show that independent board members with experience in finance and accounting make up the audit committee's most potent composition for thwarting opportunistic profit management. A trade-off is made between financial knowledge and other company governance instruments due to the narrow definition of financial competence. They claimed that having an audit committee member with financial knowledge was not connected with genuine profitability management. Although it dramatically influences businesses with other poor corporate governance practices, the audit committee's financial expertise does not gradually diminish EM.

As a result, firms operating in the United Kingdom must form with a financial expert who is an independent audit committee member. Members of financially competent audit committees can reduce EM, as claimed by Bedard, Chtourou, and Courteau's (2004) research on US-based corporations. However, they could not find a connection between the audit committee's size and EM. Independent audit committees can reduce profit manipulation, claim Turner and Vann (2010). The Sarbanes-Oxley Act has a strong detrimental influence on EM, according to several earlier research (Cohen *et al.*, 2005). US corporate laws are strict. However, the earlier research found no impact on profit management even after the Sarbanes-Oxley was implemented. However, the result from this study suggests a negative relationship between size of the audit committee and EM but it was not statistically significant.

Atu *et al.* (2016) suggest that to avoid management opportunism and creative financial reporting, auditors are essential. Due to the costs associated with signing contracts with clients, auditors will ensure that clients are provided with as much information as possible in their annual reports and accounts. One of the resources that the audit committee or auditors may have access to is the ability of the auditors. The audit committee's size depends on all the committee

members. Previous study has presented that an auditor's size can affect evaluation (Yermack, 1996). Major audit firms are less prone to favour control of earnings because they are more likely to offer the resistance, variety of viewpoints, and experience required for successful supervision and reporting procedures, according to Bedard, Chtourou, and Courteau (2004). In contrast, smaller audit companies will most likely struggle to recognise and address any complications with the financial reporting process.

As a result, well-known and sizeable audit firms dissuade businesses from falsifying their revenues. Larger audit firms and auditors are more concerned with upholding their reputations because they have more clients to lose if their findings are not considered consistent, reliable, and accurate. Big audit companies have a higher wealth risk in the case of any litigations, claim *Atu et al.* (2016). They are probably more precise. Independent directors are required to form the audit committee in the UK. More committee members supported lowering EM. This study explored the connection between the size of the audit committee and EM. To conduct the test, the number of audit committee members was used as a proxy. A negative relationship was observed, although the results were found to be insignificant.

A firm's board size is important in maintaining its activities. It is a crucial CG instrument. To assess the relationship between board size and EM, all the company board of directors were used as a proxy in this study, including independent directors, the CEO, and the chairman. The findings were inconsistent. In contrast to the correlation matrix, the regression results show a positive relationship. Mansor *et al.*'s (2013) findings are incompatible with this outcome. Moreover, both outcomes were statistically insignificant. Many researchers have also shown conflicting results while determining a relationship between managers' opportunistic behaviour and the company board. Researchers compare EM strategies to corporate governance processes and provide several recommendations.

Board independence and board size are the two CG approaches most frequently used, for example, when examining the connection between EM and CG mechanisms. Compared to the result of this study, numerous academics have found no connection between board size and EM. Siregar and Utama (2008), Gulzar and Wang (2011), and Saleh, Iskandar, and Rahmat (2005) are some of these researchers. Research by Swastika (2013) indicated an adverse connection between EM and board size, in contrast to studies by Chaharsoughi and Rahman (2013) that indicate a favourable relationship. All the company board of directors members were used as a proxy in each of the studies mentioned above to define the board size.

One key mechanism of corporate governance is board size, which was significant in earlier research (Zeitlin, 1976; Puni and Anlesinya, 2020). The composition of the board, including its size, percentage of non-executive independent board members, non-duality, and non-multiple members, are all influenced by the total number of members (Jaggi, Leung, and Gul, 2009; Dhaliwal, Naiker, and Navissi, 2010). The stakeholders must get reliable financial reports from them. The number of board members of each sample firm for a certain accounting year represents the size of the company's board. This figure includes the CEO, chairman, non-executive, executive, and outside members (Shakir, 2008; Sarhan, Ntim, and Al-Najjar, 2019). Sometimes, problems with the company's board of directors might motivate people to control outcomes. Businesses might indeed suffer when they do not perform well.

Managers and the board can decide whether to manipulate earnings higher to maintain their reputation, their positions, and their likelihood of being fairly compensated and to improve their chances in the modern workplace, although it has previously anticipated its goals and reported incomes that were different from those predicted, according to Fortin, Subramaniam, Wang, and Zhang (2011) and Sun, Wang, Wang, and Zhang (2013). According to Ashiq and Weining's 2015 study on EM during an executive's initial years of work, new managers and

freshly chosen boards raise the outcome to increase their competitiveness. Most CEO control their results to avoid disappointing investors and appear to be working hard.

The desire of insiders to maintain and sustain the firm's reputation by carrying out their stakeholder obligations serves as another motivation to manage earnings. The various company and board-related factors may impact the management of earnings. According to Mard (2003) and Callao, Wroblewski, and Jarne (2021), four main motivations might lead managers to manipulate profitability. This includes managerial salary, regulatory and capital market incentives, and incentives from external contracts. The board's main duty is to reduce agency costs brought on by the division of ownership and control (Fama and Jensen, 1983). As boards get larger, the amount of board supervision declines. It becomes considerably more challenging for board members to communicate effectively as it increases.

Therefore, the board's function becomes less important when the number of individuals grows. A weak board makes it more likely that management would falsify profits (Jensen, 1993). According to Dechow, Sloan, and Sweeney (1996), organisations adopting EM have bigger boards than those that do not. Although research by Fuerst and Kang (2004) suggests, that board size and corporate value are not positively correlated. Some academics state that big boards have the requisite skills, networks, and competencies for effective and successful board functioning (Xie, Davidson, and DaDalt, 2003). They contend that resource dependency and agency theories reveal a favourable connection between business performance and board size. However, a large body of actual evidence suggests the opposite. This study finds bigger boards in most of the FTSE 100 companies ranging from 5 to 21 and the result indicate a negative relationship with EM.

Companies with a large board are not necessarily creative, especially if their makeup does not match the organisation's requirements (Pfeffer, 1972; Pfeffer, 2019). Because directors become less effective and "free-ride" on the examination of other directors, larger boards have

a detrimental influence on the level of performance and reporting (Jensen, 1993). Using data from 2011 to 2014, Lublin (2014) demonstrates that companies with smaller boards provide greater returns than those with larger boards. Results are mixed, but several studies-including those by Sahu and Manna (2013) and Shrivastav and Kalsie (2016)-indicate a positive link between board size and business performance. Other researchers, like Kumari and Pattanayak (2014), Gulzar (2011), and Beasley (1996), also indicate a negative relationship.

The association between EM and company board size has been empirically studied. There is no definite consensus regarding a link. Other experts say smaller boards effectively lower managers' opportunistic behaviour (Saona, Muro, and Alvarado, 2020). Other claims that large boards help monitor managers (Pucheta-Martínez and Gallego-Álvarez, 2020). According to Chtourou, Bedard, and Courteau (2001), bigger corporate boards increase productivity. They claim that larger committees have the authority to limit acts taken for EM. Larger boards, according to Xie *et al.* (2003), have comparatively fewer discretionary accruals. The results of other studies found that a bigger board of directors is linked to experience in enhancing its ability to regulate and monitor managers' activities (Dalton *et al.*, 1999; Peasnell, Pope, and Young, 2005).

The company board's size considerably affects its performance, as suggested by Jensen (1993). It is simpler for the CEO to manage money on boards with more than seven or eight members, and they have a lower chance of functioning properly. The findings imply that compact boards may be able to effectively regulate the CEO's behaviour and improve firm performance. Similarly, it was asserted that organisations with larger boards might have greater influence over their financial results (Dechow, Sloan, and Sweeney, 1996). Beasley (1996) agrees with this judgement as well.

Between 1980 and 1991, the researcher used a cross-sectional linear regression approach to look at the board composition of 75 dishonest and 75 honest publicly listed US

companies. They discovered that organisations with stronger boards have a higher likelihood of disclosing false financial information. The findings indicate that a smaller board size lowers the likelihood of material misstatements. According to Yermak (1996) and Saona, Muro, and Alvarado (2020), monitoring works better on smaller boards compared to bigger boards. They will be connected to bad EM practices as a result. Notably, the company's governing body is seen as the fundamental governance mechanism in the banking industry, according to Baysinger and Zardkoohi (1986), and Zulfikar *et al.* (2020). It must keep an eye on and control how banks behave.

It may thus have an impact on how profits are managed. The research on how board size affects financial reporting in banks has produced inconsistent results. According to Quttainah, Song, and Wu (2013), a sizeable board of directors can help Islamic banks combat fraud. These studies suggest that board size is a key factor impacting EM. Even yet, it might be difficult to assess the association between EM and company board size because of the inconsistent findings in earlier studies. As was previously noted, all business board members were employed as a proxy to assess the methods used by UK companies to manage earnings. The findings were not statistically significant.

Duality roles are restricted in the UK as a listing requirement (Kyerere and Ausloos, 2021). None of the sample firms used in this study has this situation, but the chairperson's independence is uncommon. That is measured to be a key element of the Corporate Governance Code. Therefore, this investigation aims to determine whether it connects with the EM strategies of UK enterprises. Companies with an independent chairperson levelled as one otherwise zero while conducting the test. Several studies appear to be interested in CEO duality. At the same time, this study finds chairpersons' independence to be an important factor for companies in the UK. This is because CEO duality almost does not exist among listed firms.

According to several studies, the partition of the CEO's and chairman's functions is a crucial element of boards. According to the Cadbury Committee (1992) and ASX (2003), the board's capacity to carry out a monitoring obligation is presumptively diminished when the CEO also works as the chairperson. Arthur and Taylor (1993) note that it is not known what basic economic forces led to their divergence. According to Beasley (1996), having the CEO named as the chairperson may lead to a power monopoly. As a result, possible conflicts of interest reduce oversight levels. The firm board is under the chairman's control. Frequently, the CEO also perform as the company chairperson.

The CEOs of these companies are in a nice place to keep an eye on both the current activities and the future course of their companies because of their varied duties. They oversee the senior executive selection, appraisal, and compensation procedures and, along with the CEO, determine the agendas for meetings. There can be a potential conflict of interest when the CEO also fulfils the chairperson's duty. The CEO or chairman oversees evaluation. It is improbable that the CEO or chairman could or would do this evaluation impartially.

Others have proposed splitting the CEO and chair positions to avoid such conflicts by having an impartial and external director hold the chairman position (Buchholz, Lopatta, and Maas, 2020). However, empirical studies by Molz (1988) and Daily and Dalton (1992) have demonstrated that keeping the CEO and board chair separate does not improve an organisation's performance. However, one may argue that management controls corporate boards and that having an external, independent chair has little impact on corporate decisions. For instance, in the past, Enron's CEO functioned as the company's CEO and the board chairperson, in contrast to WorldCom and Global Crossing, which split the responsibilities.

Although being the company's board chair is unquestionably important inside a corporation, in all three cases, the individual in control of that position could not stop inappropriate behaviour at work. To carry out its obligations, the board of directors frequently

forms committees. Although many firms use audit, pay, and nominating committees to support the board of directors, each company uses committees differently and has different objectives (Petra, 2005). The chairperson's job plays a part in improving the functioning of the board. An independent non-executive chairman enhances business success, according to various research studies (Donaldson and Davis, 1991; Rechner and Dalton, 1991).

Chaganti, Mahajan, and Sharman (1985) contend that executive chairs have little influence on a company's profitability. Compared to how duality was justified, independent chairs could encourage more responsibility. Most chairpersons in Malaysian firms are independent, non-executive directors who may provide additional information (Haniffa and Cooke, 2002). According to Cheung, Jiang, and Tan (2010), businesses where the chairperson of the board and CEO are different frequently have greater voluntary disclosure. Alternatively, Chau and Gray (2010) claim that Hong Kong's voluntary disclosure favourably correlates with the nomination of an independent chairman.

The board's capacity to accomplish its governance duties is possibly diminish when the CEO also serves as board chairman since the chairperson would have more control over the board. An important corporate governance tool is the non-duality of the job. Even so, this study looked at how the chairman-who is not just independent of the board but also does not act as CEO-relates to EM. An independent chairperson was vital for companies to overcome EM.

Corporate governance in the UK suggests gender diversification among companies. As a result, many firms have various roles filled with women nowadays. By reviewing multiple pieces of literature, this study finds that females on the board might help to increase supervision over management. Several authors also indicate that having female board members reduces EM activities. To evaluate the hypothesis, this research employed the proportion of female board members as a corporate governance proxy. It examines if this proxy correlated with EM. A mean value of 2.319 and a maximum value of 8 are displayed on the descriptive statistic as the

ratio of female members on the board. The minimum figure shows that many companies' boards do not have any female directors. According to the regression analysis and correlation matrix, EM and female board members have a negative link. However, it was not statistically significant.

Prior research has studied the ratio of female board members. Having female members tends to lead to increased demand for and monitoring of management performance (Adams and Ferreira, 2009). According to Carter, Simkins, and Simpson (2003), male and female directors have different capacities for autonomous thought and efficient executive behaviour control. Adams, Gray, and Nowland (2010) suggest that female board members are also better at critical thinking and efficient executive management. Since businesses with more women on the board typically deliver higher-quality results and require less executive management, this is an important factor in controlling profits. Independent thinking is essential for better financial data and to reduce opportunistic behaviour.

Male board members are less likely than female board members to object to the management's opportunistic behaviour, according to Elzahar, Zalata, and Hassaan (2022) and Krishnan and Parsons (2008). Shaub (1994); Sweeney (1995), and Bernardi and Arnold (1997) all provide evidence that female auditors in the USA and Canada frequently have better moral reasoning than their male colleagues. Female auditors tolerate opportunistic behaviour less than male auditors, according to research that specifically explores the link between gender and tolerance (Thorne, Massey, and Magnan, 2003). Furthermore, Hambrick and Mason (1984) claim that these factors impact the decisions made by senior management teams. Therefore, a company should reflect the experiences, attitudes, and opinions of its top executives.

Executive participation in supervisory board decision-making hence has the potential to impact business success. According to the research of Hambrick *et al.* (1998), the interdependence and the management team's dynamics substantially impact both business

performance and corporate governance. By using transformational strategies, such as team member empowerment, goal setting, and managing one's reputation for the benefit of both the business and the individual, female directors' objectives and actions may help firms develop a culture of trust (Klenke, 2002). According to Trinidad and Normore (2005) and Klenke (2003), employing a trust-based management style is more common among female CEOs. Additional writers that concur with this claim include Carter, Williams, and Reynolds (1997), Powell (1990), and Powell and Ansic (1997).

This trust-based leadership demands managers to provide female directors with greater information. Sunden and Surette (1998) and Chen *et al.* (2019) found that women make less risky choices than males. Thus, female directors take less calculated risks (Hinz, McCarthy, and Turner, 1997; Bajtelsmit and VanDerhei, 1997). As a result, female directors are less inclined to relinquish profit control to management because doing so puts them at risk of legal action and harms their reputation. EM would hurt a company's reputation, claim Hunton *et al.* (2006). With EM, companies are more likely to be sued during initial public offerings of shares (DuCharme *et al.*, 2004). As a result, according to Srinidhi, Gul, and Tsui (2011), female directors are more concerned about the prospect of legal action and reputational harm.

Female board members are, therefore, more likely to choose internal and external auditors carefully to maintain a tighter watch over them. By increasing board participation, communication, and CEO oversight-aspects likely to improve compensation quality-female directors can improve board governance. Because of this, having more women on the board may result in less effectiveness in managing earnings. Additionally, they discovered a favourable correlation between female board members and EM using several EM parameters.

Previous researchers also discovered that opportunistic EM and the ratio of the female board and their presence on the audit committee or board as non-executive directors are positively correlated (Zalata *et al.*, 2019). This also assumed that female members restricted the

management from any wrongdoing. Discretionary accrual calculated from sample firms' annual reports indicates participating in EM efforts. Despite the lack of significance of the results, having a board with a higher ratio of women is still thought to protect businesses against managerial opportunism.

This study added the financial leverage ratio of the sample firms to the empirical model while determining EM. Firms that have a greater leverage ratio are more likely to rely on creditors. This is a sign that managers are involved in actions to manage earnings. The results from this study also show a higher ratio. Given their reliance on creditors, organisations with higher financial leverage ratios may be more likely to manipulate their profitability (Aripin and Abdulmumuni, 2020). Additionally, they are likely to make financial reports with larger earnings that do not accurately reflect the company's financial situation. Numerous writers have validated these findings, including Becker et al. (1998), and Hijazi and Al-Thuneibat (2015).

These writers noted that businesses are likelier to alter their profits to satisfy the creditors' requirements. Higher return on assets indicates less EM strategies are used by companies, according to information on return on assets. This study points out that the discrepancy between the minimum and maximum ratios of financial leverage demonstrates that the majority of sample businesses rely on debt and equity. As a result, managers are more prone to alter results to satisfy the requirements of the creditors (DeFond and Jiambalvo, 1994; Dyreng, Hillegeist, and Penalva, 2022). It also found that organisations are less inclined to participate in income-boosting activities when their borrowing ratios are higher.

Furthermore, while this investigation discovered a poor link between female board members and EM, the finding was insignificant. Women often act unethically or aggressively at work less frequently than males (Krishnan and Parsons, 2008). Additionally, they behave better than their male co-workers and are more likely to act prudently when making financial decisions. Furthermore, research conducted by a few academics about the association between

the ratio of female board members and EM has not produced any firm conclusions. Numerous scholars, including Krishnan and Parsons (2008); Powell and Ansic (1997); and Gul, Fung, and Jaggi (2009), assert a negative link.

4.4. Conclusion

The findings indicate that improved CG and EM negatively impact each other. For instance, the UK Corporate Governance Code is optional for businesses, but LSE-listed companies are expected to do so on a “comply or explain” basis. It indicates that they must either have followed all the guidelines in the Corporate Governance Code or give a justification for why they did not. The description of CG and how it is used for overall business advantages are now included in a distinct part of every significant organisation’s annual report.

Over time, CG in the UK has improved. For this investigation, financial data from 2019 to 2022 was used. Regularly, the regulatory agency’s rules and regulations improve. Therefore, current outcomes will probably differ if it employs different financial data. CG, for instance, no longer permits corporations to be dualistic. However, most US and UK businesses used to have the same employee execute both duties in years past. The UK CG implies a division between two roles, giving them additional influence so that no one could abuse their position of authority. Additionally, UK-listed businesses had to adhere to CG to maintain their listing status.

Most prior research has used the Big Four as a stand-in for EM when assessing audit quality. Only one out of 101 FTSE companies studied for this analysis employs non-Big Four auditors. As a result, the audit committee’s size was determined to significantly encourage EM when used as a proxy to evaluate the audit’s quality. Most past investigations indicate that businesses audited by ‘the Big Four’ audit practices had a lower possibility of engaging in EM (Becker *et al.*, 1998l; Francis, Maydew, and Sparks, 1999). Similar to previous authors, this

study also discovered a link between EM and board size that is unfavourable, although, the results were insignificant. Theoretically, businesses with more directors may also have a higher ratio of non-executive independent board members. Independent directors in various board committees might be advantageous for the firm as they guarantee less irregularity in multiple jobs and better monitoring. As a result, EM will be decreased (Xie, Davidson, and DaDalt, 2003; Klein, 2002; Cheng, 2008; Kao, Hodgkinson, and Jaafar, 2019).

The methodology used in this study has also been employed by prior scholars to identify or assess the relationship between EM and CG mechanisms. However, other studies that used this model and obtained different results found those results to be inconsistent with the findings of this study. Different results might result from various factors, including using data samples from businesses in other industries or regulating those businesses by multiple authorities and rules. The data samples used in this research came from various business sectors of the same stock index. Still, they are all subject to the same stock exchange regulations and the same regulatory agency. As the results from this study are insignificant, different data samples or annual reports may likely provide a different result.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

5.1. Introduction

This study has aimed to determine the relationship between CG mechanisms and EM. This was to discover if the current Corporate Governance Code served its purpose. Many researchers have used this subject in their studies, but the current literature seems to avoid UK-listed firms as their data sample. This study has aimed to fill this gap by using UK-listed firms (FTSE 100, 2019-2022) as a data sample and to identify the effectiveness of the latest CG framework. Discretionary accruals were calculated to measure EM and the modified Jones Model was used for this purpose. IBM SPSS software was used for analysis. Results indicated a negative association between CG mechanisms and EM, but this was not statistically significant.

5.2. Summary of the Research

While conducting this study, previous research by other researchers was considered. Before moving on with this thesis, many ideas and discoveries were evaluated. It was an excellent approach to learning about the financial and accounting industry and how it carries out its everyday operations. My thesis supervisor provided the most support from the beginning to ensure that this thesis was completed on time and with outstanding results. Numerous academics used various methods and concepts to identify the reasons for EM. One study could have produced favourable results, whereas another employing a different set of data samples might have produced negative results.

However, the results of the majority of research that employed the modified Jones Model to evaluate EM are comparable. In this study, five hypotheses were examined to see how

they related to EM. The first two are board independence and board size. In the past, numerous researchers have employed these two. The final three hypotheses-having more women on the board, having an independent chairperson, and the audit committee size-have only recently been considered in connection to EM.

The modified Jones Model was used in this analysis to compute discretionary accruals and analyse how EM and CG mechanisms are related. The model's dependent variable is discretionary accruals. Contrarily, its independent variables include mechanisms of CG, such as the independent chairman, the proportion of women on the board, the audit committee's size, board size, and the number of independent directors. The debt-to-assets ratio, financial leverage, and return on assets are examples of control elements. The analysis of the equation was performed using IBM SPSS software. The data sample included all the FTSE 100 companies listed on the LSE between 2019 and 2022. A negative relation was found between the ratio of women on the board, the size of the audit committee, and the quantity of independent board members, although the results were insignificant. Nevertheless, these businesses are subject to CG regulations. The results might have differed if data samples were collected from companies operating in undeveloped nations.

The study also looked into the connection between EM and the independence of the board. The ratio of independent executives was identified to define the term "board independence". Non-executive outsiders with no ties to the firm are known as independent directors. For their service, they are paid a set salary plus bonuses similar to those offered to executive directors of the firm. Since the company's financial performance does not drive independent directors, they are more inclined to act in the best interests of the business and its shareholders. The existence of a board that has an independent director should strengthen the firm's monitoring processes and increase the truthfulness and dependability of its financial statements.

A common technique for evaluating a company's audit quality is to locate the external auditors in charge of the corporate audit process. The audit committee's size was used as a proxy to study the connection between audit quality and EM. Since data samples were collected from the FTSE 100 index, all corporations except one hired Big Four auditors. Hence, the size of the audit committee was chosen to conduct the test. Businesses in the UK are required to abide by or provide justification for the Corporate Governance Code.

Additionally, listed businesses on the LSE had to adhere to the Corporate Governance Code to maintain their listing status. Because of this, most businesses appoint independent directors to the audit committee, but committee sizes vary. This study's outcomes showed a clear adverse association between the size of the audit committee and EM. However, the outcomes were not significant.

The link between female board members and EM was also explored in this study as a component of CG systems. It was shown that there was a negative correlation between EM and female board members. A significant presence of female members on a board might influence how EM is conducted. Compared to their male co-workers, women are more likely to avoid unethical behaviour. When participating in any financial decision-making procedure, they are prone to act prudently. Nowadays, most UK corporations have female board members. Also, Hosny (2019) discovered that between 1999 and 2015, the ratio of female board members of UK FTSE 100 businesses rose from 4.5% to 10.5%. However, evidence suggests that businesses with an increased ratio of women on the board are probably engaged in income-decreasing activities than those that increase income. Due to a lack of time and knowledge, this could not be examined in this situation.

5.3. Contribution

This study contributes to a better understanding of the relationship between CG mechanism and EM, especially within UK-listed companies. The results were not statistically significant but indicated a negative relationship between CG mechanisms and EM. As a leader in the introduction of CG mechanisms to improve businesses and investors' trust, it was investigated if the current CG policy was serving its purpose. Also examined what motivates directors to engage in EM and how to measure them.

5.4. Policy Implication

The Corporate Governance Code in the UK has been updated to meet the needs of businesses and shareholders. However, larger companies, such as those in the FTSE 100, can avoid following CG requirements by justifying why. These rules should be lifted. The Corporate Governance Code was introduced after the Cadbury report, which was a response to the failures of several major corporations. This study using data from UK-listed companies found that these companies are only required to voluntarily follow the Corporate Governance Code, and if they choose not to, they can simply justify why. This is not ideal. Large companies, like those in the FTSE 100, have a substantial number of public shareholders. Therefore, the Corporate Governance Code should be mandatory for them and other big companies.

5.5. Limitations

The culture of the financial industry is changing more than ever, along with corporate governance. Thus, investors will have a greater tendency to believe in the company's financial reporting and make wiser investment choices. To maintain their listing status, listed firms will likely adhere to corporate governance standards. However, managers may control profits thanks to several accounting options. They act in this opportunistic way to profit themselves. However,

the company's investors are the ones who are most impacted. Corporate governance procedures are likely to vary amongst businesses. Corporate Governance Codes are founded on principles in the UK, and companies must abide by them or provide justification. The Sarbanes-Oxley Act, a rules-based CG structure, is used in the USA.

Thus, to do business, firms must be bound by specific laws. Both systems have benefits and drawbacks. Small businesses in the UK only need to produce a justification for not complying. However, US-based companies are required to abide by the laws. Most small enterprises find this to be expensive. The connection between EM and CG mechanisms may vary between these two countries. This study examines corporate governance structures from a UK perspective concerning EM. This study used five hypotheses to determine the relationship with EM. To investigate the connections between EM and board independence, audit committee size, board size, independent chairman, and female board representation, these hypotheses were developed.

Because of the pandemic, the duration of conducting this study was extended. However, this study faced difficulties in collecting data samples or using library facilities, which restricted the ability to browse more literature and books related to the research topic. Nowadays, most research is done online, but this investigation faced many situations where required documents were unavailable online or had restricted access. EM is influenced by other aspects of company governance as well, including institutional ownership, audit fees, audit opinion, the relevance of the value, independence of the auditor, and internal governance. Any of these might be the subject of future research to understand better how they relate to EM.

5.6. Future Research Scope

The results of this study were not statistically significant. However, proxies for CG mechanisms indicate a negative relationship with EM. Much literature suggests investigating

the same area. However, recent literature seems to avoid using data samples from UK-listed companies. Hence, this study took that effort. Future studies could take the same approaches, but using different company sectors should provide statistically significant results. Future researchers should be careful about choosing data samples. This study used a data sample from UK-listed firms. Although these companies follow mostly the same regulations, they are from various sectors. Identifying companies from similar sectors should provide better results to detect the relationship between CG mechanisms and EM.

5.7. Conclusion

Running a business and owning it is not the same thing. In large businesses, the owners are shareholders, but appointed directors run the business. The interests of shareholders and directors do not always align. Directors act on behalf of shareholders to maximise their wealth, but conflicts of interest can arise when directors prioritise their interests. This can lead to EM. The UK implemented the Corporate Governance Code after several corporate failures to protect the interests of shareholders. This study explored the relationship between CG mechanisms and EM. Data from UK-listed companies was used in this study. The results showed a negative relationship between some CG mechanisms, but this was not statistically significant.

References:

- Abbadi, S. S., Hijazi, Q. F. and Al-Rahahleh, A. (2016) 'Corporate governance quality and earnings management: evidence from Jordan', *Australasian Accounting Business & Finance Journal*, 10(2), p. 54-75.
- Abbott, L. J., Parker, S. and Peters, G. F. (2004) 'Audit committee characteristics and restatements', *Auditing: A Journal of Practice & Theory*, 23(1), p. 69-87.
- Abdalkrim, G. (2019) 'Chief executive officer compensation, corporate governance and performance: evidence from KSA firms', *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 19(6), pp. 1216-1235.
- Abed, S., Al-Attar, A. and Suwaidan, M. (2012) 'Corporate governance and earnings management: Jordanian evidence', *International Business Research*, 5(1), p. 216.
- Acar, G. and Coskun, A. (2020) A comparison of models for predicting discretionary accruals: A cross-country analysis, *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(9), pp.315-328.
- Adams, B., Carow, K. A. and Perry, T. (2009) 'Earnings management and initial public offerings: The case of the depository industry', *Journal of Banking & Finance*, vol. 33, no. 12, p. 2363-2372.
- Adams, R. and Ferreira, D. (2009) 'Women in the boardroom and their impact on governance and performance', *Journal of Financial Economics*, 94(2), p. 291-309.
- Adams, R. B. (2000) 'The dual role of corporate boards as advisors and monitors of management: theory and evidence'. Available at: <http://ssrn.com/abstract=241581> (Accessed on 19 August 2021)
- Adams, R., Gray, S. and Nowland, J. (2010) 'Is there a business case for female directors? Evidence from the market reaction to all new director appointments', In 23rd Australasian finance and banking conference.
- Agrawal, A. and Chadha, S. (2005) 'Corporate governance and accounting scandals', *Journal of Law and Economics*, 48(2), p. 371-406.
- Agrawal, A. and Knoeber, C. R. (1996) 'Firm performance and mechanisms to control agency problems between managers and shareholders', *Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, Vol. 31, p. 377-397.
- Aharony, J., Lee, C. W. J. and Wong, T. J. (2000) 'Financial packaging of IPO firms in China', *Journal of Accounting Research*, 38(1), p. 103-126.
- Ahmad, S., Wasim, S., Irfan, S., Gogoi, S., Srivastava, A. and Farheen, Z. (2019) Qualitative v/s. quantitative research summarized review. *Population*, 1(2), pp.2828-2832.
- Ahmed, A. S. and Duellman, S. (2007) 'Accounting conservatism and board of director characteristics: an empirical analysis', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 43(2-3), p. 411-437.
- Ahmed, K., Hossain, M. and Adams, M. B. (2006) 'The effects of board composition and board size on the informativeness of annual accounting earnings', *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 14(5), p. 418-431.
- Ahmed, A. S., Takeda, C. and Thomas S. (1999) 'Bank loan loss provisions: a re-examination of capital management, earnings management and signalling effects', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 28(1), p. 1-25.
- Alabdullah, T. T. Y. and Ahmed, E. R. (2020) 'A cross-sectional analysis of the influence of corporate governance features on the organizational outcomes: An assessment', *IIUC Studies*, pp.9-26.
- Alabi, A. W., Olaoye, F. O. and Ojo, O. D. (2022) 'The nexus between corporate governance and financial performance of the FTSE 100 Index Entities in the United Kingdom', *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 7(6), pp.235-246.
- Alchian, A. (1950) 'Uncertainty, evolution, and economic theory', *Journal of Political Economy*, 58(3), p. 211-221.
- Al-Azeez, H. A. R., Sukoharsono, E. G. and Andayani, W. (2019) 'The impact of board characteristics on earnings management in the international oil and gas corporations', *Academy of Accounting and Financial Studies Journal*, 23(1), pp.1-26.
- Al-Haddad, L. and Whittington, M. (2019) 'The impact of corporate governance mechanisms on real and accrual earnings management practices: evidence from Jordan', *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 19(6), pp.1167-1186.

- Ali Shah, S. Z., Butt, S. A. and Hassan, A. (2009) 'Corporate governance and earnings management an empirical evidence form Pakistani listed companies', *European Journal of Scientific Research*, 26(4), p. 624-638.
- Almashhadani, H. A. and Almashhadani, M. (2022) 'An overview of recent developments in corporate governance', *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 11(5), pp. 39-44.
- Almasria, N. A. (2022) 'Corporate governance and the quality of audit process: An exploratory analysis considering internal audit, audit committee and board of directors', *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 7(1), pp.78-99.
- Al-Rahahleh, A. S. (2017) 'Corporate governance quality, board gender diversity and corporate dividend policy: Evidence from Jordan'. *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 11(2), p.86-104.
- Alvarado, N. R., De Fuentes, P. and Laffarga, J. (2019) 'Do auditors mitigate earnings management during economic crisis? Intervención de los auditores en la gestión de resultados durante la crisis económica' *Revista de Contabilidad-Spanish Accounting Review*, 22(1), pp. 6-20.
- Alves, S. (2014) 'The effect of board independence on the earnings quality: evidence from Portuguese listed companies', *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 8(3), p. 23-44.
- Alzoubi, E. S. S. (2019) 'Audit committee, internal audit function and earnings management: evidence from Jordan', *Meditari Accountancy Research*, 27(1), pp. 72-90.
- Amat, S. O., Gowthorpe, C. and Perramon, J. (2005) 'Manipulation of earnings reports in Spain-some evidence', *Journal of Applied Accounting Research*, 8(3), pp. 93-115.
- Ananchotikul, N., Kouwenberg, R. and Phunnarungsi, V. (2010) 'Do firms decouple corporate governance policy and practice?' *European Financial Management*, 16, p. 712-737.
- Anderson, R. and Reeb, D. (2004) 'Board composition: balancing family influence in S&P 500 firms', *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 49(2), p. 209-237.
- Andres, P., Azofra, V. and Lopez, F. J. (2005) 'Corporate boards in OECD countries: size, composition, compensation, functioning and effectiveness', *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, Vol 13, p. 197-210.
- Anthony, J. H. and Petroni, K. R. (1997) 'Accounting estimation disclosures and firm valuation in the property-casualty insurance industry', *Journal of Accounting, Auditing & Finance*, 12(3), p. 257-281.
- Anuchitworawong, C. (2004) '*Deposit insurance, corporate governance and discretionary behavior: evidence from thai financial institutions* (No. 2004-15)' Center for Economic Institutions, Institute of Economic Research, Hitotsubashi University.
- Arena, M. P., Dewally, M. and Peck, S. W. (2020) 'Fight or flee: Outside director departures prior to contested management buyout offers', *Corporate governance: an international review*, 28(5), pp. 274-293.
- Aripin, N. and Abdulmumuni, O. (2020) 'Financial leverage and financial performance of Nigerian manufacturing firms', *International Journal of Supply Chain Management*.
- Arsoy, A. P. and Crowther, D. (2008) 'Corporate governance in Turkey: reform and convergence', *Social Responsibility Journal*, 4(3), p. 407-421.
- Arthur, N. and Taylor, S. (1993) 'Chairman, chief executive, or both?' *Company Director*, 9, p. 20-21.
- Arun, T. G., Almahrog, Y. E. and Aribi, Z. A. (2015) 'Female directors and earnings management: Evidence from UK companies', *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 39, p. 137-146.
- Arya, A., Glover, J. C. and Sunder, S. (2003) 'Are unmanaged earnings always better for shareholders?' *Accounting Horizons*, vol. 17, p. 111-116.
- Asghar, A., Sajjad, S., Shahzad, A. and Matemilola, B. T. (2020) 'Role of discretionary earning management in corporate governance-value and corporate governance-risk relationships', *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 20(4), pp. 561-581.
- Ashiq, A. and Weining, Z. (2015) 'CEO tenure and earnings management', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 59, p. 60-79.
- Ashraf, M., Michas, P. N. and Russomanno, D. (2020) 'The impact of audit committee information technology expertise on the reliability and timeliness of financial reporting', *The Accounting Review*, 95(5), pp. 23-56.

- ASX (Australian Stock Exchange), (2003) 'Corporate Governance Council', *Principles of Good Corporate Governance and Best Practice Recommendations*, (ASX, Sydney).
- Athanasakou, V. E., Strong, N. C. and Walker, M. (2009) 'Earnings management or forecast guidance to meet analyst expectations?' *Accounting & Business Research*, vol. 39, no. 1, p. 3-35
- Atu, O. O. K., Atu, F. O., Enegebe, O. P. and Atu, E. C. (2016) 'Determinants of earnings management in Nigerian quoted companies', *Igbinedion University Journal of Accounting*, 1(1), p. 9-20.
- Baber, W. R., Kang, S. and Kumar, K. R. (1998) 'Accounting earnings and executive compensation: the role of earnings persistence', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*. 25 (2), p. 169-193.
- Badertscher, B. A., Phillips, J. D., Pincus, M. and Rego, S. O. (2009) 'Earnings management strategies and the trade-off between tax benefits and detection risk: To conform or not to conform?' *The accounting review*, 84(1), p. 63-97.
- Bagnoli, M. and Watts, S. G. (2000) 'The effect of relative performance evaluation on earnings management: a game-theoretic approach', *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, vol. 19, no. 4-5, p. 377-397.
- Bajtelsmit, V. L. and VanDerhei, J. L. (1997) 'Risk aversion and pension investment choices', *Positioning pensions for the twenty-first century*, 45(2), p.66.
- Ball, R., Kothari, S. and Robin, A. (2000) 'The effect of international institutional factors on properties of accounting earnings', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 29(1), p. 1-52.
- Ball, R., Robin, A. and Wu, J. (2003) 'Incentives versus standards: properties of accounting income in four east asian countries', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 36(1-3), p. 235–270.
- Ball, R. and Shivakumar, L. (2008) 'Earnings quality at initial public offerings', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 45(2-3), p. 324-349.
- Barca, F. (1995) 'On corporate governance in Italy: issues', *Facts, and Agency*. Manuscript. Bank of Italy, Rome.
- Barton, J. (2001) 'Does the use of the financial derivatives affect earnings management decisions?' *The Accounting Review*, 76(1), p. 1- 26.
- Barton, J. and Mercer, M. (2005) 'To blame or not to blame: analysts' reactions to external explanations for poor financial performance', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 39(3), p. 509-533.
- Bartov, E. (1993) 'The timing of asset sales and earnings manipulation', *The Accounting Review*, 68, p. 840–855.
- Bartov, E., Gul, F. and Tsui, J. (2000) 'Discretionary-accruals models and audit qualifications', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, December, p. 421-452.
- Bashir, M. G. (2017) 'Determinants of earnings management among retail chains in Nairobi County', (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi).
- Baydoun, N., Maguire, W., Ryan, N. and Willett, R. (2012) 'Corporate governance in five Arabian Gulf countries', *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 28(1), p. 7-22.
- Baysinger, B. D. and Zardkoohi, A. (1986) 'Technology, residual claimants, and corporate control', *Journal of Law, Economics & Organization*, 2(2), p. 339-349.
- Beasley, M. (1996) 'An empirical analysis of the relation between the board of director composition and financial statement fraud', *The Accounting Review*, 71(4), p. 443–464.
- Beasley, M. S. and Salterio, S. E. (2001) 'The relationship between board characteristics and voluntary improvements in audit committee composition and experience'. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 18(4), p. 539-570.
- Beatty, A., Chamberlain, S. L. and Magliolo, J. (1995) 'Managing financial reports of commercial banks: The influence of taxes, regulatory capital, and earnings', *Journal of Accounting Research*, 33(2), p. 231-261.
- Beatty, A. L., Bin, K. and Petroni, K. R. (2002) 'Earnings management to avoid earnings declines across publicly and privately held banks', *Accounting Review*, vol. 77, no. 3, p. 547-570.
- Beaudreau, B. (2005) *How the Republicans Caused the Stock Market Crash of 1929: GPT's, Failed Transitions, and Commercial Policy*, iUniverse.
- Beaver W. H. and Engel E. E. (1996) 'Discretionary behavior with respect to allowances for loan losses and the behavior of security prices', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, vol. 22, no. 1-3, p. 177-206.
- Beaver, W. H. and McNichols, M. F. (2006) 'The characteristics and valuation of loss reserves of property casualty insurers', *Review of Accounting Studies*, vol. 3, p. 73-95

- Beaver, W. H., McNichols, M. F. and Nelson, K. K. (2003) 'Management of loss reserve accrual and the distribution of earnings in the property-casualty insurance industry', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 35(3), p. 347-376.
- Beaver, W., Eger, C., Ryan, S. and Wolfson, M. (1989) 'Financial reporting, supplemental disclosures, and bank share prices', *Journal of Accounting Research*, 27(2), p. 157-178.
- Beaver, W. H. (2002) 'Perspectives on recent capital market research', *The Accounting Review*, 77(2), p. 453-474.
- Becker, C., Defond, M., Jiambalvo, J. and Subramanyam, K. (1998) 'The effect of audit quality on earnings management', *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 15(1), p. 1-24.
- Bedard, J., Chtourou, S. M. and Courteau, L. (2004) 'The effect of audit committee expertise, independence, and activity on aggressive earnings management', *Auditing: A Journal of Practice and Theory*, 23(2), p. 15-35.
- Belas, J., Gavurova, B. and Toth, P. (2018) 'Impact of selected characteristics of SMES on the capital structure', *Journal of Business Economics and Management*, 19(4), p. 592-608
- Belas, J., Smrcka, L., Gavurova, B. and Dvorsky, J. (2018) 'The impact of social and economic factors in the credit risk management of SME', *Technological and Economic Development of Economy*, 24(3), p. 1215-1230.
- Bencomo, R. Q. (2021) 'The role of independent non-executive directors in resolving corporate governance disputes: A framework of conciliation for effectively addressing controversies within shareholders, stakeholders and the board of directors?' *Trento Student Law Review*, 3(1), pp. 17-58.
- Beneish M. D. (1997) 'Detecting GAAP violation: implications for assessing earnings management among firms with extreme financial performance', *Journal of Accounting & Public Policy*, vol. 16, no. 3, p. 271-309.
- Beneish M. D. (1999) 'The detection of earnings manipulation', *Financial Analysts Journal*, 55(5), p. 24-36.
- Beneish M. D. (2001) 'Earnings management: A perspective', *Managerial Finance*, vol. 27, no. 12, p. 3.
- Benoit, R. (2006) *The Lord and Benoit report: bridging the Sarbanes-Oxley disclosure control gap* Worcester, MA: Lord and Benoit LLP.
- Bens, D. A. and Johnston, R. (2009) 'Accounting discretion: Use or abuse? An analysis of restructuring charges surrounding regulator action', *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 26(3), p. 673-699.
- Benston, G. J. and Hartgraves, A. L. (2002) 'Enron: what happened and what we can learn from it', *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, vol. 21, no. 2, p. 105-127.
- Bernardi, R. and Arnold, D. (1997) 'An Examination of Moral Development within Public Accounting by Gender, Staff Level, and Firm', *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 14(4), p. 653-668.
- Berthelot, S., Coulmont, M. and Serret, V., 2012. 'Do investors value sustainability reports? A Canadian study', *Corporate social responsibility and environmental management*, 19(6), p.355-363.
- Bertrand, M. and Mullainathan, S. (2003) 'Enjoying the quiet life? Corporate governance and managerial preferences', *Journal of political Economy*, 111(5), p. 1043-1075.
- Betz, M., O'Connell, L. and Shepard, J. M. (1989) 'Gender differences in proclivity for unethical behavior', *Journal of business ethics*, 8(5), p.321-324.
- Betzer, A. and Theissen, E. (2009) 'Insider trading and corporate governance: the case of Germany'. *European Financial Management*, 15, p. 402-429.
- Bhagat, S. and Black, B. S. (1998) 'Independent directors', *The New Palgrave Dictionary of Economics and the Law*, Peter Newman, Ed, 2, p. 283-287.
- Bilan, Y. and Jurickova, V. (2021) *Detection of earnings management by different models*. In SHS Web of Conferences (Vol. 92, p. 02005). EDP Sciences.
- Billet, M. T. and Xue, H. (2007) 'The takeover deterrent effect of open market share repurchases', *Journal of Finance*, 62(4), p. 1827-1850.
- Black, B., de Carvalho, A. G., Kim, W. and Yurtoglu, B. B. (2023) 'How useful are commercial corporate governance ratings? Evidence from emerging markets', *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 80, p. 102405.
- Bowen, R., DuCharme, L. and Shores, D. (1995) 'Stakeholders' implicit claims and accounting method choice', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 20(3), p. 255-295.
- Boycko, M., Shleifer A. and Vishny, R.W. (1995) *Privatizing Russia*. Cambridge, Mass: MIT Press.

- Braun, G. P. and Rodriguez, J. (2008) 'Earnings management and accounting values: a test of gray (1988)', *Journal of International Accounting Research*, vol. 7, no. 2, p. 1-23.
- Bradbury, M., Mak, Y. T. and Tan, S. M. (2006) 'Board characteristics, audit committee characteristics and abnormal accruals', *Pacific Accounting Review*, 18(2), p. 47-68.
- Braga-Alves, M. V., Ellis, J., Mandelker, G. N. and Zutter, C. J. (2009) 'The effect of takeover probability on earnings management', *Working Paper*. Marquette University.
- Breuer, M. and Schütt, H. H. (2023) 'Accounting for uncertainty: an application of Bayesian methods to accruals models', *Review of Accounting Studies*, 28(2), pp. 726-768.
- Brickley, J. A., Coles, J. L. and Terry, R. L. (1994) 'Outside directors and the adoption of poison pills', *Journal of Financial Economics*, 35(3), p. 371-90.
- Brickley, J. and James, C. (1987) 'The takeover market, corporate board composition, and ownership structure the case of banking', *The Journal of Law and Economics*, 30, p. 161-180.
- Brown, R. and Gørgens, T. (2009) 'Corporate governance and financial performance in an Australian context' (No. 2009-02), The Treasury, Australian Government.
- Brown, L. D. and Higgins, H. N. (2001) 'Managing earnings surprises in the US versus 12 other countries', *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 20(4), p. 373-398.
- Bryman, A. (2012) *Social research methods*, (4th ed.), Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Buchholz, F., Lopatta, K. and Maas, K. (2020) 'The deliberate engagement of narcissistic CEOs in earnings management', *Journal of Business Ethics*, 167, pp. 663-686.
- Burgstahler, D. C. and Dichev, I. D. (1997) 'Earnings management to avoid earnings decreases and losses', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 24(1), p. 99-126.
- Burgstahler, D. C., Hail, L. and Leuz, C. (2006) 'The importance of reporting incentives: earnings management in European private and public firms', *The Accounting Review*, 81(5), p. 983-1016.
- Bushman, R., Chen, Q. and Engel, E. (2004) 'Financial accounting information, organizational complexity and corporate governance systems', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 37(2), p. 167-201.
- Bushee, B. (1998) 'The influence of institutional investors on myopic R&D investment behavior', *The Accounting Review*, 73(3), p. 305-333.
- Buyuksalvarci, A. and Abdioglu, H. (2010) 'Corporate governance, financial ratios and stock returns: an empirical analysis of Istanbul Stock Exchange (ISE)', *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, Vol. 57 (November), p. 70-81.
- Byrd, J. W. and Hickman, K. A. (1992) 'Do Outside Directors Monitor Managers? Evidence from tender offer bids', *Journal of Financial Economics*, 32(2), p. 195-207.
- Byrnes, J. P., Miller, D. C. and Schafer, W. D. (1999) 'Gender differences in risk-taking: A meta-analysis'. *Psychological bulletin*, 125(3), p. 367.
- Cadbury Code (1992) 'Report of the Committee on the Financial Aspects of Corporate Governance (The 'Cadbury Committee' & 'The Code of Best Practice')', Financial Reporting Council. Available at: www.ecgi.org/codes/country (Accessed on 10 May 2020)
- Cadbury Committee (1992) 'Report on the Financial Aspects of Corporate Governance', London: GEC.
- Caliendo, M., Fossen, F. and Kritikos, A. (2012) 'Trust, positive reciprocity, and negative reciprocity: Do these traits impact entrepreneurial dynamics?' *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 33(2), p. 394-409.
- Callao, S., Wroblewski, D. and Jarne, J. I. (2021) 'A systematic approach to the motivations for earnings management: A literature review', *Int. J. Emerg. Trends Soc. Sci.*, (ART-2021-135087).
- Campello, M., Graham, J. R. and Harvey, C. R. (2011) 'The real effects of financial constraints: Evidence from a financial crisis', *Journal of Financial Economics*, Vol. 97, No. 3, p. 470-487.
- Carcello, J. V. and Neal, T. L. (2003) 'Audit committee independence and disclosure: Choice for financially distressed firms', *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 11(4), p. 289-299.
- Carcello, J. V., Hollingsworth, C. W. and Neal, T. L. (2006) 'Audit committee financial experts: A closer examination using firm designations', *Accounting Horizons*, 20(4), p. 351-373.
- Carcello, J. V., Hollingsworth, C. W., Klein, A. and Neal, T. L. (2006) 'Audit committee financial expertise, competing corporate governance mechanisms, and earnings management', *Competing Corporate Governance Mechanisms, and Earnings Management* (February 2006).
- Carroll, A. B. (1979) 'A three-dimensional conceptual model of corporate performance', *Academy of management review*, 4(4), p. 497-505.

- Carter, D. A., Simkins, B. J. and Simpson, W. G. (2003) 'Corporate Governance, Board Diversity, and Firm Value', *Financial Review*, 38(1), p. 33-53.
- Carter, N., Williams, M. and Reynolds, P. (1997) 'Discontinuance among firms in retail: the influence of initial resources, strategy and gender', *Journal of Business Venturing*, 12(2), p. 125-145.
- Catalyst (2007) Catalyst census of women corporate officers and top earners of the fortune 500 (Report), New York. Available at: <https://www.catalyst.org/research/2007-catalyst-census-of-women-corporate-officers-and-top-earners-of-the-fortune-500/> (Accessed on: 10 June 2022)
- Catalyst (2008) Catalyst census of women board directors of the fortune 500 (Report), New York. Available at: <https://www.catalyst.org/research/2008-catalyst-census-of-women-board-directors-of-the-fortune-500/> (Accessed on: 16 June 2022)
- Catalyst (2009) Catalyst census: fortune 500 women board directors (Report), New York. Available at: <https://www.catalyst.org/research/2009-catalyst-census-fortune-500-women-board-directors/> (Accessed on: 10 June 2022)
- Catalyst (2010) Catalyst census: fortune 500 women board directors (Report), New York. Available at: <https://www.catalyst.org/research/2010-catalyst-census-fortune-500-women-board-directors/> (Accessed on: 10 June 2022)
- Catalyst (2011) Catalyst census: fortune 500 women board directors (Report), New York. Available at: <https://www.catalyst.org/research/2011-catalyst-census-fortune-500-women-board-directors/> (Accessed on: 10 June 2022)
- Catalyst (2012) catalyst census: fortune 500 women executive officers and top earners (Report), New York. Available at: <https://www.catalyst.org/research/2012-catalyst-census-fortune-500-women-executive-officers-and-top-earners/> (Accessed on: 10 June 2022)
- Chambers, R. (1999) 'The poverty of accounting disclosure', *Abacus*, Vol. 35, No. 3, p. 241-251.
- Chaharsoughi, M. T. and Rahman, R. A. (2013) 'Corporate governance and earnings quality: The experience of listed companies in Iran', *Journal of Modern Accounting and Auditing*, 9(6), p. 790.
- Chaganti, R. S., Mahajan, V. and Sharman, S. (1985) 'Corporate Board Size, Composition and Corporate Fail-ures in Retailing Industry', *Journal of Management Studies*, Vol. 22, No. 4, p. 400-417.
- Charkham, J. (1994) *Keeping good company: a study of corporate governance in five countries*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- Chau, G. and Gray, S. J. (2010) 'Family ownership, board independence and voluntary disclosure: evidence from Hong Kong', *Journal of International Accounting, Auditing and Taxation*, Vol. 19, No. 2, p. 93-109.
- Chen, J., Leung, W. S., Song, W. and Goergen, M. (2019) 'Why female board representation matters: The role of female directors in reducing male CEO overconfidence', *Journal of Empirical Finance*, 53, pp. 70-90.
- Chen, Y. and Li, S. X. (2009) 'Group identity and social preferences', *The American Economic Review*, 99(1), p. 431-457.
- Cheng, S. (2008) 'Board size and the variability of corporate performance'. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 87(1), p. 157-176.
- Cheng, Q. (2000) 'Earnings management to meet analysts' forecasts and the impact of stock-based compensation', *Journal of Accounting Research*, vol. 82, no. 3, p. 153-183.
- Cheng, S. (2004) 'R&D expenditures and CEO compensation', *The Accounting Review*, 79(2), p. 305-328.
- Cheung, Y., Jiang, P. and Tan, W. (2010) 'A transparency disclosure index measuring disclosures: Chinese listed companies', *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, Vol. 29, No. 3, p. 259-280.
- Chin, C. L., Chen, Y. J. and Hsieh, T. J. (2009) 'International diversification, ownership structure, legal origin, and earnings management: evidence from Taiwan', *Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*, 24, p. 233-262.
- Ching, K. M., Firth, M. and Rui, O. M. (2006) 'Earnings management, corporate governance and the market performance of seasoned equity offerings in Hong Kong', *Journal of Contemporary Accounting & Economics*, 2(1), 73-98.
- Choi, J., Jeon, K. and Park, J. (2004) 'The role of audit committees in decreasing earnings statement: Korean evidence', *International Journal of Accounting, Auditing & Performance Evaluation*, Vol. 1, No. 1, p. 37- 60.

- Choi, Y. S., Walker, M. and Young, S. (2006) 'Disagreement over the persistence of earnings components: Evidence on the properties of management-specific adjustments to GAAP earnings', *Journal of the Korean Accounting Association*, 2006, p. 1-33.
- Chtourou, S. M., Bedard, J. and Courteau, L. (2001) 'Corporate Governance and Earnings Management', Available at SSRN: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.275053> (Accessed on 10 June 2022)
- Chung, R., Firth, M. and Kim, J. B. (2002) 'Institutional monitoring and opportunistic earnings management', *Journal of Corporate Finance*, No. 8, p. 29-48.
- Clark, A. M., (1998) 'The qualitative-quantitative debate: moving from positivism and confrontation to post-positivism and reconciliation', *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 27(6), p. 1242-1249.
- Clarkson, P., Dontoh, A., Richardson, G. D. and Sefcik, S. (1992) 'The Voluntary Inclusion of Earnings Forecasts in IPO Prospectuses', *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 8(1), p. 601-626.
- Cohen, D. A., Dey, A. and Lys, T. Z. (2005) 'Trends in earnings management and informativeness of earnings announcements in the pre-and post-Sarbanes Oxley periods' (February 1, 2005). Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.658782> (Accessed on 17 May 2022)
- Cohen, D. A., Dey, A. and Lys, T. Z. (2008) 'Real and Accrual-Based Earnings Management in the Pre- and Post-Sarbanes-Oxley Periods', *The Accounting Review*, 83(3), p. 757-787.
- Cohen, J. R., Hoitash, U., Krishnamoorthy, G. and Wright, A. M. (2014) 'The effect of audit committee industry expertise on monitoring the financial reporting process.' *The Accounting Review*, 89(1), p. 243-273.
- Cohen, D. A., Darrrough, M. N., Huang, R. and Zach, T. (2011) 'Warranty reserve: contingent liability, information signal, or earnings management tool?' *Accounting Review*, 86(2), p. 569-604.
- Coles, J. L., Hertzfel, M. and Kalpathy, S. (2006) 'Earnings management around employee stock option reissues', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 41(1-2), p. 173-200.
- Collins, J. H., Shackelford, D. A. and Wahlen, J. M. (1995) 'Bank differences in the coordination of regulatory capital, earnings, and taxes', *Journal of Accounting Research*, vol. 33, no. 2, p. 263-291.
- Comment, R. and Schwert, G. W. (1995) 'Poison or Placebo? Evidence on the deterrent and wealth effects of modern antitakeover measures', *Journal of Financial Economics*, 39(1), p. 3-43.
- Conyon, M. J. and Mallin, C. A. (1997) 'A review of compliance with Cadbury', *Journal of General Management*, Vol. 22(3), p. 24-37.
- Cook, K. A., Huston, G. R. and Omer, T. C. (2008) 'Earnings management through effective tax rates: the effects of tax-planning investment and the Sarbanes Oxley Act of 2002*', *Contemporary Accounting Research*, vol. 25, no. 2, p. 447-471.
- Cormier, D. and Martinez, I. (2006) 'The association between management earnings forecasts, earnings management, and stock market valuation: evidence from French IPOs', *The International Journal of Accounting*, 41(3), p. 209-236.
- Cornett, M., Marcus, A. and Tehranian, H. (2008) 'Corporate governance and pay-for-performance: The impact of earnings management', *Journal of Financial Economics*, 87(2), p. 357-373.
- Cornett, M. M., McNutt, J. J. and Tehranian, H. (2009) 'Corporate governance and earnings management at large US bank holding companies', *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 15(4), p. 412-430.
- Cox, T. (1994) *Cultural diversity in organizations: Theory, research and practice*. Berrett-Koehler Publishers.
- Crutchley, C. E., Jensen, M. R. and Marshall, B. B. (2007) 'Climate for scandal: corporate environments that contribute to accounting fraud', *Financial Review*, 42(1), pp.53-73.
- Cruz, C., Justo, R., Larraza-Kintana, M. and Garces-Galdeano, L. (2019) 'When do women make a better table? Examining the influence of women directors on family firm's corporate social performance', *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 43(2), pp. 282-301.
- Dahya, J. and Travlos, N. G. (2000) 'Does the one-man show pay? Theory and evidence on the dual CEO revisited', *European Financial Management*, Vol. 6, No. 1, p. 85-98.
- Dahya, J., McConnell, J. J. and Travlos, N. (2002) 'The Cadbury Committee, corporate performance, and top management turnover', *Journal of Finance*, 57(1), p. 461-483.
- Daily, C. M. and Dalton, D. R. (1992) 'The relationship between governance structure and corporate performance in entrepreneurial firms', *Journal of Business Venturing*, Vol. 7(5), p. 375-386.
- Dakhlallah, M. M., Rashid, N., Abdullah, W. A. W., Qawqzeh, H. K. and Dakhlallah, A. M. (2020) 'Accrual-based earnings management, real earnings management and firm performance: evidence from public

- shareholders listed firms on Jordanian's stock market', *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*, 12(1).
- Dalton, D. R., Daily, C. M., Ellstrand, A. E. and Johnson, J. L. (1998) 'Meta-analytic reviews of board composition, leadership structure and financial performance', *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol 19(3), p. 269-290.
- Dalton, D. R., Daily, C. M., Johnson, J. L. and Ellstrand, A. (1999) 'Number of directors and financial performance: A meta-analysis', *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 42, N° .6, p. 674-686.
- Das, S., Shroff, P. K. and Zhang, H. (2009) 'Quarterly earnings patterns and earnings management', *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 26(3), p.797-831.
- Davidson, R., Goodwin-Stewart, J. and Kent, P. (2005) 'Internal governance structures and earnings management', *Accounting and Finance*, Vol. 45, No. 2, p. 241-267.
- DeAngelo, L. (1981) 'Auditor size and audit quality', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 3(3), p. 183–199.
- DeAngelo, L. E. (1986) 'Accounting numbers as market valuation substitutes: a study of management buyouts of public stockholders', *The Accounting Review*, 61(3), p. 400-420.
- DeAngelo, H., DeAngelo, L. E., and Skinner, D. (1996) 'Reversal of fortune: dividend signalling and disappearance of sustained earnings growth', *Journal of Financial Economics*, 40(3), p. 341-371.
- Dechow, P. M., and Dichev, I. D. (2002) 'The quality of accruals and earnings: the role of accrual estimation errors', *The Accounting Review*, 77(s-1), p. 35-59.
- Dechow, P., Ge, W. and Schrand, C. (2010) 'Understanding earnings quality: A review of the proxies, their determinants and their consequences', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 50(2-3), p. 344-401.
- Dechow, P. M. and Skinner, D. J. (2000) 'Earnings management: reconciling the views of accounting academics, practitioners, and regulators', *Accounting Horizons*, vol. 14, no. 2, p. 235-250.
- Dechow, P. M., Huson, M. R. and Sloan, R. G. (1994) 'The effect of restructuring charges on CEO cash compensation', *The Accounting Review*, 69(1), p. 138-156.
- Dechow, P. M., Hutton, A. P., Kim, J. H. and Sloan, R. G. (2012) 'Detecting earnings management: A new approach', *Journal of Accounting Research*, 50(2), p. 275-334.
- Dechow, P. M., Sloan, R. G. and Sweeney, A. P. (1995) 'Detecting earnings management', *The Accounting Review*, Vol. 70, No. 2, p. 193-225.
- Dechow, P. M., Sloan, R. G. and Sweeney, A. P. (1996) 'Causes and consequences of earnings manipulation: An analysis of firms subject to enforcement actions by the SEC', *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 13(1), p. 1-36.
- Deegan, C., Rankin, M. and Voght, P. (2000) 'Firms' disclosure reactions to major social incidents: Australian evidence', *In Accounting Forum*. Vol. 24, No. 1, p. 101-130.
- DeFond, M., Hung, M. Y. and Trezevant, R. (2007) 'Investor protection and the information content of annual earnings announcements: international evidence', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 43(1), p. 37-67.
- Defond, M. L. and Jiambalvo, J. (1994) 'Debt covenant violation and manipulation of accruals', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 17(1-2), p. 145-176.
- Defond, M. and Park, C. (1997) 'Smoothing income in anticipation of future earnings', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 23(2), p. 115-139.
- Defond, M. L. and Park, C. W. (2001) 'Smoothing income in anticipation of future earnings', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, vol. 23, no. 2, p. 115-139.
- Demaki, G. O. (2011) 'Proliferation of codes of corporate governance in Nigeria and economic development', *Business and Management Review*, 1(6), p. 1–7.
- Demirkan, S. and Platt, H. (2009) 'Financial status, corporate governance quality, and the likelihood of managers using discretionary accruals', *Accounting Research Journal*, Vol. 22, No. 2, p. 93-117.
- Dhaliwal, D. S., Naiker, V. and Navissi, F. (2006) 'Audit committee financial expertise, corporate governance and accruals quality: An empirical analysis'. *Corporate Governance and Accruals Quality: An Empirical Analysis* (May 2006). Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.906690> (Accessed on 20 September 2021)
- Dhaliwal, D. A. N., Naiker, V. I. C. and Navissi, F. (2010) 'The association between accruals quality and the characteristics of accounting experts and mix of expertise on audit committees', *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 27(3), p. 787-827.

- Dixon, R., Mousa, G. A. and Woodhead, A. (2005) 'The role of environmental initiatives in encouraging companies to engage in environmental reporting', *European Management Journal*, 23(6), p. 702–716.
- Donaldson, L. and Davis, J. H. (1991) 'Stewardship theory or agency theory: CEO governance and shareholder returns', *Australian Journal of Management*, Vol. 16, No. 1, p. 49-64.
- Donaldson, T. and Preston, L. E. (1995) 'The stakeholder theory of the corporation: concepts, evidence, and implications', *Academy of Management Review*, 20(1), p. 65-91.
- DuCharme, L. L., Malatesta, P. H. and Sefcik, S. E. (2004) 'Earnings management, stock issues, and shareholder lawsuits', *Journal of Financial Economics*, 71(1), p. 27-49.
- Dyrenng, S. D., Hillegeist, S. A. and Penalva, F. (2022) 'Earnings management to avoid debt covenant violations and future performance', *European Accounting Review*, 31(2), pp. 311-343.
- Easterbrook, F. H. and Fischel, D. R. (1991) *The economic structure of corporate law*. Cambridge, Mass: Harvard University Press.
- Ecker, F., Francis, J., Olsson, P. and Schipper, K. (2011) 'Peer Firm Selection for Discretionary Accruals Models'. Available at : <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Peer-Firm-Selection-for-Discretionary-Accruals-Ecker-Francis/7dcb25226e1e74c703e716072c0edd3374481546#references> (Accessed on 10 September 2021)
- Efenyumi, P. M. E., Nwoye, J. U. and Okoye, E. I., (2022) 'Impact of nomination and governance committee attributes on earnings management of listed firms on the Nigerian exchange group', *Hmlyan Jr Eco Bus Mgn*, 3(5), pp.26-34.
- Eilifsen A., Messier, F. W. Jr., Glover, M. S. and Prawitt, F. (2010) *Auditing and Assurance Services*, McGraw-Hill, UK.
- Ejaz, M., Jalal, R. N. U. D. and Fayyaz, U. E. R. (2022) 'Directors' reports cosmetic treatment: impact of earnings management on financial report readability', *Global Business and Economics Review*, 26(1), pp. 20-36.
- El Diri, M., Lambrinoudakis, C. and Alhadab, M. (2020) 'Corporate governance and earnings management in concentrated markets', *Journal of Business Research*, 108, pp. 291-306.
- Elmghaamez, I.K. and Akintoye, E., (2021) 'Internal corporate governance mechanisms and financial performance: evidence from the UK's top FTSE 100 listed companies', *International Journal of Business Governance and Ethics*, 15(2), pp.190-214.
- Elzahar, H., Zalata, A. and Hassaan, M. (2022) 'Attributes of female directors and accruals-based earnings management', *Cogent Business & Management*, 9(1), p. 2139212.
- Epps, R. W., and Ismail, T. H. (2009) 'Board of directors' governance challenges and earnings management', *Journal of Accounting & Organizational Change*, 5(3), p. 390-416.
- Equal Opportunity for Women in the Workplace Agency (2010) 'EOWA 2010: Australian census of women in leadership', Available at: <https://www.worldcat.org/title/eowa-2010-australian-census-of-women-in-leadership/oclc/826446004> (Accessed on 10 September 2021)
- Etherington, L. D. and Schulting, L. (1995) 'Ethical development of accountants: The case of Canadian certified management accountants', *Research on Accounting Ethics*, 1(3), p. 235–251.
- European Professional Women's Network (2010) EPWN. European pwn: board monitor 2010. Available at: <https://boardgender.org/profiles/european-pwn-board-monitor-2010/> (Accessed on 10 September 2021)
- Ezzamel, M. A. and Watson, R. (1993) 'Organisational form, ownership structure and corporate performance: A contextual empirical analysis of UK companies', *British Journal of Management*, Vol. 4(3), p. 161-176.
- Fama, E. F. (1980) 'Agency problems and the theory of the firm', *Journal of Political Economy*, Vol 88(2), p. 288-307.
- Fama, E. and Jensen, M. C. (1983) 'Separation of ownership and control', *Journal of Law and Economics*, 26(2), p. 301-325.
- Fan, P. H. and Wong, T. J. (2002) 'Corporate ownership structure and the informativeness of accounting earnings in East Asia', *Journal of Accounting Economics*, 33(3), p. 401 -425.
- Fanelli, V. and Ryden. A. K. (2018) 'Pricing a swing contract in a gas sale company', *Economics, Management, and Financial Markets*, 13(2), p. 40-55

- Farmer, T. A. (1993) 'Testing the effect of risk attitude on auditor judgment using multi attribute utility theory', *Journal of Accounting, Auditing & Finance*, vol. 8, no. 1, p. 91-110.
- FASB (2022) Summary of statement no. 109. Available at: <https://fasb.org/page/PageContent?pageId=/reference-library/superseded-standards/summary-of-statement-no-109.html&bcpath=tff> (Accessed on 05 January 2022)
- Fields, T. D., Lys, T. Z. and Vincent, L. (2001) 'Empirical research on accounting Choice', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 31(1), p. 255–307.
- Firth, M., Fung, P. M. and Rui, O. M. (2007) 'Ownership, two-tier board structure, and the informativeness of earnings - evidence from China', *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 26(4), p. 463–496.
- Fischer, M. and Rosenzweig, K. (1995) 'Attitudes of students and accounting practitioners concerning the ethical acceptability of earnings management', *Journal of Business Ethics*, 14(6), p. 433-444.
- Fodio, M. I., Ibikunle, J. and Oba, V. C. (2013) 'Corporate governance mechanisms and reported earnings quality in listed Nigerian insurance firms', *International Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 2(5), p. 279–286.
- Fogel, K., Ma, L. and Morck, R. (2021) 'Powerful independent directors', *Financial Management*, 50(4), pp. 935-983.
- Fortin, S., Subramaniam, C., Wang, X. and Zhang, S. (2011) 'Governance mechanisms, incentive alignment, and bond market reaction', *CAAA Annual Conference 2011*, Available at SSRN: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1741963> (Accessed on 10 February 2021)
- Francis, J. and Wang, D. (2008) 'The joint effect of investor protection and Big 4 audits on earnings quality around the world', *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 25(1), p. 157–191.
- Francis, J. and Yu, M. (2009) 'Big 4 office size and audit quality', *The Accounting Review*, 84(5), p. 1521–1552.
- Francis, J. R., Maydew, L. E., and Sparks, H. (1999) 'The role of Big 6 auditors in the credible reporting of accruals', *AUDITING: A Journal of Practice & Theory*, 18(2), p. 17-34.
- Francis, J. R. (2011) 'A framework for understanding and researching audit quality', *AUDITING: A Journal of Practice & Theory*, 30(2), p. 125–152.
- Frankel, R., Johnson, M. and Nelson, K. (2002) 'The relation between auditors' fees for non-audit services and earnings management', *The Accounting Review*, 77(s-1), p. 71–105.
- FRC (2018) *UK Corporate Governance Code*. Available at: <https://www.frc.org.uk/directors/corporate-governance-and-stewardship/uk-corporate-governance-code> (Accessed on 19 June 2022)
- FRC (2021) *International Standard on Auditing (UK) 240* (Revised May 2021). Available at: [https://www.frc.org.uk/getattachment/e48499f2-b69b-4f45-8bef-762583eab1cd/ISA-\(UK\)-240-Final.pdf](https://www.frc.org.uk/getattachment/e48499f2-b69b-4f45-8bef-762583eab1cd/ISA-(UK)-240-Final.pdf) (Accessed on 20 June 2022)
- Fuerst, O. and Kang, S. H. (2004) 'Corporate governance, expected operating performance, and pricing', *Corporate Ownership and Control*, 1(2), p. 13-30.
- Fuller, S. H., Joe, J. R. and Luippold, B. L. (2021) 'The effect of auditor reporting choice and audit committee oversight on management financial disclosures', *The Accounting Review*, 96(6), pp. 239-274.
- Fuzi, S. F. S., Halim, S. A. A. and Julizaerma, M. K. (2016) 'Board independence and firm performance', *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 37, p. 460-465.
- Gajevszky, A. (2014) 'The impact of auditor's opinion on earnings management: evidence from Romania', *Network Intelligence Studies*, 2(3), p. 61-73.
- Gao, P. and Zhang, G. (2019) 'Accounting manipulation, peer pressure, and internal control', *The Accounting Review*, 94(1), pp.127-151.
- Gaver, J. J. and Gaver, K. M. (1998) 'The relation between nonrecurring accounting transactions and CEO cash compensation', *The Accounting Review*, 73(2), p. 235- 253.
- Gaver, J. J., Gaver, K. M. and Austin, J. R. (1995) 'Additional evidence on bonus plans and income management', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 19(1), p. 3-28.
- Gavious, I., Segev, E. and Yosef, R. (2012) 'Female directors and earnings management in high-technology firms', *Pacific Accounting Review*, 24(1), p. 4-32.
- Gazi, M. A. (2009) 'Can governance and regulatory control ensure private higher education as business or public goods in Bangladesh?' *African Journal of Business Management*. 3(12), p. 890-906.

- Ghosh, A., Marra, A., and Moon, D. (2010) 'Corporate boards, audit committees, and earnings management: pre-and post-SOX evidence', *Journal of Business Finance & Accounting*, 37(9-10), p. 1145-1176.
- Githaiga, P. N., Muturi K, P. and Caroline B, T. (2022) 'Board characteristics and earnings management. Does firm size matter?' *Cogent Business & Management*, 9(1), p. 2088573.
- Given, L. M. ed. (2008) *The Sage encyclopedia of qualitative research methods*. Los Angeles, Calif.: Sage Publications. ISBN 1-4129-4163-6.
- Gompers, P., Ishii, J. and Metrick, A. (2003) 'Corporate governance and equity prices', *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 118(1), p. 107-155.
- González, J. S. and García-Meca, E. (2014) 'Does corporate governance influence earnings management in Latin American markets?' *Journal of Business Ethics*, 121(3), p. 419-440.
- Gore, P., Pope, P. F. and Singh, A. K. (2007) 'Earnings management and the distribution of earnings relative to targets: UK evidence', *Accounting and Business Research*, 37, p. 123-149.
- Graham, J. R., Harvey, C. R. and Rajgopal, S. (2005) 'The economic implications of corporate financial reporting', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 40(3), p. 3-73.
- Greenbury, R. (1995) *Directors' remuneration: report of the study group chaired by Sir Richard Greenbury*, London: Gee.
- Griffiths, I. (1986) *Creative Accounting*, London: Sidgwick & Jackson.
- Guay, W. R., Kothari, S. P. and Watts, R. L. (1996) 'A market-based evaluation of discretionary accrual models', *Journal of Accounting Research*, vol. 34, no. 3, p. 83-105.
- Gul, F., Fung, S. and Jaggi, B. (2009) 'Earnings quality: Some evidence on the role of auditor tenure and auditors' industry expertise', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 47(3), p. 265-287.
- Gulzar, M. A. (2011) 'Corporate governance characteristics and earnings management: empirical evidence from Chinese listed firms', *International Journal of Accounting and Financial Reporting*, 1(1), p. 133-151.
- Gulzar, M. A. and Wang, Z. (2011) 'Corporate finance characteristics and earnings management: Empirical evidence from Chinese listed firms', *International Journal of Accounting and Financial Reporting*, 1(1), p. 133-151.
- Gunny, K. (2010) 'The relation between earnings management using real activities manipulation and future performance: Evidence from meeting earnings benchmarks', *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 27(3), p. 855-888.
- Gurung, V. and Gupta, C., (2019). A review on Satyam computer failure lessons for corporate governance and world. Available at SSRN 3370291.
- Habib, A., Uddin, B. and Islam, A. (2013) 'Financial distress, earnings management and market pricing of accruals during the global financial crisis', *Managerial Finance*, 39(2), p. 155-180.
- Hackenbrack, K. and Nelson, M. W. (1996) 'Auditors' incentives and their application of financial accounting standards', *Accounting Review*, vol. 71, no. 1, p. 43-59.
- Hambrick, D. and Mason, P. (1984) 'Upper echelons: the organization as a reflection of its top managers', *Academy of Management Review*, 9(2), p. 193-206.
- Hambrick, D., Nadler, D. and Tushman, M. (1998) *Navigating change: how CEOs, top teams, and boards steer transformation*. Boston, MA: Harvard Business School Press.
- Hampel R. (1998) 'Committee on corporate governance: final report', London: Gee.
- Haniffa, R. M. and Cooke, T. E. (2002) 'Culture, corporate governance and disclosure in Malaysian corporations', *Abacus*, 38(3), p. 317-349.
- Hanna, J. D. (1999) 'Never say never', *CA Magazine*, p. 35-39.
- Harris, O., Karl, J. B. and Lawrence, E. (2019) 'CEO compensation and earnings management: does gender really matter?' *Journal of Business Research*, 98, pp.1-14.
- Harun, M. S., Hussainey, K., Mohd Kharuddin, K. A. and Farooque, O. A. (2020) 'CSR disclosure, corporate governance and firm value: a study on GCC Islamic banks', *International Journal of Accounting & Information Management*, 28(4), pp. 607-638.
- Haw, I. M., Ho, S. M. and Li, Y. S. (2011) 'Corporate governance and earnings management by classification shifting', *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 28(2), p. 517-553.
- Hayn, C. (1995) 'The information content of losses', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 20(2), p. 125-153.

- Healy, P. M. (1985) 'The effect of bonus schemes on accounting decisions', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 7(1-3), p. 85-107.
- Healy, P. and Wahlen, J. (1999) 'A review of the earnings management literature and its implications for standard setting', *Accounting Horizons*, Vol. 13, No. 4, p. 365-384.
- Heirany, F., Sadrabadi, A. N. and Mehrjordi, F. F. (2013) 'Investigating the effect of corporate governance mechanisms on the quality of accounting profit', *International Journal of Academic Researching Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*, 3(3), p. 315-328.
- Herrmann, D., Inoue, T. and Thomas, W. (2003) 'The sale of assets to manage earnings in Japan', *Journal of Accounting Research*, 41(1), p. 89-108.
- Hijazi, Q. and Al-Thuneibat, A. (2015) 'Auditor's opinions and earnings management: evidence from Jordan', *Proceedings of The Third International Conference on Innovation Economy*, University of Jordan, Amman, Jordan, 14-15 April 2015.
- Hinz, R. P., McCarthy, D. D. and Turner, J. A. (1997) 'Are women conservative investors? Gender differences in participant directed pension investments', *Wharton Pension Research Council Working Papers*. 578.
- Hlel, K., Kahloul, I. and Bouzgarrou, H. (2020) 'IFRS adoption, corporate governance and management earnings forecasts', *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*, 18(2), pp.325-342.
- Hodge, F. D. (2003) 'Investors' perceptions of earnings quality, auditor independence, and the usefulness of audited financial information', *Accounting Horizons*, vol. 17, p. 37-48.
- Holderness, C. G. and Sheehan, D. P. (1991) 'Monitoring an owner: The case of Turner Broadcasting', *Journal of Financial Economics*, 30(2), p. 325-346.
- Holthausen, R. W., Larcker, D. F. and Sloan, R. G. (1995) 'Annual bonus schemes and the manipulation of earnings', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 19(1), p. 29-74.
- Holthausen, R. W. and Leftwich, R. W. (1983) 'The economic consequences of accounting choice: implications of costly contracting and monitoring', *Journal of Accounting & Economics*, vol. 5, no. 2, p. 77.
- Hossain, M., Prevost, A. K. and Rao, R. P. (2001) 'Corporate governance in New Zealand: The effect of the 1993 Companies Act on the relation between board composition and firm performance', *Pacific-Basin Finance Journal*, 9(2), p. 119-145.
- Hosny, K. H. (2019) 'Board diversity and firm performance: empirical evidence from the United Kingdom' (Master's thesis).
- Houmes, R. E. and Skantz, T. R. (2010) 'Highly valued equity and discretionary accruals', *Journal of Business Finance and Accounting*, 37(1-2), p. 60-92.
- Hribar, P. and Collins, D. W. (2002) 'Errors in estimating accruals: Implications for empirical research', *Journal of Accounting Research*, 40(1), p. 105-134.
- Hsieh, Y. T., Chen, T. K., Tseng, Y. J. and Lin, R. C. (2018) 'Top management team characteristics and accrual-based earnings management', *International Journal of Accounting*, 53(4), p. 314-334.
- Hughes, P. J. (1986) 'Signalling by direct disclosure under asymmetric information', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 8(2), p. 119-142.
- Hunton, J. E., Libby, R. and Mazza, C. (2006) 'Financial reporting transparency and earnings management', *The Accounting Review*, 81(1), p. 135-158.
- Huson, M., Tian, Y., Wier, H. and Wiedman, C. (2012) 'Managing earnings management: compensation committees' treatment of earnings components in CEOs' terminal years', *The Accounting Review*, 87(1), p. 231-259.
- Ianniello, G. (2015) 'The effects of board and auditor independence on earnings quality: evidence from Italy', *Journal of Management and Governance*, 19(1), p. 229-253.
- ICAEW (2017) The Cadbury report: Codes and reports. [Online] Available at: <http://www.icaew.com/en/library/subject-gateways/corporate-governance/codes-and-reports/cadbury-report> (Accessed on 18 June 2021)
- IFAC (2004) International Federation of Accountants 2004 Annual Report. Available at: https://www.ifac.org/system/files/publications/files/IFAC_2004_Annual.pdf (Accessed on 19 August 2022)

- Indriani, A. D. and Pujiono, P. (2021) 'Analysis of earnings management practices using the modified Jones model on the industry company index Kompas 100', *The Indonesian Accounting Review*, 11(2), p.235.
- Iraya, C., Mwangi, M., and Wanjohi, G. (2015) 'The effect of corporate governance practices on earnings management of companies listed at the Nairobi securities exchange', *European Scientific Journal*, 11(1), p. 169-178.
- Jackling, B. and Johl, S. (2009) 'Board structure and firm performance: evidence from India's top companies', *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 17(4), p. 492–509.
- Jackson, S. B. and Pitman, M. K. (2001) 'Auditors and earnings management', *The CPA Journal*, 71(7), p.38.
- Jaggi, B. and Leung, S. (2007) 'Impact of family dominance on monitoring of earnings management by audit committees: Evidence from Hong Kong', *Journal of International Accounting, Auditing and Taxation*, 16(1), p. 27–50.
- Jaggi, B., Leung, S. and Gul, F. A. (2009) 'Family control, board independence and earnings management: Evidence based on Hong Kong firms', *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 28(4), p. 281-300.
- Jamadar, Y., Ong, T. S., Abdullah, A. A. and Kamarudin, F. (2022) 'Earnings and discretionary accruals', *Managerial and Decision Economics*, 43(2), pp. 431-439.
- Jamnik, A. (2019) 'Moral theories and application in business ethics (ethical codes)', *In International Scientific Conference*, Juraj Dobrila University of Pula, pp. 227-246.
- Jensen M. C. and Fama, E. F. (1983) 'Agency Problems and Residual Claims', *Journal of Law and Economics*, 26(2), p. 327-349.
- Jensen, M. C. and Meckling, W. H. (2019) Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs and ownership structure. *In Corporate Governance* (p. 77-132), Gower.
- Jensen, M. C. (1993) 'The modern industrial revolution, exit, and the failure of internal control systems', *The Journal of Finance*, 48(3), p. 831-880.
- Jensen, M. C. (2019) Eclipse of the public corporation. *In Corporate governance* (pp. 239-252), Gower.
- Jiang, W. and Anandarajan, A. (2009) 'Shareholder rights, corporate governance and earnings quality: The influence of institutional investors'. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 24(8), p. 767-791.
- Jiang, J. X., Petroni, K. R. and Wang, I. Y. (2010) 'CFOs and CEOs: Who have the most influence on earnings management?' *Journal of Financial Economics*, 96(3), p. 513–526.
- Jimoh, J. and Iyoha, F. (2012) 'Stewardship and corporate governance in the banking sector: evidence from Nigeria', *Accounting and Finance Research*, Vol. 1, No. 1, p. 198.
- Johnson, V. E., Khurana, I. K. and Reynolds, J. K. (2002) 'Audit-firm tenure and the quality of financial reports', *Contemporary Accounting Research*, vol. 19, no. 4, p. 637-660.
- Jones, J. J. (1991) 'Earnings management during import relief investigations', *Journal of Accounting Research*, vol. 29, no. 2, p. 193-228.
- Jones, M. (2011) 'Creative accounting, fraud and international accounting scandals', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 24(8), p. 99-126.
- Jones, T. M. (1995) 'Instrumental stakeholder theory: A synthesis of ethics and economics', *Academy of Management Review*, 20(2), p. 404-437.
- Kahneman and Tversky (1979) 'Prospect theory: An analysis of decision under risk', *Econometrica*, 47 (2), p. 263-291.
- Kakabadse, N. K., Yang, H. and Sanders, R. (2010) 'The effectiveness of non-executive directors in Chinese state-owned enterprises', *Management Decision*, 48(7), p. 1063–1079.
- Kanapathippillai, S., Gul, F., Mihret, D. and Muttakin, M. B. (2019) 'Compensation committees, CEO pay and firm performance', *Pacific-Basin finance journal*, 57, p.101187.
- Kandel, B. (2020) 'Qualitative versus quantitative research', *Journal of product Innovation management*, 32(5), p.658.
- Kao, L. and Chen, A. (2004) 'The effects of board characteristics on earnings management', *Corporate Ownership & Control*, 1(3), p. 96–107.
- Kao, M. F., Hodgkinson, L. and Jaafar, A. (2019) 'Ownership structure, board of directors and firm performance: evidence from Taiwan', *Corporate Governance: The international journal of business in society*, 19(1), pp. 189-216.

- Kaplan, R. S. (1985) 'Comments on Paul Healy: Evidence on the effect of bonus schemes on accounting procedure and accrual decisions', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 7, p. 109-113.
- Kaplan, S. and Minton, B. (1994) 'Appointments of outsiders to Japanese boards: determinants and implications for managers', *Journal of Financial Economics*, 36(2), p. 225-257.
- Kapoor, N. and Goel, S. (2019) 'Do diligent independent directors restrain earnings management practices? Indian lessons for the global world', *Asian Journal of Accounting Research*, 4(1), pp. 52-69.
- Karamanou, I. and Vafeas, N. (2005) 'The association between corporate boards, audit committees, and management earnings forecasts: An empirical analysis', *Journal of Accounting Research*, 43(3), p. 453-486.
- Karim, A. M. (2021) 'An Empirical Study on Viewpoint Among Auditors and Accountants: Creative Accounting and Forensic Accounting Implication', *Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry*, 12(7).
- Kasznik, R. (1999) 'On the association between voluntary disclosure and earnings management', *Journal of Accounting Research*, 37(1), p. 57-82.
- Ketola, A. Y. (2009) *Earnings management shareholders point of view*, University of Technology, Lappeenranta. Available at: <https://lutpub.lut.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/90738/Earnings%20Management%20Shareholders%20point%20of%20view.pdf?sequence=1> (Accessed on 15 June 2020)
- Kim, S. H., Udawatte, P. and Yin, J. (2019) 'The effects of corporate social responsibility on real and accrual-based earnings management: evidence from China', *Australian Accounting Review*, 29(3), p. 580-594.
- Kini, O., Kracaw, W. and Mian, S. (1995) 'Corporate take-overs, firm performance and board composition', *Journal of Corporate Finance*, Vol 1(3-4), p. 383-412.
- Klein, A. (1998) 'Firm performance and board committee structure', *Journal of Law and Economics*, Vol. 41(1), p. 275-304.
- Klein (2002) 'Audit committee, board of director characteristics, and earnings management', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 33(3), p. 375-400.
- Klenke, K. (2002) *Women weaving webs: the transformative powers of technology*. Paper presented at the 1st Global Transformation in Politics, Culture and Society Conference, Brussels on 6-8 December.
- Klenke, K. (2003) 'Gender influences in decision-making processes in top management teams', *Management Decision*, 41(10), p. 1024 -34.
- Kliestik, T., Valaskova, K., Nica, E., Kovacova, M. and Lazaroiu, G. (2020) 'Advanced methods of earnings management: Monotonic trends and change-points under spotlight in the Visegrad countries', *Oeconomia Copernicana*, 11(2), pp.371-400.
- Koh, P. S. (2003) 'On the association between institutional ownership and aggressive corporate earnings management in Australia', *The British Accounting Review*, 35(2), p. 105-128.
- Koh, P. S., Laplante, S. K. and Tong, Y. H. (2007) 'Accountability and value enhancement roles of corporate governance'. *Accounting & Finance*, 47(2), p.305-333.
- Kosnik, R. (1987) 'Greenmail a study of board performance in corporation governance', *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 32, p. 163-185.
- Kosnik, R. D. (1990) 'Effects of board demography and directors' incentives on corporate greenmail decisions', *Academy of Management Journal*, 33(1), p. 129-150.
- Kothari, S. P., Leone, A. J. and Wasley, C. E. (2005) 'Performance matched discretionary accrual measures', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 39(1), p. 163-197.
- Kovacova, M. and Kliestik, T. (2017) 'Logit and Probit application for the prediction of bankruptcy in Slovak companies. Equilibrium', *Quarterly Journal of Economics and Economic Policy*, 12(4), p. 775-791.
- Krishnan, G. V. (2003) 'Audit Quality and the Pricing of Discretionary Accruals', *Auditing*, vol. 22, no. 1, p. 109.
- Krishnan, G. V. (2003) 'Does Big 6 auditor industry expertise constrain earnings management?' *Accounting Horizons*, vol. 17, p. 1-16.
- Krishnan, J. (2005) 'Audit committee quality and internal control: An empirical analysis', *The Accounting Review*, 80(2), p. 649-675.

- Krishnan, G. V. and Parsons, L. M. (2008) 'Getting to the bottom line: An exploration of gender and earnings quality', *Journal of Business Ethics*, 78(1-2), p. 65-76.
- Kumari, P. and Pattanayak, J. K. (2014) 'The role of board characteristics as a control mechanism of earnings management: a study of select Indian service sector companies', *IUP Journal of Corporate Governance*, 13(1), p. 58.
- Kyere, M. and Ausloos, M. (2021) 'Corporate governance and firms financial performance in the United Kingdom', *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 26(2), pp. 1871-1885.
- Lambert, R. A. (1984) 'Income smoothing as rational equilibrium behavior', *The Accounting Review*, 59, p. 604-618.
- Lamoreaux, P. T., Litov, L. P. and Mauler, L. M. (2019) 'Lead Independent Directors: Good governance or window dressing?' *Journal of Accounting Literature*, 43(1), pp.47-69.
- Lampe, J. and Finn, D. (1992) 'A model of auditors' ethical decision processes', *Auditing: A Journal of Practice and Theory*, 11, p. 33-59.
- Larcker, D. and Tayan, B. (2020) *Corporate governance matters*. FT Press.
- La Porta, R., Lopez-de-Silanes, F., Shleifer, A. and Vishny, R. (1997) 'Legal determinants of external finance'. *Journal of Finance*, 52(3), p. 1131-1150.
- La Porta, R., Lopez-de-Silanes, F., Shleifer, A., and Vishny, R. (2000) 'Investor protection and corporate governance', *Journal of Financial Economics*, 58(1-2), p. 3-27.
- La Porta, R., Lopez-De-Silanes, F., Shleifer, A. and Vishney, R. (2002) 'Investor protection and corporate valuation', *Journal of Finance*, Vol. 57, No. 3, p. 1147-1170.
- Laing, D. and Weir, C. (1999) 'Governance structures, size and corporate performance in UK firms', *Management Decision*, 37(5), p. 457-464.
- Larcker, D. and Tayan, B. (2020) *Corporate governance matters*. FT Press.
- Latham, M. (1999) 'The corporate monitoring firm', *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, Vol. 7, No. 1, p. 1-21.
- Lee, C., Rosenstein, S., Rangan, N. and Davidson, III, W. (1992) 'Board composition and shareholder wealth. the case of management buyouts', *Financial Management*, 21, p. 58-72.
- Leng, A. C. A. (2004) 'The impact of corporate governance practices on firms' financial performance: Evidence from Malaysian companies', *ASEAN Economic Bulletin*, 21(3), p. 308-318.
- Leuz, C., Nanda, D. and Wysocki, P. D. (2003) 'Investor protection and earnings management: an international comparison', *Journal of Financial Economics*, Vol. 69, No. 3, p. 505-527.
- Levitt, A. (1998) 'Arthur Levitt addresses "Illusions"', *Journal of Accountancy*, vol. 186, no. 6, p. 12-13.
- Levitt, J. (1998) 'The 'Numbers Game'', *CPA Journal*, vol. 68, no. 12, p. 14.
- Lin, J. W. and Hwang, Mi. (2010) 'Audit quality, corporate governance, and earnings management: a meta-analysis', *International Journal of Auditing*, Vol. 14, No. 1, p. 57-77.
- Linck, J., Netter, J. and Yang, T. (2005) 'Effects and unintended consequences of the Sarbanes-Oxley Act on corporate boards', *The Review of Financial Studies*, 22(8), p. 3287-3328.
- Lipton, M. and Lorsch, J. (1992) 'A modest proposal for improved corporate governance', *Business Lawyer*, Vol. 48, p. 59-77.
- Liu, J. (2012) 'Board monitoring, management contracting and earnings management: An evidence from ASX listed companies', *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, Vol. 4, No 12, p. 121-136.
- Liu, J., Harris, K. and Omar, N. (2013) 'Board committees and earnings management', *Corporate Board: Role, Duties & Composition*, 9(1), p. 6-17.
- Liu, M. (2020) 'Real and accrual-based earnings management in the pre-and post-engagement partner signature requirement periods in the United Kingdom', *Review of Quantitative Finance and Accounting*, 54(3), pp.1133-1161.
- Liu, Q. and Lu, Z. (2007) 'Corporate governance and earnings management in Chinese listed companies: a tunnelling perspective', *Journal of Corporate Finance*, Vol. 13, No. 5, p. 881-906.
- Llukani, T. (2013) 'Earnings management and firm size: an empirical analyze in Albanian market', *European Scientific Journal*, 9(16), p. 135-143.
- Loderer, C. and Peyer, U. (2002) 'Board overlap, seat accumulation and share prices', *European Financial Management*, Vol 8(2), p.165-192.
- Louis, H. (2004) 'Earnings management and market performance of acquiring firms', *Journal of Financial Economics*, 74(1), p. 121-148.

- Lublin, J. S. (2014) 'Smaller boards get bigger returns', *Wall Street Journal*. Available at: <https://www.wsj.com/articles/smaller-boards-get-bigger-returns-1409078628> (Accessed on 14 June 2021)
- Maduagufor, U. (2008) *Stock Market News*. Available at: www.stokmarketnigeria.com (Accessed on 15 June 2022)
- Mahjoub, I. and Miloudi, A. (2015) 'Earnings management: A review of literature', *Euro and The European Banking System: Evolutions and Challenges*, December, p. 691-703.
- Makar, S. D., Alam, P. and Pearson (2000) 'Earnings management: when does juggling the numbers become fraud?' *Fraud Magazine*, 14(1), pp. 60-77.
- Man, C. K., and Wong, B. (2013) 'Corporate governance and earnings management: A survey of literature', *Journal of Applied Business Research*, (JABR), 29(2), p. 391-418.
- Mangala, D. (2019) 'Do corporate governance characteristics constrain earnings management? The role of board, audit committee and ownership structure in Indian corporate sector', *IUP Journal of Accounting Research & Audit Practices*, 18(4), pp.7-32.
- Mansor, N., Che-Ahmad, A., Ahmad-Zaluki, N. A. and Osman, A. H. (2013) 'Corporate governance and earnings management: A study on the Malaysian family and non-family owned PLCs', *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 7, p. 221-229.
- Marashdeh, Z., Alomari, M. W., Aleqab, M. M. and Alqatamin, R. M. (2021) 'Board characteristics and firm performance: The case of Jordanian non-financial institutions', *Journal of Governance and Regulation*, volume 10(3), pp. 150-159.
- Mard, Y. (2003) 'Accounting performance and earnings management', *In Identification and control of risks: challenges for auditing, accounting and management control*. Available at: <https://shs.hal.science/halshs-00582798> (Accessed on 12 June 2020)
- Marquardt, C. A. and Wiedman, C. I. (2004) 'How Are Earnings Managed? An Examination of Specific Accruals', *Contemporary Accounting Research*, vol. 21, no. 2, p. 461-491.
- Marra, A., Mazzola, P. and Prencipe, A. (2011) 'Board monitoring and earnings management pre- and post-IFRS', *The International Journal of Accounting*, 46(2), p. 205-230.
- Mather, P. and Ramsay, A. (2003) 'The effects of corporate governance mechanisms on earnings and impression management around CEO changes', *Annual Financial Reporting and Business Communication Conference*, Cardiff, July.
- Matsumoto, D. A. (2002) 'Management's incentives to avoid negative earnings surprises', *The Accounting Review*, 77 (3), p. 485-514.
- Matsunaga, S. R. and Park, C. W. (2001) 'The effect of missing a quarterly earnings benchmark on the CEO's annual bonus', *The Accounting Review*, 76(3), p. 313-332.
- Michalkova, L. (2021) 'Earnings quality and accruals over company' s life cycle', *In SHS Web of Conferences*, Vol. 92, p. 02043, EDP Sciences.
- McAnally, M. L., Srivastava, A. and Weaver, C. D. (2008) 'Executive Stock Options, Missed Earnings Targets and Earnings Management', *The Accounting Review*, 83(1), p. 185-216.
- McNichols, M. F. (2000) 'Research design issues in earnings management studies', *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, vol. 19, no. 4-5, p. 313-345.
- McNichols, M. F. (2002) 'Discussion of the quality of accruals and earnings: The role of accrual estimation errors', *The Accounting Review*, 77(s-1), p. 61-69.
- McNichols, M. and Wilson, G. P. (1988) 'Evidence of Earnings Management from the Provision for Bad Debts', *Journal of Accounting Research*, vol. 26, no. 3, p. I31.
- McVay, S., Nagar, V. and Tang, V. W. (2006) 'Trading Incentives to Meet the Analyst Forecast', *Review of Accounting Studies*, 11(4), p. 575-598.
- Merchant, K. A. and Rockness, J. (1994) 'The ethics of managing earnings: an empirical investigation', *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 13(1), p. 79-94.
- Messier, W. F., Glover, S. M. and Prawitt, D. F. (2008) *Auditing and Assurance Services: A Systematic Approach*. 6th ed., Boston, MA: McGraw-Hill Irwin.
- Mitra, S. (2002) 'The impact of institutional stock ownership on a firm's earnings management practice: An empirical investigation', Louisiana State University and Agricultural and Mechanical College.
- Mitton, T. (2002) 'A cross-firm analysis of the impact of corporate governance on the East Asian financial crisis', *Journal of Financial Economics*, 64(2), p. 215-241.

- Molz, R. (1988) 'Managerial domination of boards of directors and financial performance', *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 16(3), p. 235-249.
- Morck, R., Shleifer, A. and Vishny, R. W. (1988) 'Management Ownership and Market Valuation: An Empirical Analysis', *Journal of Financial Economics*, 20(1), p. 293-315.
- Mortas, M. (2019) 'Obstacle to transparency in financial reporting: fraudulent financial reporting', *New Horizons in Social, Human and Administrative Sciences*, p. 271.
- Moyer, S. E. (1990) 'Capital adequacy ratio regulations and accounting choices in commercial banks', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, vol. 13, no. 2, p. 123-154.
- Mrabure, K. O. and Abhulimhen-Iyoha, A. (2020) 'Corporate governance and protection of stakeholders rights and interests', *Beijing I. Rev.*, 11, p.292.
- Nasiri, M. and Ramakrishnan, S. (2020) 'Earnings management, corporate governance and corporate performance among Malaysian listed companies', *Journal of Environmental Treatment Techniques*.
- Nelson, S. P. and Devi, S. (2013) 'Audit Committee Experts and Earnings Quality', *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 13, p. 335-351.
- Nenova, T. (2003) 'The value of corporate votes and control benefits: a cross-country analysis', *Journal of Financial Economics*, 68(3), p. 325-351.
- Neuman, W. L. (2000) *Social research methods: qualitative and quantitative approaches*. 7th ed. Available at: http://letrunghieutvu.yolasite.com/resources/w-lawrence-neuman-social-research-methods_-qualitative-and-quantitative-approaches-pearson-education-limited-2013.pdf (Accessed on 25 June 2022)
- Ngo, D. N. P. and Le, A. T. H. (2021) 'Relationship between the audit committee and earnings management in listed companies in Vietnam', *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(2), pp. 135-142.
- NYSE (2014) NYSE: Corporate Governance Guide. Available at: https://www.nyse.com/publicdocs/nyse/listing/NYSE_Corporate_Governance_Guide.pdf (Accessed on 19 June 2022)
- O'Brien, P. C. and Bhushan, R. (1990) 'Analyst following and institutional ownership', *Journal of Accounting Research*, 28, p. 55-76.
- OECD (2004) OECD principles of corporate governance. Available at: <https://www.oecd.org/corporate/ca/corporategovernanceprinciples/31557724.pdf> (Accessed: 20 June 2022). (Accessed: 20 June 2022)
- Omri, M. A, Ajlani, I. and Rbia, M. A, (2005) 'Discretionary practices of Tunisian banks'. In *7th international symposium in management sciences*, Hammamet, Tunisia.
- Orazalin, N. (2020) 'Board gender diversity, corporate governance, and earnings management: Evidence from an emerging market', *Gender in Management: An International Journal*, 35(1), pp.37-60.
- Pagano, M., Panetta, F. and Zingales, L. (1995) 'Why Do Companies Go Public? An Empirical Analysis', *Manuscript*. Graduate School of Business. The University of Chicago.
- Park, Y. S., Konge, L. and Artino Jr, A. R. (2020) 'The positivism paradigm of research', *Academic Medicine*, 95(5), pp.690-694.
- Park, Y. and Shin, H. (2004) 'Board composition and earnings management in Canada', *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 10(3), p. 431-457.
- Patrick, E. A., Paulinus, E. C. and Nympha, A. N. (2015) 'The influence of corporate governance on earnings management practices: a study of some selected quoted companies in Nigeria', *American Journal of Economics, Finance and Management*, Vol. 1, No. 5, p. 482-493.
- Pearce, J. A. and Zhara, S. A. (1992) 'Board compensation from a strategic contingency perspective', *Journal of Management Studies*, Vol. 29, p. 411-438.
- Peasnell, K. V., Pope, P. F. and Young, S. (1998) 'Managerial ownership and the demand for outside directors', *International Centre for Research in Accounting*, Working Paper, University of Lancaster.
- Peasnell, K., Pope, P. and Young, S. (2000) 'Accrual management to meet earnings targets: UK evidence pre- and post-Cadbury', *The British Accounting Review*, 32(4), p. 415-445.
- Peasnell, K. V., Pope, P. F. and Young, S. (2005) 'Board monitoring and earnings management: do outside directors influence abnormal accruals?' *Journal of Business Finance and Accounting*, 32(7) & (8), p. 1311-1346.

- Peni, E. and Vähämaa, S. (2010) 'Female executives and earnings management'. *Managerial finance*, Vol. 36, No. 7, p. 629-645.
- Perry, S. and Williams, T. (1994) 'Earnings management preceding management buyout offers', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 18(2), p. 157-79.
- Petra, S. T. (2005) 'Do outside independent directors strengthen corporate boards?' *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 5(1), pp.55-64.
- Petroni, K. (1992) 'Optimistic reporting in the property-casualty insurance industry', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 15(4), p. 485-608.
- Petroni, K., Ke, B. and Safieddine, A. (1999) 'Ownership concentration and sensitivity of executive pay to accounting performance measures: Evidence from publicly and privately-held insurance companies', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 28(2), p. 185-209.
- Pfeffer, J. (1972) 'Size and composition of corporate boards of directors: the organization and its environment', *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 17, p. 218–228.
- Pfeffer, J. (2019) 'Size and composition of corporate boards of directors: The organization and its environment', *In Corporate governance*, (pp. 53-64), Gower.
- Pfeffer, J. and Salancik, G. R. (1978) 'A resource dependence perspective'. *In Intercorporate relations. The structural analysis of business*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Phillips, J., Pincus, M. and Rego, S. O. (2003) 'Earnings management: New evidence based on deferred tax expense', *The Accounting Review*, 78(2), p. 491-521.
- Piot, C. and Janin, R. (2007) 'External auditors, audit committees and earnings management in France', *European Accounting Review*, 16, p. 429–454.
- Pourciau, S. (1993) 'Earnings management and non-routine executive changes', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 16(1, 2&3), p. 317-336.
- Powell, G. (1990) 'One more time: do male and female managers differ?' *Academy of Management Executive*, 43(3), p. 68-75.
- Powell, M. and Ansic, D. (1997) 'Gender differences in risk behavior in financial decision making: an experimental analysis', *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 18(6), p. 605-628.
- Pucheta-Martínez, M. C. and De Fuentes, C. (2007) 'The impact of audit committee characteristics on the enhancement of the quality of financial reporting: An empirical study in the Spanish context', *Corporate governance: An international review*, 15(6), pp.1394-1412.
- Pucheta-Martínez, M. C. and Gallego-Álvarez, I. (2020) 'Do board characteristics drive firm performance? An international perspective', *Review of Managerial Science*, 14(6), pp. 1251-1297.
- Puni, A. and Anlesinya, A. (2020) 'Corporate governance mechanisms and firm performance in a developing country', *International Journal of Law and Management*, Vol. 62 No. 2, pp. 147-169.
- Quttainah, M. A., Song, L. and Wu, Q. (2013) 'Do Islamic banks employ less earnings management?' *Journal of International Financial Management & Accounting*, vol. 24, no 3, p. 203-233.
- Rahman, D., Faff, R. and Oliver, B. (2021) 'Does board independence constrain insider opportunism?' *Australian Journal of Management*, 46(3), pp. 499-522.
- Rahman, A. and Haniffa, R. M. (2005) 'The effect of role duality on corporate performance in Malaysia', *Corp. Ownership Cont.*, 2(2), p. 40-47.
- Rahman, M. M., Moniruzzaman, M. and Sharif, M. J. (2013) 'Techniques, motives and controls of earnings management', *International Journal of Information Technology and Business Management*, 11(1), p. 22-34.
- Raimo, N., Vitolla, F., Marrone, A and Rubino, M. (2021) 'Do audit committee attributes influence integrated reporting quality? An agency theory viewpoint', *Bus Strat Env*, 30:522–534.
- Ramachandran, J., Ngete, Z. A., Subramanian, R. and Sambasivan, M. (2015) 'Does corporate governance influence earnings management? Evadne from Singapore', *The Journal of Developing Areas*, p. 263-274.
- Rao, N. and Dandale, S. (2008) 'Earnings management: a study of equity rights issues in India', *ICFAI J. Appl. Finance*, 14, p. 20-34.
- Rauterberg, G. (2020) 'The essential roles of agency law', *Michigan Law Review*, pp. 609-653.
- Rechner, P. L. and Dalton, D. R. (1991) 'CEO duality and organizational performance: a longitudinal analysis', *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol. 12, No. 2, p. 155-160.

- Rediker, K. J. and Seth, A. (1995) 'Boards of directors and substitution effects of alternative governance mechanisms', *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol 16, p. 85-99.
- Rodriguez, E. F. and Anson, S. G. (2001) 'Wealth effects associated with the compliance with the code of best practice: The Spanish experience', *In Business intelligence: knowledge management in the company*, p. 291-299.
- Roe, M. (1991) 'A political theory of American corporate finance', *Columbia Law Review*, 91(1), p. 10-67.
- Roe, M. (1993) 'Some differences in corporate structure in Germany, Japan, and the United States', *The Yale Law Review*, 102, p. 1927-2003.
- Romano, R. (1993) *The genius of American corporate law*. Washington, D.C: American Enterprise Institute Press.
- Roreng, P. P. (2021) 'The effect of corporate governance on earnings management', *The journal of contemporary issues in business and government*, 27(3), pp. 1001-1007.
- Roychowdhury, S. (2006) 'Earnings management through real activities manipulation', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, No. 42, p. 335-370.
- Ruigrok, W., Peck, S., Tacheva, S., Greve, P. and Hu, Y. (2006) 'The determinants and effects of board nomination committees', *Journal of Management & Governance*, 10(2), p. 119-148.
- Ruiz, C. V. (2016) 'Literature review of earnings management: who, why, when, how and what for', *Finnish business review*, 21(1), p. 74-87.
- Sadaf, R., Olah, J., Popp, J. and Mate, D. (2018) 'An investigation of the influence of the worldwide governance and competitiveness on accounting fraud cases: a cross-country perspective', *Sustainability*, 10(3), p. 1-11.
- Saeed, A., Ali, Q., Riaz, H. and Khan, M. A. (2022) 'Audit committee independence and auditor reporting for financially distressed companies: evidence from an emerging economy', *SAGE Open*, 12(2), p. 21582440221089951.
- Sahu, T. N. and Manna, A. (2013) 'Impact of board composition and board meeting on firms' performance: a study of selected Indian companies', *Vilakshan: The XIMB Journal of Management*, 10(2), p. 99-112.
- Saleh, M. N., Iskandar, M. T. and Rahmat, M. (2005) 'Earning management and board characteristics: Evidence from Malaysia', *Journal Pengurusan*, 24, p. 77-103.
- Saleh, M. N. and Iskandar, M. T. (2007) 'Audit committee characteristics and earning management: Evidence from Malaysia', *Asian Review of Accounting*, 15(2), p. 147-163.
- Saona, P., Muro, L. and Alvarado, M. (2020) 'How do the ownership structure and board of directors' features impact earnings management? The Spanish case', *Journal of International Financial Management & Accounting*, 31(1), pp.98-133.
- Sarhan, A. A., Ntim, C. G. and Al-Najjar, B. (2019) 'Board diversity, corporate governance, corporate performance, and executive pay', *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 24(2), pp.761-786.
- Schipper, K. (1989) 'Commentary on earnings management', *Accounting Horizons*, Vol. 3 (December), p. 91-102.
- Scott W. R. (1997) *Financial Accounting Theory*, Prentice-Hall, Scarborough
- SEC (2017) Rules and Regulations for the Securities and Exchange Commission and Major Securities Laws. Available at: <https://www.sec.gov/about/laws/secrulesregs> (Accessed on: 20 May 2022)
- Setiawan, D., Phua, L. K., Chee, H. K. and Trinugroho, I. (2020) 'The effect of audit committee characteristics on earnings management: The case of Indonesia', *Afro-Asian Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 10(4), pp.447-463.
- Shakir, R. (2008) 'Board size, executive directors and property firm performance in Malaysia', *Pacific Rim Property Research Journal*, 14(1), p. 66-80.
- Sharma, V. D. (2004) 'Board of director characteristics, institutional ownership, and fraud: Evidence from Australia', *Auditing: A Journal of Practice and Theory*, 23(2), p. 105-117.
- Shaub, M. (1994) 'An analysis of factors affecting the cognitive moral development of auditors and auditing students', *Journal of Accounting Education*, 12(1), p. 1-26.
- Sheikh, N., Wang, Z. and Khan, S. (2013) 'The impact of internal attributes of corporate governance on firm performance', *International Journal of Commerce and Management*, 23(1), p. 38-55.
- Shen, M. (2007) *Accounting choices of soliciting targets*. New York: M S N Enterprise Hall.

- Shivdasani, A. (1993) 'Board composition, ownership structure, and hostile takeovers', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 16(1-3), p. 167-198.
- Shivdasani, A. and Yermack, D. (1998) 'CEO involvement in the selection of new board members: an empirical analysis', *Journal of Finance*, Vol. 54, No. 5, p. 1829-53.
- Shleifer, A. and Vishny, R. W. (1986) 'Large shareholders and corporate control', *The Journal of Political Economy*, 94(3 Part 1), p. 461-488.
- Shleifer, A. and Vishny, R. (1997) 'A survey of corporate governance', *Journal of Finance*, 52(2), p. 737-783.
- Shores, D., Bowen, R. and DuCharme, L. (1995) 'Stakeholders' implicit claims and accounting method choice', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 20(3), p. 255 – 295.
- Shrivastav, S. M. and Kalsie, A. (2016) 'The relationship between CEO duality and firm performance: an analysis using panel data approach', *IUP Journal of Corporate Governance*. 15(2), p. 37-58.
- Siekelova, A., Androniceanu, A., Durana, P. and Frajtova Michalikova, K. (2020) 'Earnings management (EM), initiatives and company size: An empirical study', *Acta Polytechnica Hungarica*, 17(9), p. 41-56.
- Siekelova, A. (2021) 'Historical development of earnings management models', *In SHS Web of Conferences*, (Vol. 92, p. 02058), EDP Sciences.
- Siekelova, A., Belas, J., Podhorska, I. and Durana, P. (2021) 'Accrual-based earnings management: a case study in v4 focusing on mining and quarrying sector', *Acta Montanistica Slovaca*, 26(1).
- Siregar, S. V. and Utama, S. (2008) 'Type of earnings management and the effect of ownership structure, firm size, and corporate-governance practices: Evidence from Indonesia', *The International Journal of Accounting*, Volume 43, Issue 1, p. 1-27.
- Skousen, K. F., Glover, S. M. and Prawitt, D. F. (2005) *An Introduction to Corporate Governance and the SEC*. Thomson South-Western, Mason, OH.
- Sloan, R. G. (1996) 'Do stock prices fully reflect information in accruals and cash flows about future earnings?' *The Accounting Review*, 71(3), p. 289 – 315.
- Smith, T. (1992) *Accounting for growth*, London: Century Business.
- Soliman, M. and Ragab, A. A. (2013) 'Board of director's attributes and earning management: Evidence from Egypt', *In Proceedings of 6th International Business and Social Sciences Research Conference*.
- Solomon, J., (2020). *Corporate governance and accountability*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Somnath, D., Shroff, K. and Zhang, H. (2009) 'Quarterly earnings patterns and earnings management', *Contemporary Accounting Research*, vol. 26, no. 3, p. 797-831.
- Song, J. and Windram, B. (2004) 'Benchmarking audit committee effectiveness in financial reporting', *International Journal of Auditing*, 8(3), p. 195–205.
- Srinidhi, B., Gul, F. A. and Tsui, J. (2011) 'Female directors and earnings quality', *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 28(5), p. 1610-1644.
- Srinivasan, S. (2005) 'Consequences of financial reporting failure for outside directors: evidence from accounting restatements and audit committee members', *Journal of Accounting Research*, 43, p. 291–334.
- Standards Australia International, (2003) 'AS 8000–2003', Australian Standard – good governance principles, (Standards Australia International, Sydney).
- Stigler, G. (1958) 'The Economies of Scale', *Journal of Law and Economics*, 1, p. 54-71.
- Stocken, P. C. and Verrecchia, R. E. (2004) 'Financial reporting system choice and disclosure management', *The Accounting Review*, 79(4), p. 1181- 1203.
- Strakova, L. (2020) 'Earnings management in global background', *In SHS Web of Conferences*, (Vol. 74, p. 01032), EDP Sciences.
- Subramanyam, K. (1996) 'The pricing of discretionary accruals', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 22(1-3), p.249-281.
- Suda, K. and Shuto, A. (2006) 'Earnings management to meet earnings benchmarks: Evidence from Japan', *Focus on Finance and Accounting Research*, Nova Science Publisher Inc., New York, p. 67-85.
- Suh, Y. S. (1990) 'Communication and income smoothing through accounting method choice', *Management Science*, 36, p. 704-723.

- Sun, Y., Wang, W., Wang, X. F. and Zhang, W. (2013) 'Shareholder activism and earnings management incentives: an empirical examination of shareholder proposals in the United States', *Journal of International Management & Accounting*, 24(3), p. 34-37.
- Sunden, A. E. and Surette, B. J. (1998) 'Gender differences in the allocation of assets in retirement savings plans', *American Economic Review*, 88(2), p. 207-11.
- Svabova, L., Kramarova, K. and Durica, M. (2018) 'Prediction model of firm's financial distress', *Ekonomicko-manazerske spektrum*, 12(1), p. 16-29.
- Swai, J. P. and Mbogela, C. S. (2016) 'Accrual-based versus real earnings management: the effect of ownership structure: evidence from East Africa', *ACRN Oxford Journal of Finance and Risk Perspectives*, 5(2), p. 121-140.
- Swastika, D. L. T. (2013) 'Corporate governance, firm size, and earning management: Evidence in Indonesia stock exchange', *IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance (IOSR-JEF)*, 10(4), p. 77-82.
- Sweeney, A. (1994) 'Debt-covenant violations and managers' accounting responses', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 17(3), p. 281-308.
- Sweeney, J. (1995) 'The moral expertise of auditors: an exploratory analysis', *Research on Accounting Ethics*, 1, p. 213-234.
- Taktak, B., N. and Mbarki, I. (2014) 'Board characteristics, external auditing quality and earnings management', *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economies*, Vol. 4, No 1, p. 79-96.
- Teoh, S. H., Welch, I. and Wong, T. J. (1998) 'Earnings management and the long-term under performance of initial public offerings', *Journal of Finance*, vol. 53, p. 1935-1974.
- Terjesen, S., Sealy, R. and Singh, V. (2009) 'Women directors on corporate boards: A review and research agenda', *Corporate governance: an international review*, 17(3), p. 320-337.
- Thiruvadi, S. and Huang, H.W. (2011) 'Audit committee gender differences and earnings management', *Gender in Management: An International Journal*, 26(7), p.483-498.
- Thomas, T. and Zhang, X. (2000) 'Identifying unexpected accruals: a comparison of current approaches', *Journal of Accounting & Economics*, vol. 2, no. 1, p. 79-98.
- Thorne, L., Massey, D. and Maignan, M. (2003) 'Institutional context and auditors' moral reasoning: A Canada-. U.S.A. comparison', *Journal of Business Ethics*, 43(4), p. 305-321.
- Torchia, M., Calabro, A. and Huse, M. (2011) 'Women directors on corporate boards: From tokenism to critical mass', *Journal of Business Ethics*, 102, p. 299-317.
- Trautman, L. J., Butler, S., Chang, F. R., Hooper, M., McCray, R. and Simmons, R. (2022) 'Corporate Directors: Who They Are, What They Do, Cyber Risk and Other Challenges', *Buff. L. Rev.*, 70, p. 459.
- Tricker, A. (2009) *Essentials for Board Directors: An A-Z Guide*. Bloomberg Press, New York, NY
- Trinidad, C. and Normore, A. H. (2005) 'Leadership and Gender: A Dangerous Liaison?' *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 26(7), p. 574-90.
- Turner, L. E. and Godwin, J. H. (1999) 'Auditing, earnings management, and international accounting issues at the securities and exchange commission', *Accounting Horizons*, vol. 13, no. 3, p. 281-297.
- Turner, L. and Vann, E. (2010) 'Audit committee independence and earnings management: how independent are independent directors?' *Journal of Forensic & Investigative Accounting*, 2(3), p. 1-41.
- Uzun, H., Szweczyk, S. H. and Varma, R. (2004) 'Board composition and corporate fraud', *Financial Analysts Journal*, 60(3), p. 33-43.
- Vafeas, N. (2000) 'Board structure and the informativeness of earnings', *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 19(2), p. 139-160.
- Vafeas, N. and Theodorou, E. (1998) 'The relationship between board structure and firm performance in the UK', *The British Accounting Review*, 30(4), p. 383-407.
- Valaskova, K., Kliestik, T. and Kovacova, M. (2018) 'Management of financial risks in Slovak enterprises using regression analysis', *Oeconomia Copernicana*, 9(1), p. 105-121.
- Van den Berghe, L. A. A., and Baelden, T. (2005) 'The complex relation between director independence and board effectiveness', *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 5(5), pp.58-83.
- Vance, S. C. (1964) *Boards of directors: structures and performance* (Vol. 17), School of Business Administration, University of Oregon Press, Eugene, OR.

- Wahlen, J. M. (1994) 'The nature of information in commercial bank loan loss disclosures', *Accounting Review*, vol. 69, no. 3, p. 455-478.
- Wali, S. and Masmoudi, S. M. (2020) 'Internal control and real earnings management in the French context', *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*, 18(2), pp. 363-387.
- Wang, Y., Abbasi, K., Babajide, B. and Yekini, K. C. (2020) 'Corporate governance mechanisms and firm performance: evidence from the emerging market following the revised CG code', *Corporate Governance: The international journal of business in society*, 20(1), pp.158-174.
- Wang, R., Zhou, S. and Wang, T. (2020) 'Corporate governance, integrated reporting and the use of credibility-enhancing mechanisms on integrated reports', *European Accounting Review*, 29(4), pp. 631-663.
- Watts, R. L. and Zimmerman, J. L. (1978) 'Towards a positive theory of the determination of accounting standards', *Accounting Review*, vol. 53, no. 1, p. 112.
- Watts, R. L. and Zimmerman, J. L. (1986) *Positive accounting theory*. Prentice-Hall.
- Watts, R. L. and Zimmerman, J. L. (1990) 'Positive accounting theory: a ten year perspective', *Accounting Review*, vol. 65, no. 1, p. 131-156.
- Weir, C. and Laing, D. (2001) 'Governance structures, director independence and corporate performance in the UK', *European Business Review*, Vol. 13 No. 2, p. 86.
- Weisbach, M. (1988) 'Corporate governance', *The Yale Law Journal*, 93, p. 1197-1230.
- Weisbach, M. (1988) 'Outside directors and CEO turnover', *Journal of Financial Economics*, 20(1-2), p. 431-460.
- Williamson, O. (1981) 'The modern corporation: origins, evolution, attributes', *Journal of Economic Literature*, 19(4), p. 1537-1568.
- Williamson, O. E. (1988) 'Corporate finance and corporate governance', *The Journal of Finance*, 43(3), p. 567-591.
- Wright, C. J., Shaw, J. R. and Guan, L. (2006) 'Corporate governance and investor protection: earnings management in the U. K. and U. S', *Journal of International Accounting Research*, vol. 5, no. 1, p. 25-40.
- Wu, Y. W. (1997) 'Management buyouts and earnings management', *Journal of Accounting, Auditing, and Finance*, 12, p. 373-89.
- Wu, S., Chen, M. C. and Lee, P. C. (2016) 'Independent directors and earnings management: The moderating effects of controlling shareholders and the divergence of cash flow and control rights', *The North American Journal of Economics and Finance*, 35, p. 153-165.
- Xie, B., Davidson, W. N. and DaDalt, P. J. (2003) 'Earnings management and corporate governance: The role of the board and the audit committee', *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 9(3), p. 295-316.
- Yang, J. S. and Krishnan, J. (2005) 'Audit committees and quarterly earnings management', *International Journal of Auditing*, Vol. 9, p. 201-219.
- Yermack, D. (1996) 'Higher market value of companies with a small board of directors', *Journal of Financial Economics*, Vol. 40, p. 185-212.
- Young, S. (1999) 'Systematic measurement error in the estimation of discretionary accruals: An evaluation of alternative modelling procedures', *Journal of Business Finance and Accounting*, 26(7-8), p. 833-862.
- Young, S. (2000) 'The increasing use of non-executive directors: its impact on UK board structure and governance arrangements', *Journal of Business Finance and Accounting*, Vol 27, p. 1311-1342.
- Zalata, A. M., Ntim, C. G., Choudhry, T., Hassanein, A. and Elzahar, H. (2019) 'Female directors and managerial opportunism: Monitoring versus advisory female directors', *The Leadership Quarterly*, 30(5), p. 101309.
- Zang, A. Y. (2012) 'Evidence on the trade-off between real activities manipulation and accrual-based earnings management', *Accounting Review*, 87, p. 675-703.
- Zeitlin, M. (1976) 'On class theory of the large corporation: response to Allen', *American Journal of Sociology*, 81(4), p. 894-903.
- Zulfikar, R., Lukviarman, N., Suhardjanto, D., Ismail, T., Dwi Astuti, K. and Meutia, M. (2020) 'Corporate governance compliance in banking industry: The role of the board', *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 6(4), p. 137.